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Success factors of blended-learning systems from the perspective of students living in remote marginalized communities globally.

An evaluation of JWL´s higher education blended-learning system.

Course: eEducation 13

submitted by: Anna, Mayr, 11852409

Reviewer: Univ.-Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Stefan Oppl

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to identify the factors that determine the success of blended learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions situated globally.

A better understanding of the target-group-specific factors that impact the success of blended-learning systems in terms of satisfaction with the system and intention to continue using the system can help to achieve the goal of providing access to higher education to a wider range of youth in marginalized areas such as refugee camps. The method of a comparative literature analysis is used in this thesis to investigate the current state of research on the success factors of blended-learning systems. Based on the findings from the literature review, the research framework of Zhang & Dang, 2020 is chosen as the framework to be applied to the case study. In the context of Jesuit Worldwide Learning (JWL), an NGO that has been providing blended-learning programs for higher education in marginalized regions for more than 10 years, the quantitative investigation of the success factors is conducted through an online survey completed by students in marginalized regions in Afghanistan, Guyana, India, Iraq, Kenya, Malawi, Myanmar and Sri Lanka. The results reveal that the following factors influence the success of blended-learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions worldwide:

Intention to use the system for further courses, Satisfaction, Motivation, Teaching Method, Information Quality, System Quality, Service Quality, Media Richness, Task-Technology Fit, Blended-Learning-Flexibility, Learning Climate, Facilitator Characteristics and within JWL's context the hardware and internet connectivity. JWL specific conditions as well as the findings from the literature analysis are included in the interpretation of the results.

Kurzreferat

Das Ziel dieser Studie ist es, Faktoren zu identifizieren, die den Erfolg von Blended-Learning-Systemen aus der Perspektive von Studierenden in marginalisierten Regionen weltweit beeinflussen.

Ein besseres Verständnis der zielgruppenspezifischen Faktoren, die den Erfolg im Sinne der Zufriedenheit mit dem System und der Intention, das System weiterhin zu nutzen, beeinflussen, kann dazu beitragen, mehr Jugendlichen in marginalisierten Regionen wie Flüchtlingslagern Zugang zu Hochschulbildung zu ermöglichen.

Die Methode der komparativen Literaturanalyse wurde in dieser Arbeit verwendet, um den aktuellen Stand der Forschung zu den Erfolgsfaktoren von Blended-Learning-Systemen zu untersuchen. Basierend auf den Erkenntnissen aus der Literaturanalyse wurde das Forschungsmodell von Zhang & Dang, 2020 als Basismodell gewählt, welches dann in einer Fallstudie angewendet wurde. Im Kontext von Jesuit Worldwide Learning (JWL), einer NGO, die seit mehr als 10 Jahren mittels verschiedener Blended-Learning-Programme Hochschulbildung in marginalisierten Regionen anbietet, wurde die quantitative Untersuchung der Erfolgsfaktoren anhand einer Online-Umfrage durchgeführt. Deren Teilnehmende sind Studierende in marginalisierten Regionen in Afghanistan, Guyana, Indien, Irak, Kenia, Malawi, Myanmar und Sri Lanka. Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass folgende Faktoren den Erfolg von Blended-Learning-Systemen aus Sicht der Studierenden in marginalisierten Regionen weltweit beeinflussen:

Absicht, das System für weitere Kurse zu nutzen, Zufriedenheit, Motivation, Lehrmethode, Informationsqualität, Systemqualität, Servicequalität, Media Richness, Task-Technology-Fit, Blended-Learning-Flexibilität, Lernklima, Facilitator-Charakteristika und - im Kontext von JWL - die Hardware und Internetanbindung.

In die Interpretation der Ergebnisse fließen sowohl die JWL-spezifischen Rahmenbedingungen als auch die Erkenntnisse aus der Literaturanalyse ein.

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1 Higher Education at the Margins

When it comes to access to higher education, one group stands out as facing particularly challenging circumstances. Globally around 68.5 million people are either displaced within their home country or living in exile as refugees. (Federal Foreign Office et al., 2019) According to UNHCRs education report Refugee youth's first challenge is a lack of secondary schooling. Due to the challenging living conditions, there are very few secondary-school graduates. The proportion of women in particular is very low. But those who meet the entry requirements for higher education programs face even greater challenges. There are hardly any institutions that offer such programs in places that are accessible to refugees. Restrictions on the movement of stateless persons or national regulations that do not allow refugees to enroll in universities put higher education out of reach for many young refugees. Many of them have to work hard to support their families financially, and full-time courses of study, which are usually associated with high tuition fees, are therefore only affordable for a very small number of them. Girls and disabled people are even more challenged by those circumstances. In addition, the lack of internet connectivity and reliable power makes participating in higher education very difficult. (UNHCR, 2019, p. 13)

In 2019 a conference called "The Other 1 Percent" took place in Berlin. The title of this refugee institutions conference refers to the fact that only one per cent of refugees enrolled in tertiary education, compared to 37 per cent of young people worldwide (Federal Foreign Office et al., 2019).

As mentioned at the beginning, the technological change and digitalization in recent years offers the potential to mitigate at least some of these challenges. In their strategic report for refugee inclusion, the United Nations refugee agency UNHCR committed to the goal that 15% of refugee youth can access higher education by 2030. To reach this goal the UNHCR proposes five educational pathways which they aim to enforce. Their five-point strategy includes investigations in national enrollments, third country higher education pathways, technical and vocational education and training, scholarships and connected learning programs. (UNHCR, 2020b) The UNHCR promotes **connected learning** as an approach to enable students living in marginalized remote areas to enroll with top universities, by using IT technology and conducting onsite face-to-face learning. This approach, which merges online and face-face learning, is referred to synonymously as blended-learning throughout this paper, since blended-learning is the widely-used term in scientific e-learning literature. Since 2010, more than 25,000 refugee students spread over 23 countries have been participating in such technology-supported learning environments to study and share knowledge globally. (UNHCR, 2020a)

The digitalization of university teaching has been discussed for many years, and in particular the potential of media use in teaching has been discussed in numerous expert circles. Jürgen

Handke, who published several versions of his book on digital higher education, describes in the first pages of his most recent publication his experiences of the recent trends and developments in the field from the perspective of a German university. A radical rethinking of university teaching was requested by some experts in higher education and supported with numerous funding programs in order to open up to new teaching and learning approaches. At the same time, many lecturers preferred to ignore this topic. But at the beginning of 2020, with the Corona crisis, this suddenly changed. In an unprecedented real-time test, teachers were asked to switch to digital teaching immediately. What had previously been considered as impossible, now had to be made possible. In the process, it became clear to many lecturers, professors and students what had been missed over the years. The technological possibilities had been available for a long time. The question of how successful digitally-supported teaching is conceived and carried out has hardly been taken into account so far. (Handke, 2020, pp. 1–7)

On the other hand, the digitalization of university teaching that was suddenly triggered in this way also brought new flexibility for students. On-site presence on campus was no longer required. In a way, the digitalization of higher education has also facilitated access for non-traditional students. Accessibility of higher education adapted to the needs of the target group is very important to reach students in their everyday lives.

From the point of view of the potential of technologies in the field of education discussed at the beginning, it seems particularly promising to take a closer look at the expansion of blended-learning programs. How could such blended-learning programs develop to contribute to the goal of enrolling 15% of refugees in higher education by 2030? How can these technology-enhanced learning environments be designed to address the challenges that create barriers which prevent youth in the refugee context from participating in tertiary education? To understand how these learning environments can be designed in the best possible way, it is advisable to take a closer look at the critical factors influencing the success of digitally supported learning environments. In the current research literature on the success factors of e-learning systems, some well-researched focus issues are visible. The whole development of technology-enhanced learning is still very young and in the beginning was developed in a very technology-focused way. For example, the agglomerations around the technology acceptance research which emerged since Davis published a widely-used research framework in 1989 (Davis et al., 1989). Another example is the system success perspective which became popular especially with an update of the model of DeLone and McLean around 2003 (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003). Since then, numerous links between the approaches have developed. Over time, explanatory approaches from other disciplines have been brought in to better explain the social and human influences that are essential to the learning process. Throughout this process in this landscape, e-learning-specific aspects in particular emerged as central points of interconnections. Especially the blended learning concept mentioned in the connected learning approach, which gained more

and more importance as a promising concept. Over the years, several influencing factors have been found to be significant across numerous studies and applications of blended learning scenarios. This has led to the development of comprehensive research designs. However, even though these approaches have largely been tested in several cases, factors influencing specific target groups, such as globally mixed student groups or refugee students, have hardly been examined.

The aim of this thesis is to identify criteria which will help JWL and other providers of blended learning programs to address the needs of students in marginalized areas. This in the end should contribute to facilitating access to higher education for young refugees and thus contribute to improving opportunities in line with the UNHCR's goal.

Therefore, this master thesis addresses the following research question: What are the success criteria of a blended learning system, for students situated in marginalized regions around the world?

This research question leads to several sub-questions which will be addressed by several steps and research methods throughout this thesis. As a first step, the current state literature should be analyzed to find out **which factors have an influence on the success of blended learning systems according to the current state of research**. This should include the analysis of the development of research perspectives over time and therewith also the development of the research stage on impacting factors. Further, a wide range of analyzed use cases should be taken into account to include global perspectives. The impact factors found through this process will help to determine a current blended learning research design that is appropriate for the research conducted as part of this thesis.

To evaluate the success factors from the perspective of students living in marginalized areas, such as in a refugee context, a user evaluation needs to be conducted to examine **which of the success criteria of the elaborated research framework are of relevance from the perspective of students all around the globe living in a marginalized context?**

As one of key drivers of blended-learning in marginalized areas, the nongovernmental organization Jesuit Worldwide Learning (JWL) is widely known. Furthermore, JWL is part of the Connected Learning in Crisis Consortium. Due to the longstanding cooperation with UNHCR and the Higher Education Programs, JWL is quite appropriate as a use case with the research that is taking place in the broader context of UNHCR's mission. The UNHCR web page on connected higher education shows a quote from a student, Mariam, who lives in Kakuma refugee camp in Kenya and was enrolled in JWL Diploma courses in Liberal Studies. She appreciates the opportunity for remote participation in the university program. (UNHCR, 2020a)

JWL has offered higher education programs for marginalized communities since 2010. Since 2018, the author of this thesis has been working on several projects as course designer for JWL. From this experience, the author is very familiar with JWL's course program, and therefore decided to evaluate the professional certificate programs, which are the well-established blended learning programs. These programs have been running since 2018. In total 478 students from all over the world have been participating so far and could therefore participate in the online survey. The JWL Professional Certificate Course is particularly suitable as a research context for this work due to its blended-learning design and its students from marginalized regions around the world.

This thesis is structured as follows; in the first part the aspects of the research question are characterized in more detail. First, the target group from whose point of view the research takes place and their challenges with regard to higher education are introduced. Then, initiatives in the context of technology-enhanced learning for marginalized target groups are outlined and the blended-learning approach is presented as one of the most effective e-learning approaches. In the last section of the first chapter, digital learning environments are distinguished and a common understanding for this thesis is created. In the second chapter, the case study on which this thesis is based is presented in more detail. In the first section, the work of the organization Jesuit Worldwide Learning (JWL) is presented as an example of how higher education at the margins can work. Then, the group of students studied in the empirical part, and the blended learning programs which they attend, are briefly presented. The third chapter deals with a comparative analysis of the current state of the research literature on system success factors. First, basic perspectives of research on technological systems and their success factors are presented. In addition to these approaches, case studies from the field of e-learning and the further development of models in this area are also discussed. After summarizing the e-learning-specific factors from the literature point of view, the further specialized search is directed towards research models that have investigated blended-learning success factors, because the aim of this literature analysis is to find a suitable current research tool. Subsequently, the choice of a comprehensive blended-learning system success model is justified, and the categories and factors investigated with it are presented and related to the case study. The fourth chapter describes the research method. The approach to the different aspects of comparative literature analysis, questionnaire development, and qualitative investigation of the system improvement proposals is discussed. In chapter five, the results of all parts of the research are presented in detail. Chapter six is the discussion of the results in terms of supports and contradictions from the literature analysis. Finally, in the conclusion, the results are summarized, practice implications are derived, the limitations of the thesis are described, and next research steps are identified. Chapter eight contains the bibliography and the ninth section contains the appendix.

1.1 Challenges and barriers to access higher education from the perspective of students in marginalized regions around the globe

This thesis addresses the factors that determine the success of blended learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions around the world. In order to address this question, it should first be clarified whose perspective is being taken. In order to understand why certain factors are important from the perspective of this target group, it is important to first look at the challenges and problems of accessing higher education from the perspective of the target group. Only with the challenges of the target group in mind, is it possible to understand the differences in the evaluation of success-critical factors to results which occur in such evaluations in other groups of students.

The term **at the margins** in this paper is used to delineate the research perspective and should in no way represent a discrimination. **At the margins** refers to people, especially youth, at the margins of society, due to poverty, living in low-resource environments and locations, experiencing a lack of opportunities, forced displacement or conflict. The aim is, thus to draw attention to the different framework conditions of the studies. Especially when talking about students in marginalized regions, this term should not discriminate but rather draw attention to a group of students who face great challenges in gaining access to higher education. Refugees are particularly underrepresented in higher education programs because they face particular challenges in accessing higher education. Many authors address refugees' challenges for a more equal access to higher education (Brugha & Hollow, 2017; Federal Foreign Office et al., 2019; Gladwell et al., 2016b; UNESCO, 2018). Refugees are therefore particularly included in the term students from marginalized communities used in this thesis. But other groups of young people who, because they live in marginalized regions, and similarly face challenges in access to higher education are also considered in this paper. The term **students in marginalized regions** should include both groups. So as not to discriminate against anyone, the group of students in marginalized regions will not be further specified here according to regional or similar criteria. Students with special needs should not be neglected in the discussion of equitable access to higher education, but since the study of success factors from the perspective of diversity and inclusion is a very broad field of research and beyond the scope of this paper, it will not be specifically addressed here.

Jigsaw Consult published a report in 2016 that provides a comprehensive mapping of programs that offer higher education for refugees, the landscape review (Gladwell et al., 2016a, p. 56). One of the conclusions that relates to how learning technology needs to be designed in order to enable good practices is: "Effective integration of technology that is appropriate for the operating context" (Gladwell et al., 2016a, p. 56). By evaluating the success factors of blended learning

systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions, this thesis aims to contribute to the creation of such an appropriate learning system.

Looking at the challenges of refugees and people living in marginalized regions in terms of access to higher education as documented in reports, different levels can be identified.

Higher level challenges and barriers to be addressed by global initiatives.

On the one hand, there are challenges that arise from the education systems, and on the other hand, there are challenges that arise from the education levels (UNESCO, 2018, p. 14). These problems are only briefly touched upon here, as they have to be addressed at a higher level from international institutions due to their complexity and interconnectedness and cannot be addressed by a learning system. Young people who, due to their living conditions, cannot study at traditional higher education institutions often lack an overview of the alternatives and programs available to them (Gladwell et al., 2016a, p. 12).

Another problem is the insufficient documentation of degrees and the problem of credit transfer to other institutions. This poses a great challenge to refugees and other students who cannot study permanently at one institution. (Gladwell et al., 2016a, p. 12; UNESCO, 2018, p. 14)

Many young people in marginalized regions cannot afford to pay the tuition fees, as they have to use the money primarily to ensure the survival of their families. Refugees in particular are often seen as international students in the host countries and have to pay high tuition fees and do not receive any state funding because they are not citizens of the country. (Gladwell et al., 2016a, p. 12; UNHCR, 2019, p. 13)

But also the access requirements to higher education programs are a barrier (UNESCO, 2018, p. 14).

The requirement of having completed secondary school limits potential students for higher education programs in marginalized regions. Only a limited number of youth fulfill the entrance qualifications. Many young people struggling to survive with their families do not invest as many years in their education. Especially within the group of girls, few reached a sufficient secondary schooling level and therefore girls are even more underrepresented in higher education programs. (Gladwell et al., 2016a, p. 12; UNESCO, 2018, p. 14; UNHCR, 2019, p. 13)

Many programs also require a certain level of English skills, which is a barrier for many students who cannot invest the time and money to reach the appropriate English levels. (Gladwell et al., 2016a, pp. 12–13; UNESCO, 2018, p. 14)

Individual challenges and barriers for students in marginalized regions

The focus of this paper is not on the previously mentioned challenges and barriers that prevent youth in marginalized regions from having an equal access to higher education, but rather on the challenges that students face due to their individual situation in marginalized regions once

a higher education program is offered, and especially to which challenges this program needs to be adapted to enable students to participate successfully.

These problems of the target group can be classified into problems regarding distance, special challenges for women and the lack of learning communities and self-confidence.

Distance

In the UNHCR report on strategies for refugee education until 2030, the distance and the low number of higher education institutions in accessible places are mentioned as challenges in the field of tertiary education. In marginalized regions, there are hardly any on-site universities. Campus universities are often located only in larger metropolitan areas. On the one hand, refugees cannot overcome these distances due to movement restrictions in camps, and on the other hand, many young people in marginalized regions whose families depend on them to contribute to feeding their families cannot leave their relatives on their own. The family's financial sustainability has higher priority than higher education. (UNHCR, 2019, p. 13)

Special challenges for women

The responsibility for domestic and childcare tasks often falls on women, leaving them with even less time or opportunity to participate in educational programs. In addition to this challenge, the Jigsaw Consult report identifies the early marriage of women in many cultures, the lack of access to sanitary products and, in particular, a lack of self-confidence among women as major challenges for women to participate in higher education programs. (Gladwell et al., 2016a, p. 13)

JWL's experience has also shown that the long distances to learning centers are dangerous, particularly for women, and thus hinder them even more to attend higher education programs (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020).

The lack of learning communities and self-confidence

Students from remote rural areas often face feelings of isolation and a lack of peers struggling for the same aim, to support each other in their higher education programs (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020). In the landscape review by Jigsaw Consult, one of the key conclusions for higher education programs for refugees was that with regard to the pedagogical approach, "significant levels of non-academic support provided to students to help in their studies" (Gladwell et al., 2016a, p. 56) are crucial. The significance of social embeddedness and the importance of the role of a facilitator, for the students' motivation and the success of learning is also emphasized in the publication of Looser (Looser, 2011, p. 234). Thus, the lack of these learning communities and support persons represents a major challenge for students in marginalized regions (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020). For refugees, the conflict in their countries of origin often means that they have to interrupt their education and are often out of education for many years during the time of flight. They need even more support to try a new start. Often the lack of self-confidence of the students is a barrier to participation in higher education programs. (Gladwell et al., 2016a, pp. 12–13)

Many of these challenges can be addressed through learning technologies. In its report - A lifeline to learning, leveraging technology to support education for refugees - UNESCO describes the opportunities for overcoming these challenges through technology-supported learning environments. The next section briefly outlines the approaches that can be taken. Before that, however, the challenges that arise when using technology-supported learning environments for higher education programs in marginalized regions should be outlined here.

Challenges for technology-based higher education programs in marginalized regions

To see learning technologies as a solution to overcome some of the challenges and barriers faced by students to attend higher education programs in marginalized regions, it is necessary to adapt the learning technologies to the specific requirements. Students in marginalized regions frequently face the lack of reliable electricity or power supply. Furthermore, in many remote rural areas and even in refugee camps, the lack of reliable and continuous internet connectivity challenges students. In addition, a lack of availability and maintenance of appropriate devices for studying should be taken into account. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020; UNESCO, 2018, p. 13)

In summary, there are numerous barriers for students in marginalized regions to access higher education. When offering higher education programs for students in marginalized regions, it is important to ensure that these programs address the challenges faced by the target group. Possible solutions to overcome these challenges will be explained in the following section.

1.2 Learning technologies enabling youth in marginalized and less-developed regions to access higher education

In various areas of life, technologies are promising new ways to overcome challenges and barriers.

“The vastly use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to develop human resources (people) is essential in order to develop a knowledge based economy, particularly in developing countries” (Ghazal, Aldowah, et al., 2018, p. 688).

The potential of ICT to overcome the challenges mentioned in the previous section with regard to access to higher education for young people in marginalized regions is therefore briefly outlined here.

Digitalization has a high impact on higher education accessibility. Higher education is more flexible if digital solutions are implemented. In traditional university frameworks, students must pause their studying in case of illness, pregnancy or staying abroad. Digitally-supported flexible lectures allow students to continue studying in such cases. Internet platforms enable access to high quality learning materials for free. The generation of digital native students isn't limited to

access scientific content and research findings only through traditional higher education institutions anymore. (Handke, 2020, pp. 24–36)

The problem of distance, which prevents many young people in marginalized regions from studying at campus universities, can be overcome in the age of digitalization by bringing the learning content directly to the students, no matter where they live, through technological solutions. This saves many long and potentially dangerous journeys. These are often a particular problem for women. The use of technology thus allows decentralized study and offers students more flexibility. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

The authors Ghazal & Al-Samarraie, et al. also address this enormous advantage of technology-supported higher education offerings in their publication on the success factors for promoting students' experience and satisfaction in a blended learning environment, which they evaluated in Yemen.

„E-learning has the potential to promote self-directed learning by increasing students access to information, increasing interactivity between student and teacher, improving collaborative efforts, eliminating geographical barriers, and building self-confidence“ (Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018, p. 77179).

However, challenges with regard to technology implementation in marginalized regions remain for the time being. It is more a matter of developing a technological system to enable learning that overcomes these challenges.

Technology-based learning cannot be viewed only as a great opportunity in principle, especially for marginalized target groups; it also works in practical implementation. This is shown in the example of the largest university in the world (Montgomery, 2021), the Indira Gandhi National Open University in India (IGNOU), where a huge number of students are already studying in a blended learning context. Half of the higher education students in India are studying via a distance education system and fifteen percent of all Indian higher education students are studying via distance learning at IGNOU. The organizational structure of IGNOU is based on more than 60 regional centers and over 2600 study centers. Students go to these decentralized learning centers to participate in face-face teaching sessions or videoconferences, or to access multimedia learning content, the online library, or materials in the format of CDs and DVDs. They also attend exams and hold presentations there. In this way, the entire learning process is covered by a blended learning approach. That enables access to higher education in a blended learning context for a huge amount of students even in less-developed and marginalized regions. (Seraji, 2017, p. 13)

Technology-enhanced learning opportunities are a promising approach to overcoming the challenges identified in section 1.1. This can be seen from the results and the practical example within this section. The following section explains the framework conditions that these e-learning offerings should fulfill from the perspective of current research.

1.3 Blended Learning - attempting a definition for a promising e-learning approach for higher education at the margins

The dynamics of technological change are also reflected in the development of digital learning environments, so there are multiple approaches for technology-supported learning. Which of them are relevant in the context of students in marginalized regions has been analyzed by UNESCO.

“Mirroring a broader trend, the use of massive open online courses (MOOCs) has also started to flourish in refugee higher education settings. However, the analysis shows that the success of digital learning courses in refugee higher education contexts has little to do with magnitude, openness, or exclusively online delivery. Instead, digital higher education courses tend to be most valuable if they are connected with blended learning approaches that provide additional online and offline learning and support structures, and if they are integrated into a broader curriculum that leads to certification and degrees.” (UNESCO, 2018, p. 6)

Especially institutions offering educational programs for non-traditional students such as students working in full-time jobs try to meet their students' needs by implementing e-learning programs (Sun et al., 2008, p. 1196). Blended-learning programs with reduced scheduled presence time are an approach to overcome the conflict of interest between employment and education, by meeting students' needs with the advantage of more flexibility in how to organize study time. Since these arguments show that in the context of higher education programs for students in marginalized regions blended-learning programs are the most effective, the question remains what exactly is meant by a blended-learning program and how do these programs differ from other e-learning programs.

According to Arnold et al. blended-learning can be seen as a special format of e-learning courses (Arnold et al., 2018, p. 22). But this does not explain which e-learning courses and technology-supported learning approaches are covered by the term 'blended learning'. Meena & Vasantha describe blended learning in their publication as combination of technology adaption and traditional methods for learning. Blended learning makes the digital learning approach more personalized by combining online resources with in-person instruction. (Meena & Vasantha, 2018, p. 1894) Definitions like these can be found often in the current literature. Graham C.R. looked at the numerous definitions of blended learning and derived four contentious issues that are repeatedly addressed in the definitions.

Firstly, what is 'blended'? Is it the online and face-face learning sessions or the instructional modalities such as the delivery media or is it the instructional methods? The author gives a clear answer to this question, which is also valid in the context of this thesis. 'Blended' refers to the

mixing of online and face-to-face learning phases, because the mixing of delivery media or instructional methods also takes place in all conventional classroom teaching and thus everything would otherwise become blended learning. Another point in many definitions is the question whether a blended-learning program changes the contact or seat time compared to the same offer in the traditional approach? Or whether the addition of a face-to-face introductory session to an online program makes it a blended learning program? Within the case study and thus the empirical part of this work, blended learning is understood as replacing the input phase of a traditional class with online learning, while collaborative learning phases in the traditional sense take place face-to-face in so-called in-class meetings. The next point of discussion is the question of what percentage of online learning is required or acceptable for a program to be called blended learning. Some authors agreed on 30%-80% online learning. How meaningful such strict specifications are remains controversial. Within this work, however, this understanding of 30-80% online learning can be used. The fourth issue in the various definitions is whether the quality and thus the pedagogical value is one of the criteria in a definition of blended learning. In the framework of this thesis, which is based on the case study of JWL, the empirical part is based on the understanding of blended-learning resulting from the pedagogical approach of the so called Ignatian Pedagogy, which has proven itself for many years in Jesuit education (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020). Thus, the blended learning approach is in a way based on a pedagogical concept. Therefore, the context-related definition includes this specification of the quality aspect. These aspects are interpreted differently depending on the institution, and thus it is possible that the examples presented in the literature analysis are based on different definitions of the aspects of blended learning. Because, as the author Graham proves with numerous sources, blended learning is seen on the general level as a vaguely limiting construct, which each institution designs in an individual sense and strictly delimits for its own context. (Graham, 2013, pp. 3–7)

In summary, the projects observed by UNESCO show that higher education for refugees is successful when it is based on blended learning and thus on different offline and online learning phases. The successful projects also incorporated basic concepts of learner-centered pedagogies such as social inclusion, peer learning, and mentoring. (UNESCO, 2018, p. 7)

To enable this kind of e-learning experience the blended-learning system needs to be more than just an information system, and therefore the term blended-learning system will be understood not only as information or learning management system within this thesis. How this blended-learning system is structured and designed will be explained in the following section. In dept understanding of JWLs blended-learning system is required to better understand the research results and to be able to interpret them.

1.4 The fusion of pedagogical orientation and comprehensive blended-learning systems

Each target group is unique and “E-learning system adoption is not a one-size-fits-all approach that is applied equally among stakeholders located throughout the world (Bhuasiri et al., 2012, p. 850).” Therefore, each target group needs an individual e-learning approach. As the last chapters have explained in detail, based on current research findings and experiences, it is assumed that blended learning systems based on a pedagogical concept are the most appropriate to design successful higher education programs for students in marginalized regions worldwide.

Adopting a pedagogical approach to reflect the target group’s learning needs is not only relevant in the context of higher education for students in marginalized regions, but the authors of the report on Refugee Higher Education and Employability see it as an approach that could also be seen as a global trend.

“Employment-sensitive curriculum and pedagogy is one area in which the refugee higher education context reflects and can contribute to the development of global trends in higher education” (Brugha & Hollow, 2017, p. 19).

Even though this work is about examining success factors of a system from the perspective of a specific target group, it should not be a purely technical approach of information system success evaluation, due to the numerous arguments for the important role of a pedagogical-based approach. Therefore, blended-learning characteristics should also be included in the system evaluation. The term blended-learning system is understood holistically for a learning management system which is adapted to the pedagogical principles of blended learning. For example, it allows features such as mentoring or interaction with peers. At the same time it is important to distinguish that this work is not about the factors that enable the establishment of successful higher education programs, but about the factors that relate to the blended-learning system. So it should be clear that this thesis considers the impact factors of a technical system, but also takes into account factors that are related to aspects of the pedagogical concept. For such blended-learning systems, success criteria will be evaluated. The success of a system is defined within the perspective of the empiric investigation of this thesis as a system that satisfies students and motivates students to intend to take more courses using this system.

Internet technology provides access to a huge number of learning resources for students’ self-paced learning. Geographical boundaries are less limiting than internet accessibility in this context. Internet-based features can be used for instructional purposes to enable interactive and collaborative learning by distance. Software solutions like wikis, video-conferences, chat, forums, collaborative documents and cloud technology are adding further aspects of flexibility in

digital higher education. (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020, p. 68) Digital learning environments combining these aspects are needed to enable access to higher education free of barriers. But just providing technological solutions to access higher education is not enough. Jürgen Handke formulated theses to define a framework for the success of a future-oriented digitalization of teaching. In one of his theses he refers to the statement of Aaron Sams during the 1st Inverted Classroom Conference in 2012 in Marburg, “Didactics / pedagogy must drive technology and not vice versa” (Handke, 2020, p. 4) Connecting this statement to the discussion on equal accessibility of higher education, technological approaches to designing a digital learning environment need to be guided by instructional design perspective. (Handke, 2020, p. 12) Positive aspects of digitalization in higher education such as flexibility and accessibility are based on a well-designed digital learning environment: A blended-learning system which includes pedagogical aspects as well as technological functionalities. Which criteria lead to success of such systems will be addressed in this research.

2 Blended learning in the case study of JWL Professional Certificate Programs

This thesis aims to investigate the success factors of blended-learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions globally. The results of this evaluation might contribute to the efforts of “UNHCR’s 15by30 strategy, aiming to increase the percentage of refugee youth accessing higher education from 3% to 15% by 2030” (Connected Learning in Crisis Consortium, 2020a, p. UNHCR), as connected higher education is one pillar of the UNHCR’s strategy to reach this goal. Connected learning programs are initiated by the Connected Learning in Crisis Consortium. This collaboration between various institutions and organizations,

“aims to promote, coordinate, collaborate and/or support the provision of quality higher education in contexts of conflict, crisis and displacement through connected learning by sharing and disseminating knowledge, experience and evidence; developing innovative and good practice; and ensuring accountability to students and their communities in order to foster self-reliance.” (Connected Learning in Crisis Consortium, 2020b)

The UNHCR’s web page on tertiary education and focus area on connected higher education starts with a quote from a student from Kakuma refugee camp who is enrolled in a connected learning program.

““This JWL program is excellent and I am very grateful to all who have supported it,” says Mariam, 22, a refugee who enrolled in the Diploma of Liberal Studies offered by Jesuit Worldwide Learning in Kakuma. “I cannot relocate to go to university, in Nairobi for instance, but this special opportunity allows me to study here in Kakuma, near my family.” (UNHCR, 2020a)

JWL is the abbreviation for Jesuit Worldwide Learning, a global humanitarian organization offering a diverse range of higher education courses for young people aged 18 and above with the aim of fostering higher education at the margins (Jesuit Worldwide Learning, 2020). As this quote shows, JWL is fitting as a case study for the connected learning initiative. The research to evaluate the blended-learning success criteria will be conducted within the context of JWL.

In the following chapter, firstly the NGO JWL is presented in more detail. Starting with the vision and inspiration, the mission and implementation in practice will be explained in order to get a complete picture of an established connected learning initiative. Subsequently, the chapters specify in more detail the framework in which the empirical part of the research into the previous question will be carried out. For this purpose, the investigated programs and their frameworks are defined and the structure of the target group is described in more detail from the perspective of which the factors are evaluated. In particular, the blended learning system of JWL with all system aspects will be discussed in detail. Thus, a concrete case study of the blended learning systems at the center of this thesis is presented.

Subsequently, section 2.1.3 specifies in more detail the framework in which the empirical part of the research into the previous question will be carried out. For this purpose, the investigated programs and their frameworks are defined and the structure of the target group is described in more detail from the perspective of which the factors are evaluated. Thus, the perspective of students in marginalized regions worldwide, as stated in the research question, is defined more precisely.

The author of this thesis has been working on the continuous development of JWL's blended-learning system for many years. The information on the JWL case study is described from the author's own experience and is also partly adapted from the publicly available summary "Growing Global Higher Education at the Margins - Understanding JWL's blended mobile learning model" (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020) in which text sections written by the author of this thesis were also published.

2.1 JWL - Higher Education at the Margins

Jesuit Worldwide Learning vision is

"Learning together to transform the world. JWL believes that tertiary learning and the formation of a global community of learners addresses the root causes of poverty, isolation, despair, conflict and displacement in order to build a more peaceful and humane world. JWL knows education fosters hope." (Jesuit Worldwide Learning, 2020)

Therefore, JWL instils the Jesuit tradition of critical thinking, reconciliation, justice, and care for our environment, forming youth at the margins to become leaders for the sustainable

development goals. Through a scalable model of mobile blended learning that is informed by research and leverages technology, breaks down barriers to higher education, learners gain access to global education that enables them to transform themselves and their communities. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

Since this thesis conducts research on the success factors of blended learning systems in the context of JWL in order to answer its research question, this chapter describes the NGO JWL in more detail. Starting from the preceding vision, the mission of JWL is outlined briefly in section 2.1.1. How it is possible to implement this mission is then explained in section 2.1.2. The understanding of the mission and the network that enables the implementation is necessary to get the background for the next chapter, the implementation of JWL's mission. This implementation manifests in the blended learning system that is evaluated from the students' point of view and is therefore the focus of this thesis.

2.1.1 Inspiration, mission and direction of the operations

The reference point of JWL's work is the Universal Apostolic Preferences of the Society of Jesus. The new Preferences published in 2019 are four areas vital for our world today and will be introduced briefly in the following section to get an understanding of the mission and vision of JWL. That is important to understand the context of the case study.

Walking with the excluded

The first Preference is walking with the excluded, what is understood as the call to walk with the poor, the outcasts of the world, those whose dignity has been violated, in a mission of reconciliation and justice. (Curia Generalizia della Compagnia di Gesù, 2019)

Therefore the NGO focuses on socially and geographically marginalized communities, refugees, forcibly displaced and conflict-affected communities; tribal communities; people deprived of their freedom and dignity, and especially also women. Their programs mainly take place in regions and countries with a low Human Development Index, with low education and often with high level of conflicts, social and environmental degradation. JWL collaborates with Jesuit Universities and other higher education institutions to help them to engage with the excluded communities and Jesuit institutions serving the poor. Through this approach the Universities in collaboration with JWL serve local communities with tertiary learning and form a global community of learners in the virtual class promoting global thinking and local action. The aim of this approach is to form in excluded communities civil and political leaders in a mission of reconciliation, justice, and peace. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

Journeying with youth

The second Preference is journeying with youth, which is understood as accompanying young people in the creation of a hope-filled future. (Curia Generalizia della Compagnia di Gesù, 2019) Therefore, based on the Jesuit tradition, JWL has made it its mission to work with young people in excluded communities facilitating high-quality tertiary education through blended mobile learning. The focus on education builds on 470 years' tradition of Jesuit Education and formation of youth. Which is understood within the Jesuits as integral education and formation of the head, heart and hands. The organization has decided to take advantage of the benefits of digitalization and therefore they are using innovative methodology and learning technologies. The concept of the NGO is to provide hardware and internet connectivity through Local Learning Centers based on the decentralized and globally established Jesuit network. In addition, the offers are designed in such a way that they can be accessed on a wide range of end devices, including personal devices. That enables youth to study in low-connectivity contexts, learning anytime and anywhere. In this way, the organization provides the network, infrastructure, and administration to give young people the opportunity to access global learning pathways of high-quality language, higher education courses with transferable credits and degrees. Furthermore, JWL understands from this apostolic preference that young people themselves can develop this network of learning centers and thus create future perspectives for themselves and their community. That is why the NGO has aligned its activities in the sense that it empowers youth to carry their education forward and to open new learning centers in their communities. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

Caring for our common home

The third Preference is caring for our common home. Which means to collaborate for the protection and renewal of God's creation. (Curia Generalizia della Compagnia di Gesù, 2019) From this Apostolic Preference JWL takes the call to promote a global conscience about the value of creation of our world. They aim to create awareness of the care of our common home, in the sense of environmental and social sustainability. Therefore JWL develops and implements higher education programs and Technical Vocational Education Training (TVET) in the sphere of sustainable development. For example, JWLs most intensive higher education program: the Bachelor in Sustainable Development, which JWL offers in collaboration with the Xavier University in Bhubaneswar in India and Hekima University in Nairobi. JWL takes it as their challenging task to create courses that not only bring the latest knowledge but also integrate the latent knowledge and experience in (indigenous) communities. In this way, the organization aims to contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations. So JWL sees it as their mission with this approach to form community leaders to take an integral approach towards sustainable and peaceful communities.(Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

Showing the way into other-centeredness

The fourth Preference is the transformation from self-centeredness into other-centeredness through discernment. (Curia Generalizia della Compagnia di Gesù, 2019)

With all its educational programs, the NGO JWL therefore tries to foster critical thinking and to create the intellectual environment that favors free personal learning processes, which are independent of social, ethnic or religious pressure. JWL relies on a transformative pedagogical approach, Ignatian pedagogy, to promote action-oriented learning along the way. From JWL's point of view, action-oriented learning is the best approach to initiate sustainable learning processes in the students. Therefore, all courses offered by JWL are designed according to the principles of Ignatian pedagogy. This means that all courses have a consistent didactic approach. It is also very important to JWL to take from this Preference the mission to foster the students' spiritual dimension in their own specific culture and belief systems by offering courses of interreligious, intercultural ethical values and dialogue of mutual respect as this offers a deeper alternative to secularization. JWL's higher education programs are an approach to offer accompaniment for young people intellectually as they make complex decisions in the social, economic, cultural, religious, and political spheres. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

2.1.2 A network of collaboration partners enables JWL's work

In order to understand how higher education at the margins is realized at JWL, it is important to first provide a brief overview of how this vision is made possible from an organizational perspective. JWL relies on a strong network of partnerships to achieve its vision.

Jesuit Worldwide Learning works with Jesuit as well as other mission-aligned universities and educational institutions. These culturally rich and diverse institutions share their resources with Jesuit Worldwide Learning in order to make higher quality higher education programs accessible to others who would not otherwise have the opportunity. In this collaborative effort, universities contribute their subject matter knowledge, professors to accompany students as online facilitators, the accreditation of courses to enable students to reach credits, certificates and degrees of renowned universities. In the field, JWL works with the Jesuit Provinces and institutions, and other like-minded organizations who already work closely with the urban and rural poor, the displaced, and other socially and geographically marginalized communities. The operational partners contribute with infrastructure and management of community learning centers, and on site accompany students at the margins by facilitating students learning. As JWL's vision and mission also speak to and further the achievement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), JWL also partner with the United Nations, especially at the local level. As JWL serve refugees and internally-displaced persons in both camp and urban settings, UNHCR is a natural partner as well as non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and community-based organizations. Furthermore, JWL collaborates with technology partners to be able to deliver higher education at the margins. Beyond students having access to devices to study wherever

they may be, partnerships with Seitwerk GmbH for the development and sustained management of our Student Information System (SIS), Learning Management System (LMS) and blended-learning courses took place. Through innovative technology, the system works both on and offline, meeting several of our students' needs. As regards finance, JWL's work is mainly supported by public and private foundations, and corporate entities. Not to be overlooked as collaborative partners are, of course, the students themselves. The transformative education provided by JWL guides and enables learners to grow into men and women for others, to become leaders who serve and lift their communities. Throughout their studies, they cultivate this sense of commitment, engagement, and ownership not only of their success but also that of their peers, the learning environment, and the surrounding community. They translate their knowledge and skills into action as individuals and/or as part of a student-based organization, testing and developing their leadership skills as they support the education of others as mentors or learning facilitators, for example. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

2.1.3 JWL's approach for practical implementation of higher education at the margins

The author of this thesis has been working on the continuous development of this blended learning system for many years. This section is summarized from her own experience, therefore no sources are mentioned.

First, the central concepts and cornerstones of JWL's blended learning system are explained. This includes the functionalities of the LMS as well as instructional design principles that have an influence on the design and flow of the programs at JWL due to the transformative approach of JWL's pedagogy. The term blended-learning system at JWL always refers to the entire system that is designed according to the transformative approach and used in the blended-learning courses, so this includes the technical system the LMS as well as organizational system parts like support and instructional design elements. JWL's blended learning system does include several aspects like online and onsite learning components as well as the anchoring of the blended learning structure in the overall system. Due to this strong integration of onsite face-to-face and online learning phases, the JWL concept corresponds to the definition of blended learning described in section 1.3 and is therefore suitable for further consideration as a case study for blended learning systems. The system components will be explained in more detail in the following section.

Onsite Learning

The concept of JWL relies on infrastructure and a strong on-site network. The learning centers, which are often operated by alumni or students, act self-organized under the umbrella of JWL

country representatives, so they can react independently and quickly to individual circumstances on site. In this way, JWL offers students a point of contact and a reliable partner for all their needs related to their higher education programs. At the start of each course, students from different regions around the world can apply via their centers. JWL makes sure that at least a small learning group of students from each location comes together. Each of these onsite learning groups usually meets twice a week. This is incorporated into the course design of all JWL courses by providing activities and suggestions to be done during these meetings. Ideally, these so-called in-class meetings take place throughout the week, for example on Tuesdays and Thursdays for around one hour per meeting. The in-class meetings are organized and led at all learning centers by learning group facilitators employed by JWL. The learning group facilitators are called Onsite Facilitators by JWL and usually do not have a course-specific subject matter background, as the subject matter support is not their responsibility either. The task of the onsite facilitator is to support the learning process of the students on site, to motivate them, to enable them to access the digital learning materials and to encourage continuous learning. This includes organizing the meetings and coordinating with the learning center coordinator to ensure that a room is available for the in-class meeting at their local learning center. In addition, it is their responsibility to make sure that the students have access to a PC, laptop or tablet with internet access and manage to access the learning materials. During the in-class meetings it is the responsibility of the onsite facilitator to make sure that the collaborative tasks are completed, to encourage the exchange between the students of the local learning group about the learning material and to listen to the problems of the students, and if necessary to mediate to the contact person at JWL, for example if a student is sick for a long time or has to withdraw from a course. The onsite facilitators are also responsible for establishing contact with the students. If, for example, a student is inactive for a long time with regard to the submissions on the online learning platform, it is the onsite facilitator's responsibility to find out the reasons for this and to coordinate the further steps with JWL.

As already mentioned, there is usually also a center coordinator on site at each learning center. In small centers, the roles of onsite facilitator and coordinator are sometimes held by the same person. In larger learning centers, the coordinator is responsible for the administration of all student groups and facilitators, coordinating with JWL in Geneva and Munich on upcoming program launches, application processes and center hardware equipment. In most countries where JWL centers are established, there are also JWL country representatives who constitute a further organizational level. A big advantage of JWL is that as an NGO of the Jesuit Society it can rely on the established network of local partners in many places around the globe. Thus, the rooms and infrastructure on site are often rented by other organizations, such as the sister organization JRS - Jesuit Refugee Service. Due to the worldwide network of the Jesuits especially

in marginalized regions, it is comparatively easy for JWL to establish learning centers in marginalized regions worldwide.

Understanding these underlying processes of onsite learning in the JWL blended-learning system is crucial to properly understand the evaluated success factors in the context of the case study.

Online Learning

In addition to onsite learning, JWL's online learning system plays a crucial role in their higher education at the margins concept.

Subject Matter Experts from reputable universities around the world cooperate with JWL and provide learning content. With the help of a team of e-learning experts, the learning content is prepared according to Ignatian pedagogy and media pedagogical principles. In this manner, multimedia and interactive learning packages are created based on the learning content of the universities. The academic quality of the course content is ensured by providing and reviewing the learning units' content by the certifying institutions, and Subject Matter Experts. Each JWL course consists of 8 such units, which students normally study one per week. These packages are distributed through the JWL LMS called JWL HeLP. In this way, the offer is scalable and students in remote areas who could not reach campus universities due to distances have the opportunity to access these higher education programs. An eight-week JWL course normally has a workload of 160 hours, which means that students spend 20 hours per week on the JWL course. Of this, approximately 4 hours per week/unit are spent reading and working through the input packages which include video, audio, text, image and reading material. Since the content can be accessed through all devices and also be downloaded in an offline learning app, students are free to flexibly integrate this input phase online or offline into their daily routine. Two hours per week are allotted to the above mentioned in-class meetings. The remaining 14 hours are spent working independently and collaboratively on the weekly activities and assignments to deepen and practice the learning. These assignments are reflected in the LMS. Students can find the assignments there and submit their work when they are connected online. Students receive continuous feedback on all assignments from the online facilitators, the faculty members from various countries and universities around the world who provide academic support to students in JWL courses. It is part of the online facilitator's job to give each student written feedback on the assignments via the online learning platform each week and to grade them with points. In this way, all student submissions are graded academically. If a student passes a course, the university can award recognized and transferable credits because all student submissions have been evaluated through the LMS by their academics. Thus, it is the online facilitator's job to ensure the professional quality of the course offered and to assist students with any subject-related questions they may have. Within the onsite context as well as in the online learning

world, the students are organized in class groups of a maximum of 25 students who simultaneously complete a course under the supervision of an online facilitator. The special characteristic of JWL programs is that the students are not only part of a local learning group, but also study online in a group. This group is composed by the LMS as heterogeneous as possible, by mixing students from different places. Since many of the activities that students have to complete each week take place in discussion boards, i.e. discussion forums within the global class, there is an intercultural exchange between the students in the global learning group. These global discussions lead students to a global mindset and way of thinking. This experience of studying together in a global network enables students from marginalized regions to overcome borders and distance and get connected globally by using the technology-supported learning environment. In these discussions, the online facilitator can also actively participate in the students' discussion of the learning materials. Synchronous virtual meetings with the online facilitator do not take place on a regular basis at JWL, as many students would have difficulties participating due to internet connectivity issues or the different time zones. This is why the asynchronous global class discussions are a crucial part of the JWL blended-learning system, as they represent an exchange within the global learning group and enable intercultural exchanges between students.

Many of the aspects and success factors evaluated originate from this underlying understanding of online learning in the JWL blended learning system.

JWL HeLP

Students at the margins face and live in challenging realities. They live in unstable environments which impact their learning style and abilities. To address the unique needs of such students, a highly individualized learning platform is required. Therefore, JWL has a unique learning environment called the JWL - HeLP. (JWL - Humanitarian e-Learning Platform)

Figure 1: JWL-HeLP Humanitarian e-Learning Platform (Own representation further published in (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

Student information System (SIS)

Functionalities such as Online Student Application and Program Administration are in place to capture data on student registration and program enrolment. This student data management portal allows the coordinators of the individual learning centers to keep track of their students. The student information gathered from these applications is organized in the form of a database and maintained through the Student Information System (SIS) which allows the management of student data, generation of reports, and tracking of student history. The system component SIS is not relevant for the question investigated in this thesis, as it is an evaluation from the students' point of view and the students themselves have no point of contact with the SIS during their learning process. The blended learning system to which this thesis refers therefore does not take the SIS part into account.

Learning Management System (LMS)

The Learning Management System is used to regulate the educational content. It is the technical centerpiece for the learning process. On this system part, the distribution and availability of learning content is managed. An LMS enables the implementation of standardized e-learning content which includes multimedia and other interactive content elements. Interaction between students and facilitators, functionalities such as discussion, student work submission and grading are enabled through the Learning Management System (LMS). An internet connection is mandatory for all actions in the LMS. Since the assignments often involve long writing tasks, students often complete the assignments offline and connect to the LMS online only to then copy or upload their texts into the submission fields. Submitting assignments and interacting in the discussion forums require an online connection. Since many students use mobile internet, these system components are especially optimized for use on mobile devices.

Offline studying by using the 'Server in the corner' and JWLs Learning Apps

The 'server in the corner' and the offline learning apps are the system components that make it possible for the target group to overcome the challenge of low connectivity and participate in a digital learning world with a poor internet connection. Throughout the JWL case study, the term **offline** is used for learning situations in which an internet connection can be used occasionally, but which are very rarely and deliberately used for teaching and learning due to the low bandwidth.

More precisely, with regard to the target group of JWL, the aim is to use the internet connection only when it is absolutely necessary and to outsource as many parts of the learning process as possible to an offline setting. To make this possible, the 'server in the corner' was developed, a small server in the size of a laptop that most learning centers are equipped with. This server requires a LAN connection and automatically tries to download all course data and thus packages of learning content from the Basecamp server every two hours. When the students are in the learning center, they can connect to this local server via a local WIFI connection of the server and load the course packages from this server. This eliminates the need for each student to try to load the course packages separately. That way, the learning materials can be distributed locally without a large load on the internet bandwidth. Mobile learning in offline settings is therefore enabled by providing learning software applications for Android and Windows devices,, as JWL students are mainly equipped with these devices. By installing the apps these devices can connect to Server in the corner and download the e-learning packages. This infrastructure enables students to access the learning content which includes videos, reading material and quizzes at any place and time irrespective of the availability of internet connectivity. Once the learning content packages are loaded, students can access the multimedia learning content at any place and in offline settings. Furthermore, an offline library is available via the server in the corner,

this library is called RACHEL. RACHEL is a portable plug-and-play server which stores educational websites and makes the content available over any local (offline) wireless connection. Through the local device a very small bandwidth is required to reach the open library. This makes the educational content easily available for students at the learning center with a limited consumption of the bandwidth.

Understanding these system components that allow students to study offline, or at least to complete many phases of the learning process offline, is crucial as the students interviewed in the evaluation refer to this system.

2.1.4 COVID-19: Challenges and mitigation strategies within JWL

2020, the year in which the evaluation was carried out in the context of this thesis, was different in many respects due to the Coronavirus pandemic, and thus results may be found in the data analysis that would not have been reproducible in other years. For this reason, this section briefly discusses the changes in the operations and processes of JWL.

In 2020, which was shaped by the global Covid-19 pandemic, it was especially challenging for many learning centers to maintain operations and enable students to continue their studies. Isabella Rega, JWL's global research director wrote a report about the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on JWL operations. National regulations varied by location, the impact of the pandemic on the countries and regions of the learning centers varied widely, and the population and infrastructure at each center varied, therefore each learning center had to find its own ways to overcome the challenges. In mid-May, JWL organized an interactive workshop for student representatives, onsite facilitators, coordinators and online facilitators from around the world to discuss the challenges and mitigation strategies in globally mixed small groups based on their roles within JWL. Students reported that they had been challenged by the isolation and some found it difficult to continue their studies as they were forced to focus on day-to-day food security due to the financial crises associated with the lockdown. In many countries it was no longer possible for students to visit the learning centers, and as a result many had problems with power cuts, poor connectivity and lack of hardware at their home locations. The learning centers responded by distributing hardware and mobile data bundles to students in some places to enable learning at home. But students also found creative ways to help each other out with laptop chargers and charging options. Digital communication tools were widely used as a substitute for in-class meetings. Students used self-organized WhatsApp groups to keep up the exchange with fellow students and to work on collaborative tasks. In many places, Zoom meetings were organized instead of in-class meetings. The online facilitators accommodated the students with more flexibility in the submission deadlines. (Rega, Isabella, 2020, p. 2,7)

“The human factor, embodied by the centers in the field and by the support from local onsite facilitators and staff has proven to be a key element for the success of JWL

mission: bringing Higher Education opportunities to the margins of this world.” (Rega, Isabella, 2020, p. 9)

All in all, these innovative and creative solutions worked and enabled the students to continue their studies, which is also shown by the course pass rate from the first semester of 2020, which has not decreased compared to 2019. (Rega, Isabella, 2020, p. 7)

2.2 Case Study Evaluation

To address the question of what factors affect the success of blended-learning systems from the perspective of students from marginalized regions worldwide, JWL can serve as a case-study context as explained in the previous chapter. The results of the JWL study could be used as a starting point for further blended-learning system improvements that are successful from the perspective of the target group to provide access to higher education for more students in marginalized regions.

However, JWL's offer is very wide and in order to be able to make reliable statements and practical implications, the scope of research was further restricted. This is because, due to the focus of this thesis, it was particularly important to focus on a specific blended-learning system. Within the stackable learning path of JWL, this requirement is only fulfilled for the group of Professional Certificate Programs. Section 2.2.1 therefore presents the framework conditions of the investigated Professional Certificate Programs in more detail.

The research question of this thesis refers to the perspective of students in marginalized regions. Section 2.2.2 therefore describes in more detail how this group of students, which is used as the population in this study, is structured.

2.2.1 Evaluated Programs – Professional Certificate Programs

JWL offers a stackable learning path to guide students through their studying. In order to study together globally, students need to speak a common language, which is why the learning path starts with a solid English language program. These courses are offered in many countries and learning centers, and also in different learning modes. That means not all English courses are delivered in the blended-learning mode and therefore this set of courses is not relevant for the evaluation within this thesis. However, students who aim to study within JWL can either start their learning path by studying within these English courses or join with a proven certificated English level of at least B2. This English level is needed to enter the second level of JWL's learning path, which are the professional certificate programs. These programs consist of three eight-week courses, so in total these programs take half an academic year. These programs are specifically designed to equip the participants with necessary skills to fill identified needs in their local context. Professional certificate programs are certified by Jesuit and other mission-aligned

higher education institutions and follow the European Credit System for Vocational Education and Training (ECVET). ECVET is a system that allows the transfer, recognition and accumulation of learning outcomes to obtain qualifications through vocational and professional training programs. During a professional certificate program, participants engage in a blended-learning experience of online and onsite knowledge acquisition, and develop practical skills and attitudes to prepare them to become change agents in their communities. The participants engage with each other and with experts who are accompanying them through the JWL learning platform. The JWL unique blended-learning model avails asynchronous interactions with learners from around the world in a virtual classroom and synchronous participation on-site with other learners in their local community. As an essential part of the course, learners engage in a practicum experience, which provides authentic real-world situations for learners to apply their learning and demonstrate their ability to the community and potential employers.

The third step within this learning path is then the academic degree programs which can be entered with a level of at least C1 in the English language. However, these academic degree programs are not further considered within the evaluation of this thesis. This is because some of these courses are running on different learning management systems of partner universities and therefore the results of an evaluation on the learning system as required due to the aim of the research will not deliver clear enough data. Therefore the focus of this thesis is on the academic professional certificate courses within JWL, as for most JWL students these are the starting point for their higher education pathway. Since 2018, these 24 course-week programs have been running via JWL's blended-learning system explained in section 2.1.3. Now that a total of twelve programs of this kind have been launched already, it is appropriate to examine this group of students as a case study for the evaluation of blended learning success factors. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

JWL started in 2018 by offering the **Youth Sport Facilitator** and the **Peace Leader** programs as their first professional certificate programs. The **Youth Sports Facilitator** program aims to transform communities through the dissemination of sustainable youth sports programs. The course trains refugees and young people from the host community to become facilitators who create, manage and sustain youth sports programs in communities at the margins, especially communities with forcibly displaced populations. The course is designed to introduce the fundamentals of planning, implementing and evaluating sports programs targeting youth of 14-24 years in a supportive, fun and healthy environment. Graduates from this program are trained to engage youth by bolstering their physical, emotional and psychological well-being, building an ethical mindset, learning teamwork and sportsmanship and developing moral character. Most importantly, course participants will learn how to build a sense of safety and security with a focus on protection, inclusiveness of gender and disability, conflict management, psycho-social first-aid, understanding referral pathways and building cross-cultural relationships among youth.

The **Peace Leader** program is an introduction to the role and practices of a Peace Leader. The program integrates selected best practices from the disciplines of Peace Studies and Servant Leadership. As Peace Leaders in training, the participants examine and practice personal and communal skills and values that are foundational for nurturing a culture of peace. This professional certificate is designed around three core themes: self-awareness and cultural awareness; conflict resolution and reconciliation; and servant leadership. In the year 2019 the Professional certificate Program, **Learning Facilitator** was started. Learning Facilitators are teachers, tutors, or any individual who desires to support the learning of others. This program prepares them to facilitate learning in formal or non-formal classroom settings. It introduces accessible learning technologies that extend the reach of education and trains the facilitators to integrate best practices of online and onsite learning to create engaging learning environments. The course culminates with a final project and practicum experience in which participants apply sound educational principles and practices to meet an identified need within the community. This is how the participants contribute in meaningful ways to the vision of Jesuit Worldwide Learning: Learning together to transform the world. In 2020 the Professional Certificate Programs in Community-based Ecotourism and Creative Writing and Design started. The program in **Community-based Ecotourism** addresses the needs of communities all over the world to promote responsible tourism that allows the generation of income while preserving the community's fragile resources. The program provides both understanding and skills in managing ecotourism resources. It introduces the concepts and principles of tourism and ecotourism and the necessary knowledge and practices to design and promote sustainable tourism-related products and services. The Professional Certificate Program on **Creative Writing and Design** aims to deliver training in the fundamentals of digital media design. It first introduces the participants to creative writing, to enable them to express their thoughts and plans creatively with text. Later on the participants get an overview of the graphic design field. It introduces the participants to expressing their ideas and messages graphically with attractive visuals and appealing designs. Then, the participants will move one step further and learn through the web design course how to create their own websites, blogs and other engaging content with a corporate style, combining written and graphical creations. (Balleis, Peter et al., 2020)

Regardless of the subject matter, all professional certificate programs follow the same blended-learning approach. Since the research in the scope of this thesis is about the success factors of the blended-learning system, all professional certificate programs were included in the evaluation. In this way, a larger population of students could be included in the study and influences due to course-specific experiences could be balanced out. It should be noted, however, that not all courses were offered the same number of times during the period under investigation and that the number of students per course varied.

2.2.2 Students in marginalized regions

JWL is committed to higher education in marginalized regions which means in communities at the margins of societies – those societies that through poverty, location, lack of opportunity, conflict or forced displacement exist among the rural or urban poor, indigenous or isolated displaced people. Learning centers are spread across marginalized and crisis regions globally: Afghanistan, Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of Congo, Guyana, India, Iraq, Italy, Jordan, Kenya, Malawi, Myanmar, Nepal, Philippines, Sri Lanka, Togo and Zambia. In most of these countries there are more than one learning centers. Together JWL and its community learning centers form a multi-cultural, multi-ethnic, and multi-religious global community of learners enabling all to contribute their knowledge and voices to foster hope to create a more peaceful and humane world. (Jesuit Worldwide Learning, 2020)

A total of 450 students have completed or are currently by October 2020 participating in professional certificate programs to date. As shown in Figure 2, the Learning Facilitator program has been the most popular with 181 students. The two programs Community-based Ecotourism and Creative Writing & Design, which have only started this year, have only been attended by a few students so far, as they are still in their first intake. The lower number of students in the Youth Sport Facilitator Program is due to the fact that the program has only run twice so far and was under revision from the end of 2019 until 2020 and was therefore paused. The Peace Leader and Learning Facilitator programs each had four intakes to date, so the programs have reached very high student numbers. The countries from which students participated in the respective programs are marked in color in the bars. A total of 124 students of the 450 students listed here are participating or have participated in the programs from learning centers in Afghanistan. With 80 students from the Dzaleka refugee camp in Malawi and 61 students from the Kakuma refugee camp in Kenya, these two long-established learning centers in refugee camps of JWL are also major providers of the professional certificate courses. In these refugee camps, both refugees and members of the local host community can enroll in JWL's programs. These students must be 18 years of age or older and meet the application requirements of the certifying institution. The courses offered by JWL are completely free of charge for the students.

Figure 2: Active and Completed Students of Professional Certificate Courses by Country (Data were collected by the author based on the JWL student database)

Within the 450 students who have completed or are currently active in professional certificate programs, 48% are female students and 52% male students. While the gender distribution among the students in general is relatively balanced, Figure 3 shows clearly there are differences by country. In most countries the number of women was a bit higher. But in Kenya and Malawi with the large learning centers in the refugee camps, it is noticeable that significantly more male students participate or have participated in the professional certificate courses.

Figure 3: Target Group of JWL Students by Country and Gender (Data were collected by the author based on the JWL student database)

3 Criteria for blended-learning system success

This thesis aims to investigate what factors influence the success of blended-learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions around the world. This will help to find starting points for the practical design of blended-learning systems in order to make them as successful as possible from the students' point of view. To answer this question, it is first necessary to identify the factors that are significant for blended learning in the context of higher education in general, i.e. independently of a specific target group. This analysis should therefore be based on the current state of academic literature and research, the methodology of the literature analysis will be explained in the first section. Beginning with section 3.2, the rest of chapter 3 deals with this subquestion and treats in the different sections the individual substeps of the detailed comparative literature analysis which is necessary to reach this overview of impact factors in literature.

In order to examine the current state of research on the success factors of blended-learning systems, we will first open up the scope of blended-learning systems in order to get to know the basic perspectives and research approaches from which the success criteria of information systems are examined.

In analogy to the evaluation of the e-learning success criteria by Al-Fraihat et al. this thesis also follows the definition that considers e-learning systems as information systems. Thus, blended-

learning systems, which are a special form of e-learning systems according to Arnold et al. (Arnold et al., 2018, p. 22), can be seen as information systems in the broadest sense and the success of a blended-learning system can be seen as information system (IS) success. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, p. 68)

The view of the research models on this broad level is important because, as Urbach and Müller argue, these underlying models will remain relevant even if they are not applied directly in specialized research fields such as learning systems or even blended-learning systems, because the specific research models of the individual disciplines are often based on these models (Urbach & Müller, 2012, pp. 12–14).

Following this approach, Section 3.2 presents research perspectives that have dealt with the success criteria of information systems. Based on the findings from the literature review on which perspectives are important in this regard by Al-Fraihat, two of the most popular perspectives are presented: the System Success Perspective according to DeLone and McLean (2003) and the Technology Acceptance Perspective according to Davis et al. (Davis et al., 1989). These two perspectives fit within the scope of this work, as they come from a technical point of view and this work according to the research question mainly addresses the system success factors of blended learning. The third part of this chapter introduces further research perspectives which should be presented at the same level in terms of basic concepts, as later models in e-learning and blended learning build on them.

All basic concepts and models are presented in this chapter first in a general way in order to understand how models for evaluating system success factors have evolved and thus provide the basis for research in specific application areas such as e-learning. In order to understand how this application of research perspectives looks like in the e-learning context, adaptations of the models to examine e-learning specific models are also presented for each research perspective presented. In this way, a comprehensive picture of the research perspectives and their implementation in the e-learning context emerges.

The findings on e-learning system success factors are compiled in the following section 3.3. In addition, this section presents further findings of researchers who have already aimed in their research to create a comprehensive overview of the e-learning system success factors. Thereby, the e-learning-specific factors are discussed which are the starting point for the further specialized research area of blended-learning system success factors presented in the next step.

In section 3.4, based on the findings on the e-learning system success factors, publications are presented that have developed and tested special research instruments for the investigation of system success factors of blended-learning systems. From these tests it can be seen which factors were significant in the blended-learning context and thus contribute to answering the sub-research question to which the whole chapter 3 is dedicated. But finding significant blended-

learning success factors is not yet the final goal of this chapter. Because of the restriction to a special target group, students in marginalized regions worldwide, the aim of this work is to evaluate these factors from the perspective of the target group. Only in this way can it be determined whether they also show correlations from their point of view that characterize them as blended-learning system success factors for this target group. In order to perform the evaluation, it is also the goal of this comparative literature analysis to find a research instrument that is suitable for this purpose.

As can be seen from the abundance of publications on digital learning systems in universities around the world, the dynamics of digitalization have a huge impact on the education sector. This continuous development of digital learning environments requires an equally continuous further development of the evaluation models (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 157)

Therefore, the choice of a research instrument is limited to the latest models; in the scope of this thesis, only models from 2018 onwards will be considered.

The choice of available established research models is then further limited by another reason. According to Al-Fraihat et al., there is the need for further research in evaluating the learning systems for continuous improvements, this process should be directed to meet the learners needs (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020, p. 68).

This brings the learner back into focus. This work focuses on a specific target group, students in marginalized regions worldwide. Therefore, when selecting the model, it should not only be considered whether it is up-to-date and includes the significant factors found during the process of literature analysis, but also whether they are relevant in the context of the JWL case study.

In the last section, a comprehensive model is presented that was found to be suitable for the evaluation of the case study according to these criteria. The model of Zhang and Dang which was published recently in 2020 provides a research framework including many of the identified blended-learning success criteria and fits to the JWL context. The factors included in this instrument, their definition in the context of this thesis and a summary of the significant findings on these factors from the literature are summarized in the final section 3.5.

This chapter thus lays the foundations for further investigation of blended-learning system success factors from the perspective of students in marginalized regions worldwide.

3.1 Methodology of the Comparative Analysis of Existing Literature

In the 1980s, researchers like Bailey and Pearson developed a tool for measuring and analyzing computer user satisfaction (Bailey & Pearson, 1983, p. 530). Since then several researchers contributed new insights from several perspectives and new evaluations of e-learning systems. In the following comparative analysis process of the existing literature, relevant publications have been classified in three categories of research perspectives: information system success,

technology acceptance, and further aspects impacting blended-learning success and satisfaction. To get an overview of the variety of research perspectives on the success of e-learning systems, the publications by Al-Fraihat show a wide spectrum (Al-Fraihat, 2019; Al-Fraihat et al., 2020). These publications are the starting point for the literature analysis with the focus on success criteria for blended-learning systems. Besides the focus on blended-learning, the target group of students in marginalized areas also impacts the literature research. The publications evaluate and analyse in both developed and developing countries. Including case studies within the developing countries helps to avoid overlooking impact factors which might be relevant for a target group of students in marginalized areas.

The research process of finding recently-published relevant literature mainly took place with Research Gate and Biber, the research database of Danube University Krems for licensed databases, ebooks and ejournals. The research perspectives system success and technology acceptance were used as search terms in combination with e-learning and blended-learning. That returned variety of publications, where the bibliographic lists were of great help to find more specified researches including and comparing further aspects and research perspectives.

The Information System Success Model (William DeLone & McLean, 2003) and the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis et al., 1989) were analyzed by looking into publications applying these two models in the general context of information systems. The consistent development in technologies led to a consistent development of these research models. The development in the research of measuring the success or evaluating acceptance of information systems was useful to understand which variables had shown significant results over time for different developmental stages of technology. Especially via the focus on publications within the e-learning context, key variables were identified.

Through this process for example the D&M IS success quality dimensions, information quality, system quality and service quality, showed their relevance within research models over decades (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020, p. 72; DeLone, William & McLean, 2003; Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 449; J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 162).

From the perspective of technology acceptance variables like the behavioral intention to use a system as indicators for the acceptance or external self-related factors such as computer self-efficacy was widely used to evaluate e-learning systems (Abdullah & Ward, 2016, p. 40; H.-R. Chen & Tseng, 2012, p. 404). Furthermore, the impact of human-related factors and media-richness were identified through this research perspective, and these elements can still be found in some of the most recent publications in this field (Alomari et al., 2020, p. 23544; Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 449; Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018, p. 77181).

Throughout the process of comparative analysis of the literature some publications showed research perspectives which couldn't be classified in such clear categories as the two approaches mentioned above. However, these publications also brought interesting insights which were

further evaluated by multiple authors in the e-learning context. One example of such a construct is the *task-technology fit*. Invented by Goodhue and Thompson in 1995, several publications on the success of e-learning systems picked up this construct (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 496; 1995, p. 217; W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, p. 90; McGill & Klobas, 2009, p. 503).

As mentioned before, the process of analyzing the literature was initiated by looking into general applications of these models in the context of information systems. In the next step the focus was more specialized into the e-learning context. In the third step, a deductive approach was used which focused on the blended learning context, as the research questions are centered around the evaluation of the success criteria of a blended-learning system. Conclusions can be drawn from the findings of the past, and thus the older publications represent the foundation for current research. The researched publications are therefore always presented from old to new. But especially in such a highly dynamic field as learning technologies, it is crucial to pick up on the latest findings and develop them further, that's why the following sections aim to find out the most appropriate research framework for this thesis.

3.2 Research Perspectives

Many researchers evaluating e-learning success criteria base their work upon the system success factors first formulated by DeLone and McLean. In this model, information quality, system quality and service quality are core factors which are interrelated directly or indirectly with several further variables. However, research according to the system success approach is only one perspective to evaluate the success criteria of an e-learning system from students' perspective. Students' acceptance of the system or other impact factors on the satisfaction with the e-learning system are further research perspectives. Literature reviews and studies with different focus between 2000 and 2020 identified the need for a comprehensive research model which includes aspects of the system success, technology acceptance, learners' satisfaction as well as the aspects of interaction between involved parties or other factors impacting the satisfaction. (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020, p. 67)

The following pages will introduce the basic concepts of these research perspectives on system success, and further present the adaptations and development of these perspectives in the field of e-learning system success criteria research.

After looking at system success models in detail from a mainly technological perspective, also research frameworks with an instructional design perspective which particularly address the blended-learning framework will be analyzed as this is fundamental to find a suitable research framework for this study.

3.2.1 Information system success perspective

To understand the satisfaction, value, or efficacy of an e-learning system, which is from a technical abstract perspective an information system, the overall measurement of information systems success is important. In 1992 DeLone and McLean published their Information Systems Success model, D&M IS Success Model. Around 300 articles referred to this comprehensive and multidimensional model, and several research projects used this model in various fields of application. Since 1992, dynamic development and changes in the practical use of information systems in sectors like e-commerce took place and required an update of the model. In 2003 De Leone and McLean published a ten-year update on their model. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 10)

This research perspective, looking from a technical viewpoint at the system success, is relevant in the context of this study, as this study aims to identify success criteria of blended-learning systems. In particular the updated D&M IS Success Model is frequently discussed in literature and should therefore be discussed to serve as scientific foundation of the research model used in this thesis. Which aspects are of interest for this study and how this model was developed and tested will be explained in the following part.

The foundations of the research model

The purpose of DeLone and McLean's first model was to summarize previous research findings on IS success into a systematic body of knowledge which could serve as fundament and guide for future research studies in this field. An example of earlier studies which have influenced the D&M IS success model are studies on the management of information systems between 1981 and 1987. To evaluate communication systems, Shannon and Weaver set, based on their communication theory, three levels: the technical, semantic and effectiveness level of a communication system. They used these to evaluate respectively the efficiency of producing and transporting information, the success of transporting the correct meaning of an information and the impact of the information on the addressee. In the original version of the D&M IS Success Model of 1992, these three levels lead to **system quality** for success measurement on the technical level, **information quality** for the measurement on the semantic level. In addition the success dimensions **organizational impact**, **individual impact**, **use** and **user satisfaction** have impacted the effectiveness level of a system. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 10)

These six dimensions of success are identified as interrelated and several researchers then further discussed if this interrelation can be seen as process or as causal dependencies. Some researchers related these dimensions to system use from the viewpoint of a temporal process. According to the temporal process model each information system is in the first stage a created system which contains information. On that level system quality and information quality could be measured. In the next stage of the system, users start exploring the system and using it for

their purpose. On this level researchers can measure the use of the system itself as well as the user's satisfaction with the information system. Using the system leads to the last stage, the impact of the system. The focus of this stage is the impact on the work for which the individuals are using the system. These impact could be measured from an individual and an organizational perspective. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 11)

So this approach of research studies seeing the process dependencies between the six dimensions information quality, system quality, use, user satisfaction, individual impact and organization impact, led in the D&M IS success model to the visible separation into three layers. In Figure 4 this is shown by the dotted lines. The first two variables are measured once the system is created. Use and user satisfaction are variables measured during the second stage, while the system is used. Individual and organizational impact can be derived from the observation of system usage behavior.

Figure 4: D&M IS Success Model original version of 1992. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 12)

Aspects of a causal model, which means analyzing if there are causal relationships between elements of the model, are discussed in the development process to the D&M IS Success model. The multidimensional interdependency in the information system success dimensions are discussed in the conclusion of the original D&M IS Success model publication. The authors warn future researchers to pay special attention to these potential causal dependencies which might occur in information systems success research. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 11)

As many researchers found in this model a useful tool applicable for various contexts, the D&M IS Success Model basic structures such as the measurement of system quality, information quality and user satisfaction can be found until now in the recently developed and published

success models for several contexts of information system use. That is why the foundations of this model are introduced here, as the D&M IS Success Model can be seen as a cornerstone in information systems success research.

The updated DeLone and McLean Model

The dynamic of digitalization pointed out the need for an update of the D&M IS Success Model, which the authors published in 2003. Updating their model DeLone and McLean had an e-commerce information system in mind and explained the changes with reference to the progress and development in the e-commerce sector. Basically, there had been three major changes based on the criticism and evaluation findings of hundreds of researchers who applied and challenged this model over ten years. On the first level a third dimension of quality was added, the service quality. This was because the authors DeLone and McLean concluded from existing literature that with a more holistic view of an IS's success, it's not enough to measure information quality and system quality. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 23)

“For measuring the overall success of the IS department, as opposed to individual systems, service quality may become the most important variable” (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 18)

Many researchers discussed a lot on the causal or process relations between the success dimensions in the model. To meet these concerns DeLone and McLean wrote in their conclusion that depending on the research context the intention to use or system use could be valuable success measures. When deciding which success dimension, they will use researchers should verify whether the system use is voluntary or not, as well as keeping in mind that use is a behavior and the intention to use is an attitude. Researchers should make a decision for their individual case and the authors of the model hope for more informed understanding. Instead of individual impact and organizational impact the updated model introduces net benefits as the result of use / intention to use and user satisfaction. The term 'net benefits' was used by other researchers and the authors decided to keep this term as this neutral term will lead to less confusion. Calling the outcome impact might lead people to say positive or negative impact, and that might cause misunderstandings on good or bad results. 'Net benefits' is neutral and allows us to see positive and negative consequences of an outcome. As shown in Figure 5, DeLone and McLean also updated the arrangement of the success dimensions slightly. In particular, they updated the arrows in their model to visualize the proposed relations between the success dimensions in a process sense. Every researcher should hypothesize the causal associations in the individual setting of each study. Now there is also a loop introduced between

the level of use, user satisfaction and the level of net benefits as the continued use of an IS might have a mutual effect. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, pp. 23–24)

Figure 5: Updated S&M IS Success Model (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 24)

In 2013, Petter, DeLone and McLean further investigated the determinants of IS success. By conducting a qualitative literature review they checked 140 previous publications on the D&M IS Success Model and identified 43 independent variables that cause success of the information system. That means these independent variables have a positive relation to the dependent variables, system quality, information quality, service quality, intention to use, use, user satisfaction and net benefits. (Petter et al., 2013, pp. 12, 45)

The categories task, user, social, project and organizational found in this paper to group the IS success determinants along with interrelations are visualized in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Determinants of IS Success (Petter et al., 2013, p. 45)

Summarizing the literature on the updated DeLone and McLean information system success model, there are the following new aspects which should be considered by future system success evaluations. In the updated version of the research model, service quality was added to the quality dimensions. Further, the authors adapted their model because the system use might in some cases be voluntary in others not. According to that, the point of measurement should be either the intention to use the system or the system use itself. Also, the third change summing up the impact in the new variable net benefits, was an adaptation to allow more flexibility of the model and avoid misunderstandings. As reaction to the ongoing debate on whether there are causal or process relations within the model's variables, the authors added arrows to visualize process relations and called for hypothesizing the causal relations according to the individual research context. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, pp. 26–28) In 2013, Petter et al. identified groups of independent variables which impact the IS success. Including these independent variables is important to identify success criteria of information systems. Therefore, further research should also take a look at task, user, social, project and organizational characteristics. (Petter et al., 2013, pp. 38–40)

DeLone and McLean IS Success model in e-learning research projects

To understand the factors influencing blended-learning systems' success, the updated D&M IS Success model is an important foundation of the research model. More than 300 researchers have validated this basic model in several scenarios. Therefore, the D&M model is one of the most supported and best-established models. The current relevance of this model is shown by the development towards the needs in the updated version and the many researchers who use this model until now for their research. Several researchers applied the D&M IS success model in the full version or partly in the context of e-learning system use. Sometimes researchers have extended it by adding other constructs or integrated parts of D&M IS success model into more context-related frameworks. Al Fraihat reviewed 15 e-learning success evaluation studies based on at least part or the full model of DeLone and McLearn between 2002 and 2018. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, pp. 13–14)

Quality Dimensions

Several researchers identified the construct of information quality, system quality and service quality as highly important impact factors for evaluating the success of blended learning (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 449). Wu et al. found that these three dimensions of the D&M IS success model have significant impact on students' expected learning performance which is an important impact factor of the learning satisfaction in their model (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 162). So, there is a widely spread consent among most of the researchers on the validity of the D&M IS success model or at least the measurement dimensions information quality, system quality and service quality. However, there are also studies which cannot find significance for all three variables of the D&M quality dimensions.

One example for such an evaluation was published in 2007 by Lee and Hwang. They evaluated the impact of computer self-efficiency and the LMS from a user satisfaction perspective. Therefore, they developed a model with the variables 'perceived ease of use of the LMS', 'perceived usefulness of the LMS', 'service quality on interaction' and 'information quality' which they assume to be related to the learner's satisfaction on the one hand. On the other side the self-regulatory learning strategy which is itself impacted by computer self-efficacy influences the learner's satisfaction. In their empirical test at a university in South Korea they identified service quality which they understand in the sense of facilitator support, learners self-regulatory learning strategy and computer self-efficiency as critical impact factors. While they couldn't find support for an impact of information quality on learners' satisfaction. (J.-K. Lee & Hwang, 2007, pp. 74–77)

It is interesting that all three dimensions do not always lead to significant impact, which might again be related to the different context of research as DeLone and McLean already pointed out. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, pp. 27–28)

Another reason is seen in other variables which are not explained through the model and need to be researched. Also, there are newly-added measurement approaches which most of the authors used to adapt the models to their research focus in the e-learning context. Out of the reviewed 15 publications only one stayed with the original research model construction. Comparing the results became more difficult by the rising dynamic of the adaptations of the D&M model in e-learning success research in the years between 2010 and 2018. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, pp. 21–27)

Looking at the details on how the models reviewed by Al-Fraihat are adapted, six of these publications individualized the net benefit regarding to their study context. Depending on the voluntary or nonvoluntary nature of the use of a learning management system in the specific cases, system use was adapted to intention to use, intention to reuse or behavioral intention to use. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, pp. 21–27)

Additional Instructional Aspects

Publications like Hassanzadeh et al. added more complexity to the model by adding a new level, 'the loyalty to system', and then relating the benefits of system use with the measurement of goals achievement (Hassanzadeh et al., 2012, p. 10960). Others adapted the formulations in the model to their context, for example a research on mobile learning success or on e-learning in an organizational context. The other major approach in adaptations of the D&M IS success model focuses on the educational perspective. And therefore, many researchers added further variables to measure aspects which are relevant from an educational perspective. Eight of Al-Fraihat's fifteen analyzed publications have added such elements of instructional purpose. Teaching and Learning Quality analyzed by Klobas and McGill (2010, p. 118) as well as Instructor Quality (Cheng, 2012, p. 365) as additional dimensions have shown a positive influence on system usage. Also, communication quality was added as additional dimension to measure e-learning system success. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, pp. 21–27)

In 2019 Seman et al. picked up the ideas of earlier studies and applied only the system quality dimensions of information quality, system quality and service quality from the D&M IS success model, for the evaluation of blended-learning satisfaction. The category individual characteristics in the measurement of computer anxiety and technology experience was added as an additional dimension, as well as course characteristics by measuring course quality and instructor quality. (Seman et al., 2019, p. 130)

Furthermore, some authors recommend choosing the instructors for e-learning courses wisely as their commitment and attitude towards the e-Learning systems also has a high impact on students' satisfaction. (Sun et al., 2008, p. 1196)

In 2018, Cidral et al. combined D&M IS Success Model with Collaboration Quality (Urbach et al., 2010, p. 3) and identified collaboration quality along with information quality, system quality

and service quality as important drivers of e-learning system use. The significant impact of collaboration quality lead to the conclusion that stakeholders would benefit if the learning platform allows collaboration and the articulation of communication among all system users. (Cidral et al., 2018, p. 283)

In the conclusion of DeLone and McLean's publication in 2003 the authors call for further field research studies to apply their model and they especially point out that "context should dictate the appropriate specification and application of the D&M IS Success Model" (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 18).

As the examples have shown, there are multiple approaches to apply the D&M IS success perspective in the e-learning system evaluation. But there are also challenges remaining once this model is applied in the e-learning context. According to the summary of Al-Fraihat on the application of the D&M model in an e-learning context Eom indicated in the publication of 2012 that the D&M IS success model was developed and focuses on e-commerce systems and as e-learning scenarios are different it is showing weaknesses there by showing not enough explanatory power. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, p. 26). The difficulty of applying the D&M IS Success Model in a specific research context is in many cases also caused by the challenge to define the IS success for this context. The way of operationalizing IS success may differ from the type of system evaluated as well as from the perspective of the stakeholders who are involved in the IS evaluation. Which success variables are chosen should therefore be influenced by the objective of the evaluation and the organizational context of the research. (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 17)

As this chapter has shown, several of the presented adapted D&M IS success models have been tested in e-learning settings. The number of evaluations and the validity of the results based on this research perspective have shown that the D&M IS success perspective can contribute to the evaluation of e-learning systems.

The significance of D&M IS success dimensions in e-learning should lead system designers to take care of the quality of information they present to learners. That means to specially check the accuracy, usefulness, and relevance of the information in student learning materials as well as on the overall learning platform. System quality should also be improved consistently to be reliable, accessible and user friendly. Due to the lack of personal interaction it is particularly important that the system quality contributes to encourage learners' participation. If the learners are facing challenges or need any kind of support the service quality shows its important impact. The accessibility, response time and feedback mechanisms are examples for such practical implications of service quality which should be carefully planned by the system designers. (H.-F. Lin, 2007, p. 819; Lwoga, 2014, p. 17)

As the application of the model in e-learning research has shown, there are several ways to adapt the model. According to the findings from the perspective of system success which was evaluated in this chapter, the following key points will be kept in mind for the final decision on a research model in this evaluation. The mode of system use can be adapted for mandatory or voluntary system use (Al-Fraihat, 2019, pp. 21–27). The individualization of the case-specific definition of benefit helps to solve the challenges according to contextualization of the model (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003, p. 17). Literature shows several publications on e-learning system success which apply only the widely recognized D&M IS success quality dimensions and combine them with other points of measurements (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 449; J.-K. Lee & Hwang, 2007, pp. 74–77; J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 162). In particular adding further points of measurement with instructional focus, like individual or student characteristics (Klobas & McGill, 2010, p. 118), facilitator characteristics (Cheng, 2012, p. 365; Klobas & McGill, 2010, p. 118), course characteristics (Seman et al., 2019, p. 130) or interaction characteristics like measuring the collaboration quality (Urbach et al., 2010, p. 3), can be found in multiple publications. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, p. 26).

In DeLone and McLeans publication together with Petter, the independent variables impacting IS success were identified. Task, user, social, project and organizational characteristics should be measured in detail (Petter et al., 2013, p. 45). The user perspective influenced by external social, cultural or political factors is an important item in the technology acceptance model (TAM) which is the second largely recognized research model for evaluating the success of technological systems. Many researchers follow the call to focus also on measuring the independent variables. Hence combinations of TAM and the D&M IS success model can be found in many studies on the success of e-learning systems. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, pp. 35–42) The following section on Technology Acceptance will clarify the background and basic structure of the TAM research framework. In order to find further aspects which should be included in a research on blended-learning system success other research perspectives like user satisfaction models or approaches focusing on blended-learning settings should also be checked in detail to identify the most relevant influencing factors.

3.2.2 Technology Acceptance Perspective

Based on the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) from social psychology, in 1989 Davis et al. developed the Technology Acceptance Model to explain the acceptance of information systems. In short, the TRA describes actual behavior as a result of behavioral intention, which is influenced by subjective norms and the attitude towards a behavior. The purpose of the model aims further than explaining the impact factors of computer system acceptance, it should also provide helpful guidelines on how to design computer systems with high acceptance. The TAM model considers external variables like social, cultural, or political factors as drivers of either perceived

usefulness or perceived ease of use. The perceived usefulness measures the subjective perception of the impact of system use on the job performance. The perceived ease of use is the subjective perception on how easy and free of effort a system is to use. These determinants lead to an attitude towards using the system and follow on to a behavioral intention to use. This behavioral intention to use is the main impact factor of actual system use. As shown in Figure 7 there is also a relation between perceived usefulness and behavioral intention to use. (Davis et al., 1989, pp. 984–989)

Figure 7: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis et al., 1989, p. 985)

Over 10 years, TAM became a widespread and many times empirically tested tool for predicting the acceptance of information systems (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000, p. 187). Acceptance of information systems is evaluated by measuring how users feel about the system use and when they use it. By using this model several research studies successfully explained the use and usefulness of systems in a variety of contexts, including e-learning systems. (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020, p. 69)

In 2000 Venkatesh and Davis still recognized a low usage of installed systems and underutilization of systems in general and tried to adapt their model to better understand user acceptance. Perceived usefulness is a highly important impact factor in their model, as shown in several studies the impact on the Intention to use is much higher than the impact of the factor perceived ease of use. A better understanding of the determinants of perceived usefulness helps to develop practical interventions in the organizational context to encounter the problem of underutilized systems by increasing the acceptance. Therefore, the authors developed an updated version of the model TAM 2, including determinants of perceived usefulness. Subjective norm, image, job relevance, output quality and result demonstrability had been identified as new points of measurement. Also, further measurement factors were added to the factor behavioral intention to use, that would help in the evaluation process to understand the effects of the newly added determinants of perceived usefulness. (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000, p. 187)

Due to the dynamic development in information system technology, also multiple acceptance models were developed by several researchers. Venkatesh et al. in 2003 saw the need for a unified user acceptance model which empirically compares eight existing models and merges them in the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology, called UTAUT. (Venkatesh et al., 2003, p. 426)

Several empirical tests showed a major improvement in the explanation power, compared to the original models, by explaining 70% variance in usage intention. As shown in Figure 8 UTAUT defines performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence as direct impact factors on the behavioral intention to use. Facilitating conditions along with the behavioral intention to use are seen as direct determinants of system use behavior. Furthermore the tests have shown the significant moderating impact of the features gender, age, experience, and voluntariness of use. (Venkatesh et al., 2003, p. 467)

Figure 8: Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology - UTAUT (Venkatesh et al., 2003, p. 447)

Low use and acceptance of information systems is still a barrier to successful information technology implementation in companies, that's why researchers continued to develop their models further to conclude useful practical implications. Also, the development of TAM 2 was continued and led to an updated version in 2008, TAM 3. The updated version specially focuses on the determinants of perceived ease of use, while TAM 2 had focused on the details of determinants of perceived usefulness. Based on the concept of anchor and adjustment, in this understanding

the variables grouped as anchors lead to an initial opinion of the users about the system, while the adjustment group represents variables which are adjusted after a first direct experience of using the system. So, the anchors are computer self-efficacy, perceptions of external control in the sense of facilitation, computer anxiety and computer playfulness which is basically the intrinsic motivation of system use. After the first use of the new systems users develop an opinion on the perceived enjoyment and the objective usability. As these variables are adjusted after the first usage they are grouped as adjustment determinants of perceived ease of use. (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008, pp. 274–278)

Figure 9 shows the TAM 3 model. There the anchors and adjustment factors as determinants of the perceived ease of use are added to the adaptations made to the TAM model by the second update.

Figure 9: Technology Acceptance Model 3 (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008, p. 280)

Four years after the publication of TAM 3, a new update of the UTAUT was also published by Venkatesh et al., the research model UTAUT 2. The authors have seen key challenges which are addressed in the second version of the UTAUT model. The model should also work for new contexts like new technologies, a wider cultural range and to previously overlooked population groups. Having these aspects in mind the most significant development to which the model needs to adapt is the growing industry of consumer technology, information systems targeting

consumer use. Earlier research on IS success as also discussed in the chapter on information system success, as well as the research on consumer behavior, found motivation constructs were an important impact factor. So, the hedonic motivation was added to the UTAUT model. Looking at the consumer context, the costs can also influence a user's adaptation decisions. Therefore, the price value was added as determinant of the intention of system use. The focus on the consumer also led to the decision to add the users' habit as an additional factor. The system users' habit not only affects the relation of intention to use and the real technology use, it also directly affects the use of technology. As shown in Figure 10, the three major adaptations of the new version of UTAUT are the determinants, hedonic motivation, price value and habit. Also the moderator voluntariness was deleted and some links and relationships between determinants and moderators were added. (Venkatesh et al., 2012, p. 159) All these changes can be found in the notes in Figure 10.

Figure 10: UTAUT 2 (Venkatesh et al., 2012, p. 160)

Technology acceptance models in e-learning research projects

As literature showed, the perspective of system acceptance is a commonly-used approach to evaluate information systems. As this study also deals with an information system, by evaluating

the success criteria of an e-learning system, it is relevant to take a look at the application of an acceptance perspective in e-learning research projects. Understanding the use and acceptance of e-learning systems is important to design a system as an effective educational tool.

The TAM model in the original or updated form is one of the most common ground theories in evaluating e-learning system acceptance. The intention to use an e-learning system is often explained by an extended TAM model. Several researchers see the need to add external variables to understand what drives e-learning system users to accept such a system. (Šumak et al., 2011, p. 2068)

In research projects on e-learning success, the TAM model is used to evaluate the acceptance and usage behavior of system users. In recent years, the TAM model was tested from several perspectives of technology-supported learning systems. The use of learning management systems, the intention towards e-learning or the intention to adopt e-learning are examples of research topics in this field. Al-Fraihat reviewed and summarized the conclusions of seventeen studies which applied the TAM model in e-learning contexts. Basically, two approaches of TAM model adaptations for the e-learning context were found. Either the authors added e-learning-specific external variables to one of the existing TAM models or they integrated other models or at least parts of models like the D&M IS success model. The need for this adaptation is emphasized by the critique of the TAM models. Some researchers are missing variables related to the social and human change process, or were unable to conclude useful practical implications. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, pp. 33–36)

One example is the study of Selim in 2003. Due to the lack of studies evaluating learners' acceptance of course websites as a learning tool, Selim identified the need for instructors to know how to implement technologies to support the learning process. The course website usefulness, the course website use and the course website ease of use was measured to reveal variables that impact the acceptance. These are the diversity of learning styles, interactivity of learning materials or facilitation through communication channels. (Selim, 2003, pp. 344–357)

Another example is the publication of Liu et al. who applied the flow theory along with the TAM model to evaluate the streaming-based e-learning system of universities in Taiwan. There had been different types of presentations; text-audio, audio-video or text-audio-video materials. The research identified a significant relation between this media richness and the intention to use the e-learning system. Furthermore they measured higher levels of perceived usefulness and concentration when the e-learning system with the highest media richness, text-audio-video, was used. (Liu et al., 2005, p. 180)

Researchers evaluating students' e-learning acceptance in South Korea also concluded that a comprehensive model might be needed to take the complexity of the intention to use an e-learning system into account. So, they extended the TAM model variable perceived usefulness by measuring the determinants instructor characteristics and teaching materials. The design of

learning content, in the sense of the level of adaptations to fit the student needs, is seen as an external variable related to the perceived ease of use. The fourth independent variable playfulness is adapted from an online consumer model and is not further specified and explained in the context of e-learning. In the results they found significant impact of instructor characteristics, teaching material and the design of learning content. (B.-C. Lee et al., 2009, p. 1327)

Another example is the publication of Chen and Tseng evaluating junior high school teachers' acceptance of web-based e-learning systems for in-service training. They added the external variables motivation to use, computer anxiety and internet self-efficacy to the TAM model as impact factors of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. The results showed that perceived usefulness is the primary impact factor on the intention to use the system and this factor is mainly driven by motivation to use and also influenced by internet self-efficacy. (H.-R. Chen & Tseng, 2012, p. 404)

With a closer focus on publications on the acceptance of learning management systems in higher education, as this is the focus of this research, research frameworks of the technology acceptance perspective can also be found.

Alharib and Drew conducted a study at the university of Shaqra in Saudi Arabia, to evaluate academics' perception of the LMS. So, this publication has a different target group, the academics not the students. But in relation to the call to also evaluate the instructor characteristics it might also be interesting to take a look at these research results. Basically, the TAM model was used as research model, extended by the three external variables job relevance, lack of LMS availability and LMS usage experience. The research was conducted prior the establishment of a LMS at the university which is why it is not possible to measure the impact of the lack of LMS availability on perceived usefulness. For the other external variables, the relation to both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use is measured. The results showed that the job relevance has a strong relation to positive perceived usefulness of an LMS. Even the lack of the LMS showed significant relation to the perceived ease of use, which the authors see as an indicator that the users believe using an LMS is not too difficult. In particular, the inexperienced users indicated higher positive openness towards an LMS. (Alharbi & Drew, 2014, pp. 145–148)

In 2016 Abdullah and Ward conducted a quantitative meta-analysis of frequently-used external factors to develop a General Extended Technology Acceptance Model for e-Learning (GETAMEL). They analyzed 107 publications according to the external variables used impacting on the main constructs of the TAM model, perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness (PU). (Abdullah & Ward, 2016, p. 40)

“Results show that the best predictor of student's PEOU of e-learning systems is Self-Efficacy ($\beta=0.352$), followed by Enjoyment ($\beta=0.341$), Experience ($\beta=0.221$), Computer Anxiety ($\beta=-0.199$) and Subjective Norm ($\beta=0.195$). The best predictor of student's PU

of e-learning systems is Enjoyment ($\beta=0.452$), followed by Subjective Norm ($\beta=0.301$), Self-Efficacy ($\beta=0.174$) and Experience ($\beta=0.169$)” (Abdullah & Ward, 2016, p. 40).

Some studies are based on combined models including aspects of the TAM models as well as elements of other research frameworks. The integration of the expectancy disconfirmation theory (EDT), the expectations confirmation model (ECM), the theory of planned behavior (TPB) or the innovation diffusion theory (IDT) can be found. Most frequently, the TAM models were combined with the system success dimensions system quality, service quality and information quality, as explained in the Information system success chapter. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, pp. 37–42)

Based on Hassanzadeh et al. who developed an integrated model of the D&M IS success model and previous findings on e-learning system success, in 2015 Mohammadi published an integrated model of the TAM and D&M IS success model. This study combined the analyzation of the quality dimensions and their influence on user satisfaction and use of e-learning systems with the impact of the construct’s perceived usefulness and ease of use from the TAM model. System quality has the highest influence on students’ satisfaction and their intention to use the e-learning system. Information quality, service quality and educational quality also showed positive effects on satisfaction. Interesting are the practical recommendations based on which elements of the design of e-learning systems are perceived as useful or lead to the use of the system. An aesthetic, well-structured layout with interactive features and possibilities to allow students to print and to transfer content as well as always keeping the overview of the learning process are some of these recommendations for appropriate system quality which should awake students’ interest. Furthermore, the availability of wide support and help opportunities with communication channels as well as tutorials and instruction materials are recommended. Synchronous and asynchronous communication features should enable collaboration and debate as well as contribute to initiating critical thinking which is important for in-depth learning. Besides these quality dimensions, perceived usefulness also positively influences the intention to use e-learning systems. Therefore features like e-mail notifications, on recordings of new sessions or summaries of uploads or posts while the student is absent from the system are recommended to increase the students perceived usefulness of the system, as this leads to higher intention to use the system. Also the importance of social and human factors was pointed out, as learning system managers should be aware of the users’ social and individual roles, risks and norms, while implementing a system. (Mohammadi, 2015, pp. 369–372)

Summarized and based on the literature review of Al-Fraihat, these examples showed that the TAM model and its measurements and research structure are suitable and tested in the field of evaluating the success of e-learning systems (Al-Fraihat, 2019, p. 43). Furthermore, these examples have shown different perspectives on how to adapt the external variables to meet the needs of learning solutions which are always unique due to their specific target group of users,

facilitators, teachers, and administrators. Some of the results which are relevant for this research are summarized here. The diversity of learning styles, the interactivity of learning materials and the facilitation through communication channels were identified as impact factors of students' acceptance of learning systems (Selim, 2003, pp. 344–357). Media-richness has significant impact on the intention to use an e-learning system (Liu et al., 2005, p. 180). Further design of learning material (B.-C. Lee et al., 2009, p. 1327), computer anxiety (Abdullah & Ward, 2016, p. 40; H.-R. Chen & Tseng, 2012, p. 404), and computer self-efficacy (Abdullah & Ward, 2016, p. 40; H.-R. Chen & Tseng, 2012, p. 404) need to be considered in future research.

The diversity of e-learning settings requires the flexibility of the TAM research framework to include diverse external variables, as most of the researchers have shown that these external variables have an impact on satisfaction. However, some other authors say the TAM model is leading to chaos. Many researchers see the TAM model therefore as a useful model which has explanatory power, but the studies with extended versions of the TAM model mostly explained a higher total variance of system use. That might also be the reason why others say that the TAM model only makes sense once it is integrated in a wider model including social change and other human and case study related processes. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, p. 43)

Application of the UTAUT model in e-learning

Almaiah & Alyoussef compared several previous studies of e-learning acceptance. Based on their results of this literature review they saw the UTAUT model as the most appropriate framework to measure the determinants of e-learning system usage in Saudi Universities. According to their findings, the UTAUT especially suits when there is a customer-focused context, and to explain the system adoption by users. Evaluating the usage of an e-learning system from students' perspective fits to that focus and therefore they applied and adapted the UTAUT model. Their results support the original UTAUT model. (Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019, p. 171908)

Throughout the years, research has confirmed that the UTAUT model is a successful instrument to evaluate the acceptance of e-learning systems in several countries, including studies from developed and developing countries. During this process, several variations of the model were developed. The variables performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, behavioral intention and facilitating conditions showed the highest significance in evaluations of e-learning system acceptance. In the results, behavioral intention and facilitating conditions showed the biggest effect on the acceptance of the e-learning system in a postgraduate program at a university in Indonesia. (Mahande & Malago, 2019, Chapter 1,4,6,7)

The application of the UTAUT to evaluate students' use of Moodle as a virtual learning environment at a technical faculty of Maribor university in Slovenia conducted in 2010 showed interesting results. The performance expectations and social influence showed a significant impact on students' attitude towards using the LMS Moodle. But the effort expectations did not, which the

authors concluded as an important hint for all e-learning system stakeholders. Students use the e-learning system when they see it as useful for their studying, not because it is easy to use. They also found no significant impact of effort expectancy, performance expectation and attitude towards using on the intention of students to use the system. The authors see the limitations in the lack of adaptations of the UTAUT model for the context of e-learning system use, and call therefore for further researchers to investigate the factors impacting students' performance expectations. (Sumak et al., 2010, pp. 20–21)

In 2019 Almaiah & Alyoussef concluded in their publication that the UTAUT model, even if it is of great use in the evaluation of e-learning systems, needs slight adaptations to fit better for this sector. Besides the determinants explained in the original UTAUT model there are further aspects like course design quality, conditions of facilitation, course content support, design of course assessment and instructors' characteristics that could impact the acceptance and usage of e-learning systems and should therefore be additionally included in evaluations of success or acceptance factors of e-learning systems. Due to asymmetric distribution Almaiah & Alyoussef left out the moderating aspects of the original UTAUT model which are gender, age, experience, and voluntariness of system use. They added the variables instructors' characteristics, course content support, course assessment and course design. Multimedia features like videos and animations within the learning materials, as well as communication tools like online chats, are elements of variable course content support, introduced in the adapted UTAUT model by Almaiah & Alvoussef. Including these elements in e-learning courses leads to higher acceptance and usage of the system according to their findings. Further appropriate course design leads directly to increasing acceptance of the e-learning system. Clear communication of learning objectives, course structure, course information and clear layout are such elements of course design. The variable courses assessment also showed a positive effect on the performance expectation and the use of the e-learning system. Continuous online assessments, immediate feedback on assessments and self-assessment tests are aspects which motivate and lead students to accept and use the e-learning system. The instructor characteristics are an ambivalent construct. According to the results of this study there is a direct significant positive impact of instructor characteristics on the use of the e-learning system. While previous studies found mostly indirect effects like motivating aspects which impact the use of the system. These motivational relations did mainly appear under conditions like the instructors need to have competent computer skills, a positive attitude towards interactions with the system, experience in setting virtual classes or uploading learning materials. **Course Design and instructor characteristics were identified as the most important influencing factors on students e-learning system use.** So in conclusion, the development of instructor abilities is also seen as one of the key action points to establish e-learning successfully within an university. (Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019, pp. 171918–171920)

All these studies using the UTAUT model in the LMS context “lack in exploring the influence of students’ perceived value of LMS use in terms of learning gained from LMS, habitual LMS use and associated fun or pleasure” (Ain et al., 2016, p. 2). Evaluating the variables habit, hedonic motivation, and price value usage of the UTAUT2 model fills this lack in literature on e-learning system acceptance evaluation. The study conducted in 2015 at the government university in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, used the UTAUT2 model and adapted the price value to learning value and students’ perceived value of LMS use was adapted according to the e-learning context. As students appreciate the value of learning with an LMS more than the time and effort they have to spend using the system the results showed that students have a positive intention towards using their e-learning system. The study results further validated the UTAUT2 model in the LMS context by explaining the impact of social influence, performance expectancy and the facilitating conditions on the behavioral intention of students to use the LMS. The authors especially mentioned equipping and supporting students with the necessary infrastructure and technical environment as important parts of facilitating conditions. (Ain et al., 2016, p. 13)

Nearly all the applications of the UTAUT / UTAUT2 model showed the high impact of facilitation conditions or facilitator characteristics. Course design and adapting the learning system in a way that students see a value in using the system are also identified as important factors to design an e-learning system in a way that it reaches high acceptance and use by the students. (Ain et al., 2016, p. 2; Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019, pp. 171918–171920; Mahande & Malago, 2019, Chapter 1,4,6,7).

Considering the findings of the Research Perspective Technology Acceptance with regard to the question examined here, the following influencing factors should be taken into account in research. First of all the conclusion of a literature review showed that human factors and social change related factors need to be addressed while evaluating the acceptance of an e-learning system (Al-Fraihat, 2019, p. 43). Media richness (Liu et al., 2005, p. 180), course design or design of learning material (Ain et al., 2016, p. 2; Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019, pp. 171918–171920; B.-C. Lee et al., 2009, p. 1327; Mahande & Malago, 2019, Chapter 1,4,6,7), computer anxiety (Abdullah & Ward, 2016, p. 40; H.-R. Chen & Tseng, 2012, p. 404), computer self-efficacy (Abdullah & Ward, 2016, p. 40; H.-R. Chen & Tseng, 2012, p. 404) and in analogy to the findings of the D&M IS success model in chapter 3.2.1 the facilitator characteristics (Ain et al., 2016, p. 2; Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019, pp. 171918–171920; Mahande & Malago, 2019, Chapter 1,4,6,7) are factors that should be taken from the technology acceptance perspective for further studies of e-learning systems.

3.2.3 Further research perspectives

After looking at the system success perspective based on the D&M IS success model and the technology acceptance perspective with TAM and UTAUT models and their variations two perspectives were introduced which are widely discussed in the literature regarding e-learning success factors. However there are also further perspectives which inspired the researchers developing frameworks for blended-learning success criteria. To better understand those frameworks later on it is important to get an understanding of these basic concepts.

Satisfaction

Al-Fraihat classifies user satisfaction as another crucial perspective in research on information systems. Because satisfaction is a crucial measure in the success, the effectiveness, the usage and the acceptance of information systems. (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020, p. 69) Therefore this perspective is also relevant towards the question addressed in this paper, which is looking for criteria of successful technology supported blended-learning environments.

In Al-Fraihat's literature review, Cyrill et al. (1963) were found as the first researchers to introduce the concept of user satisfaction for the evaluation of information system success. They mentioned if the system fulfils the needs of the users, their satisfaction with the system will increase. Later on further publications supported this theory. (Al-Fraihat, 2019, p. 43)

For example, in their study Seddon and Kiew recommended user satisfaction as the most meaningful measured value to evaluate the information system success. (Seddon & Kiew, 1996, p. 102)

Several authors criticize this approach, as looking only at the satisfaction of system use as the indicator for system success ignores other important impact factors like the D&M quality dimensions explained in the Information system success chapter. Wixom and Todd recommend the use of an integrated system including aspects of the TAM model and links the acceptance approach with user satisfaction. (Wixom & Todd, 2005, p. 100)

In 2008 Sun et al. reviewed existing literature to elaborate which factors are important for the activities and affect learners' satisfaction of e-learning. The findings were grouped in six dimensions of perceived e-learning users' satisfaction. Environment, design, technology, course, instructor, and learner are these critical impact factors. As shown in Figure 11, thirteen variables are split over these six dimensions. (Sun et al., 2008, pp. 1184–1185)

Figure 11: Dimensions and antecedents of perceived e-Learning satisfaction (Sun et al., 2008, p. 1185)

The empirical test through a research survey filled in by nearly 300 students of two public universities in Taiwan showed that 66.1% of the variance of perceived e-learning satisfaction can be explained by seven variables. Out of the thirteen variables the following seven showed significant impact on the perceived e-learning satisfaction: Diversity in assessment, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, course quality, e-learning course flexibility, instructor attitude toward e-learning and learner computer anxiety. Course quality is the most important impact factor out of this list, which is why the authors highlight the importance of carefully designed learning materials meeting the student's needs. Peer assessment or self-assessment are mentioned as examples to reach diversity in the assessment schemas as it is recommended to reach a variety of methods to evaluate the learnings. Furthermore, the authors recommend to choose the instructors for e-learning courses wisely as their commitment and attitude towards the e-Learning systems also has a high impact on students' satisfaction. (Sun et al., 2008, p. 1196)

In 2007 Lee and Hwang evaluated the impact of computer self-efficiency and the LMS from a user satisfaction perspective. Therefore they developed a model with the variables perceived ease of use of the LMS, perceived usefulness of the LMS, service quality on interaction and information quality which they assume to be related to the learners' satisfaction on the one hand. On the other side the self-regulatory learning strategy which is itself impacted by computer self-

efficacy is influencing the learner's satisfaction. In their empirical test at a university in South Korea they identified service quality which they understand in the sense of facilitator support, learners' self-regulatory learning strategy and computer self-efficacy as critical impact factors. However they didn't find support for an impact of information quality on learners' satisfaction. (J.-K. Lee & Hwang, 2007, pp. 74–77)

System effectiveness

However, satisfaction was not only evaluated individually, it's also a construct which was included in research work on other levels of research perspective.

“Satisfaction has been a widely used parameter to evaluate the effectiveness of learning environments” (Piccoli et al., 2001, p. 411).

And there is a large pool of literature, which also influences the state of research in the light of the research question but takes a broader perspective. The question of the effectiveness of IT systems and thus also the research on the effectiveness of e-learning systems. Some individual factors identified in these research papers are indeed impacting the question discussed here. Some researchers pick these aspects up in the blended-learning system success evaluation which will be discussed later on in section 3.4. However, the question of the effectiveness of an information system has to be placed on a higher level. Therefore, this research perspective is only marginally touched upon here, in contrast to the two perspectives System Success and System Acceptance.

The system effectiveness is “the outcome of the interaction between the user and the system. LMS effectiveness is measured in the length of time it took a user to accomplish a task and the accuracy with which the user achieved this” (Alomari et al., 2020, p. 23545).

In 2001, Piccoli et al. developed a framework for the dimensions and antecedents of virtual learning environment effectiveness. In their model human factors and design dimensions impact the effectiveness which they measure in performance, self-efficacy, and satisfaction. In the design dimension the variables learning model, technology, learner control, content and interaction were identified as points of measurement. In the human dimension, students and instructor characteristics variables are evaluated to identify their impact on the effectiveness. (Piccoli et al., 2001, pp. 402–406)

Task-Technology Fit

Another research perspective which is quite strongly related to the system success perspective was developed while the system success perspective tried over many years to find a better model to explain the issues of users struggling with IT systems. Some researchers tried to look at the problem from another perspective, and this perspective also brought some valuable

insights which were further used in the blended-learning success criteria evaluation and is therefore introduced here.

The ongoing issues related to the influence of IT on user performance inspired Goodhue and Thompson in 1995 to find a model to explain the connection between technology and individual performance. Two approaches had been discussed in the previous literature, seeing either the task-technology fit as a predictor of user performance or seeing users' attitude as predictor of IT system use. The authors wanted to combine these approaches. Their new comprehensive model was aiming to go beyond the D&M IS success model. Existing models had been missing the critical construct of task-technology fit, which helps to understand how technology influences a system user's performance. By merging these two approaches they further wanted to build a better theoretical basis for the impact of IT and performance. The term task-technology fit refers to tasks in the sense of activities which individuals do to turn inputs to outputs and technology refers to the IT systems used in various settings to assist users in their tasks. (Goodhue & Thompson, 1995, pp. 213–218)

“Task-technology fit (TTF) is the degree to which a technology assists an individual in performing his or her portfolio of tasks. More specifically, TTF is the correspondence between task requirements, individual abilities, and the functionality of the technology” (Goodhue & Thompson, 1995, pp. 217–218).

The task-technology fit can be used as an indicator in specially-developed diagnostic tools to understand the gaps between the user needs and the IT system capabilities better. That would help to redesign the tasks of users to take the advantage of the system, to design a new system functionality or to design training for users to increase the abilities of individuals to successfully use the system. The results of the research showed that the evaluation of the task-technology fit is impacted by system characteristics as well as by task characteristics. And task-technology fit and utilization impact the predicted performance of a system. (Goodhue & Thompson, 1995, pp. 228–230)

Lin and Wang had applied this task-technology fit construct in their evaluation around the antecedences to continued intentions of adopting e-learning system in blended-learning instruction. As Goodhue and Thompson recommended, they used the TTF as a diagnostic tool to measure the degree on which the LMS supports the learners to achieve the learning requirements. The results of their research showed significant support for their hypothesis that TTF is positively related with the confirmation of system acceptance and that TTF is positively related to students' perceived usefulness of the learning system. (W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, pp. 90, 94)

McGill and Klobas came to equal findings. They found a significant positive effect of task-technology fit on the attitude towards using the LMS (McGill & Klobas, 2009, p. 503).

Social Cognitive Theory

The social cognitive theory was published by Bandura in 1986. This theory widely used and accepted to explain an anticipated behavior of humans and to find methods on how this behavior can be changed. (Bandura, 1977) The construct Self-Efficacy was introduced by Bandura's social cognitive theory as one of the principal mechanisms through which behavioral modeling operates. Compeau and Higgins applied the social cognitive theory to training in computer skills. They used Bandura's basic framework to elaborate the processes of how the training impacts and the effectiveness of different methods. Within the research framework they adapted self-efficacy to computer self-efficacy which measures how confident users believe that they are in solving computer-related issues by themselves. (Compeau & Higgins, 1995, pp. 119–122) The construct computer self-efficacy is later widely used in system evaluations and therefore also in e-learning system evaluations.

Based on the insights of the two technical perspectives of system success and technology acceptance, it became obvious that further perspectives should be included in order to incorporate social and human factors into the evaluation of success criteria of an e-learning system (Al-Fraihat, 2019, p. 43). System satisfaction, system effectiveness, the task-technology fit, which is describing the connection between technology and individual user performance and the social cognitive theory have been discussed in this chapter as further research perspectives with relevance for the aim of this thesis. In satisfaction models the following relevant factors have been identified. In addition to the already mentioned factors like course design, self-efficacy, course quality, instructor and learner characteristics, the learner's perception of the environment within the e-learning system impacts their satisfaction (Sun et al., 2008, pp. 1184–1185). For this reason, future investigations should also include a measurement of the learning environment. Satisfaction is also elaborated by several authors in relation to system effectiveness (Piccoli et al., 2001, p. 411). As the investigation on the efficiency of an e-learning system, however, leads too far and is not relevant to the aim of this research, also the factors of the system efficiency investigations are not further considered. However, the factor task-technology fit which measures the relation of how technology influences a system user's performance should be considered in future evaluations regarding success criteria of e-learning systems. In several studies, this factor showed significant impact on users' perception of the usefulness of an e-learning system. (W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, p. 94; McGill & Klobas, 2009, p. 503)

3.3 Criteria of e-learning system success

After looking in detail at information system success models, technology acceptance models and further perspectives, a huge variety of evaluation approaches have been identified. Nearly

all publications on these models in the e-learning context showed that either additional variables for the e-learning context were added, or researchers called for further adaptations to meet the needs of e-learning systems, as e-learning systems differ from the original information system for which the models had been originally developed.

“Technology alone does not cause learning to occur” (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 162). This conclusion is related to the social cognitive theory, which says that human behavior occurs in reciprocity with the cognitive impact factors, the environment and the human behavior itself. Accordingly, the research on success factors of e-learning system needs a framework including technological, social, and environmental aspects of e-learning. (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 162)

The variety of studies from all over the world introduced in the previous chapters showed e-learning-specific impact factors. Some of them were mentioned repeatedly as crucial factors for e-learning evaluation identified from different research perspectives. The common characteristics of these factors are their focus on the human, environmental and social perspective of the e-learning system use. With these in mind, there is the need to find a comprehensive model combining social and technology aspects.

Hassan Selim already examined in 2007 this huge variety of e-learning success factors. At the beginning he organized them in four categories, and in later research results extended them to show eight categories of critical success factors: (Selim, 2007, pp. 403–408)

“(1) instructor’s attitude towards and control of the technology, (2) instructor’s teaching style, (3) student motivation and technical competency, (4) student interactive collaboration, (5) e-learning course content and structure, (6) ease of on-campus internet access, (7) effectiveness of information technology infrastructure, and (8) university support of e-learning activities. Each of the 8 categories included several critical measures.” (Selim, 2007, p. 408)

The e-learning-specific factors identified throughout the chapters above go along well with these categories identified by Selim.

With regard to the research question of this thesis which is limited to the perspective of students in marginalized regions when investigating the success factors of e-learning systems, the findings from studies in developing countries are particularly crucial.

W. Bhuasiri et al. investigated the critical success factors that influence the adoption of e-learning systems in developing countries. Building on studies of the critical success factors of e-learning systems, including the aforementioned study by Selim, the authors developed basic factors. They also included the research perspectives of social cognitive theory, the information system success model, the technology acceptance model, and motivational theories. This resulted in seven categories of general e-learning success factors: learner characteristics,

instructor characteristics, extrinsic motivation, infrastructure and system quality, course and information quality, institution and service quality, and e-learning quality. The authors then used the Delphi method to ask ITC experts and e-learning experts in developing countries which factors they thought were important for the acceptance of e-learning systems in developing countries and to prioritize them. The result of the survey was a research model with six categories and 20 factors. (Bhuasiri et al., 2012, pp. 844–849) These factors are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Hierarchical model for e-learning critical success factors in developing countries. (Bhuasiri et al., 2012, p. 851)

The results showed that, from the experts' point of view, the most important success factors for e-learning systems in developing countries

“were related to increasing technology awareness and an attitude toward e-learning, enhancing basic technology knowledge and skills, improving learning content, requiring computer training, motivating users to utilize e-learning systems, and requiring a high level of support from the university” (Bhuasiri et al., 2012, p. 853).

These results are of central importance for this work, as they focus on developing countries and prove that from the point of view of this target group, other factors are partly of importance. This thesis focuses on the evaluation of the success criteria of blended-learning systems, a subgroup of e-learning systems according to Arnold et.al., while Bhuasiri et al analyzed critical success factors of e-learning systems in general. However, the findings regarding a target group in developing countries are relevant for the interpretation of the results in chapter 6.

Looking at the case of blended-learning, which is addressed by this study, the criteria for successful blended-learning systems get even more specific. Lin and Wang mentioned in their publication of 2012 that blended learning requires successfully-designed learning environments adopted according to instructional design aspects with the aim to design a platform enabling students to achieve learning goals. This is because blended learning combines pedagogical practice while learning in-class and learning online. To enable this pedagogical practice even during the online phases a suitable platform is needed. Literature found many positive influences of such an ideal blended-learning approach on students learning. Examples are peer pressure as success factors in online discussions, increasing skills in knowledge co-creation through online collaborative work or students growing project management skills through a blended-learning experience which is following instructional methods. (W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, p. 89) The question of how to design such a system was addressed by many publications, building upon the research perspectives of system success, system acceptance or further approaches connected to e-learning system success as previously discussed. These findings were further adapted to include the social and instructional aspects of blended learning as mentioned by Lin and Wang, 2012. Which approaches researchers published to specify the identified success aspects of e-learning further for blended-learning frameworks will be discussed in the following chapter.

3.4 Research models for Blended-Learning System evaluation

This paper aims to identify key criteria of success of blended learning systems. The previous chapters looked through several perspectives on the success criteria of e-learning systems. Following the development of impacting factors over the years was helpful to understand which showed significance throughout the time and which new trends came up and showed significance in the most recent research. For all these research models the weaknesses and extensions needed for the application in the e-learning context were discussed with several examples of previous studies from all over the world. The conclusion of these chapters was the call for a comprehensive model focusing on both social and technological aspects impacting the e-learning system use. In the end of this analysis process of these existing comprehensive models the

result needs to be one research framework applicable for the use case of this thesis. As the focus of this thesis is blended-learning programs, it is now necessary to take a look at the comprehensive blended-learning models.

In 2009 at the Middle East Technical University in Turkey the authors Ozkan and Koseler conducted a research study to find a model which helps to conceptualize and measure LMS for blended-learning settings as well as for fully web-based programs. Their aim was to find a model which merges technical and social issues of e-learning. What they developed was the Hexagonal E-Learning Assessment Model, in short HELAM. As the name says, it consists of six dimensions with a total of 45 criteria spread over these dimensions. From the technical perspective of LMS use, they included the three quality dimensions of the D&M IS success model: system quality, information quality, which they understand mainly as content quality, and the service quality. As a comprehensive model the HELAM model also addresses the social issues with three dimensions. As the review of previous e-learning studies also showed, the facilitators' and students' perception of the learning environment should be included. So, the HELAM model added the learners' perspective and instructors' perspective as the fourth and fifth dimensions. What is new in this model and hadn't been mentioned in the reviewed literature in the chapters above in that compressed form is the sixth dimension which also addresses social issues, the supportive factors. The authors see the impact of the promotion of the LMS, current popularity of LMS products and tools, the costs, trends like social and political trends as well as ethical and legal issues as important factors impacting the effectiveness of an LMS and included this dimension in their model. In an empirical test they validated their instrument and reached an explained variance of 62,15% which shows their model as successful. Furthermore they found significant support for all six of their dimensions. The challenges are seen in the missing study on the interrelations of the model's aspects. That is especially important in the dimensions related to the D&M model, as already earlier studies pointed out that these are multidimensional constructs. So even if the model itself is validated and so a useful instrument for conceptualizing the implementation of LMS, further research on the relationships in the blended-learning context between the points of measurement are needed. (Ozkan & Koseler, 2009, secs. W1C-2-W1C-5)

One year later in 2010, J.-H. Wu et al. pointed out that there was a lack in studies investigating in the crucial determinants of blended-learning satisfaction, with a deeper focus on the educational aspects of technology and the context of blended-learning environments. They came up with a research model with a huge difference to all the models discussed here before, they had a quite different theoretical foundation for their model, the social cognitive theory which was already introduced in section 3.2.3. In the case of this study the predicted behavior is the user's satisfaction with the blended-learning systems. And the researchers try to identify the

determinants of the satisfaction. This theory sees a causation among the environmental impact, cognitive factors and the human behavior, as the environment influences the behavior through cognitive mechanisms. For further understanding of these environmental factors impacting the learners behavior, previous literature applying the model for the digital learning context came up with the split of technological environmental aspects like content features and system functionality and social environmental aspects in the sense of interaction and the learning climate. How these elements are structured in the research model is visualized in Figure 13. (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, pp. 156–157)

As the title of the model shows, in their study they used the term blended e-learning system in short BELS, whereas this paper uses the term blended-learning because the overarching focus has already made the reference to e-learning clear and the shortened form of blended learning is therefore sufficient.

Figure 13: The research model for BELS learning satisfaction (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 161)

This model was empirically tested with 212 valid questionnaires at universities in Taiwan. The results supported the hypothesis of all the paths shown in Figure 13 to the dependent variables performance expectation and learning climate. Between these two, performance expectations have the higher impact on the satisfaction. Overall, the results strongly supported the model as a useful instrument to evaluate blended learning satisfaction. In the conclusion related to the social cognitive theory these results mean that human behavior is the reciprocation of environmental factors and cognitive factors. Therefore, the authors pointed once again out that not only the technical environment causes learning, but the other impact factors are also important and need to be involved in the evaluation. As the results might differ by country, culture, or context

the research should be continued. Also the continuous development in blended-learning systems leads to the continuous need to uncover additional impact factors on blended-learning satisfaction. (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, pp. 162–163)

In 2012 Lin and Wang published an evaluation of the influence of the task-technology fit in blended-learning environments. They looked at measuring how the adoption of the LMS to achieve the learning goals impacts the students' continued intention to use the system. As mentioned before, the authors' perspective is directed towards a pedagogical designed format of blended learning. The research framework included the D&M IS success model quality dimensions as well as the task-technology-fit model, as internal confirmation of system acceptance. The TAM-approach-related constructs perceived usefulness and the system satisfaction are seen as external contingency factors. Examination of these internal and external factors is inspired by the contingency theory and should lead to the evaluation of overall system acceptance and continuance to use intention. The results of their research showed that blended-learning environments provide benefits as an effective teaching method for online learning as well as for the face-face sessions. The D&M IS success factor information quality showed significant impact. But the authors also pointed out that investing in the quality of the system is not enough as the factors perceived usefulness, system satisfaction and instructor's behavior also had an important influence on learners' continued to use intention. Furthermore, they found support for the task-technology fit as an important impact factor on the utilization of the LMS. Therefore, they call for strategies to promote the systems, their functionalities, and benefits for teaching along with the process of enrolling an LMS in higher education institutions. Training or extrinsic motivations like credits for facilitators using the system should motivate instructors to develop a positive mindset towards the system and use it effectively as teaching method. (W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, p. 96)

When examining existing literature in 2012, Kamla Ali Al-Busaidi found that there was still something missing; none of the existing studies looked at classmates' characteristics, course characteristics and organizational characteristics in addition to the LMS characteristics and learners and instructors' characteristics. Furthermore, the learners' perspective was mostly evaluated according to one or two, and not all of the following dimensions: system use, satisfaction, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use. In addition, the overall perspective on measuring the continuous intention to use an LMS in the blended-learning context was newly added. The empirical test of the new model combining all these aspects took place with 512 students at the Sultan Qaboos University in Oman. Nearly all students had at least one semester experience with using the LMS. The author highlights the importance of intensified internet training and computer literacy especially in developing countries as students are sometimes lacking these skills. The learner's characteristics are important as in the group of learner characteristics computer anxiety, technology experience, computer self-efficacy and personal innovativeness were

the points of measurement and these aspects had been found as significantly impacting at least one or more dimensions of success. Similarly, for the classmates' characteristics, which are measured in the classmates' attitude and interactions, and the course characteristics flexibility and quality, all these are significantly influencing the system success and therefore the designers of the blended-learning system should strengthen these factors. Only self-efficacy was not found to be significant for system success. Furthermore, the role of the instructor is important and therefore the instructors should be trained and be aware of their impact on the success of the blended learning system. Because their attitude and control on the system impacts the students' perceived ease of use while their instruction style influences the perceived usefulness and the satisfaction. Only for the influence of the instructor's online responsiveness on the system success Kamla Ali Al-Busaidi found no explanation through the empirical test. On the three quality dimensions of the D&M IS success model which are in this research grouped as LMS Characteristics, enough empirical support was found on several LMS success dimensions, which leads to the call for continuous development and improvement of the LMS. In the last group of characteristics, the organizational factors, training was found as significantly impacting students perceived usefulness, which further supports the call for intensive training of students to prepare them for the use of a blended-learning system. But for the management support the influence on the LMS success was not validated by the empirical test.

The author recommends that future researchers test the model in settings with obligatory enrollment of an LMS all over the institution as well as in blended-learning settings in cross-cultural or global context. (Al-Busaidi, 2012, pp. 28–29)

In 2018 Ghazal et al. slightly adapted this model by reducing the dependent variables to perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness following the TAM approach and finally concluding the student satisfaction (Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018, p. 77181). Al-Busaidi also measured the dependent variables system use and user satisfaction and finally evaluated the continued intention to use (Al-Busaidi, 2012, p. 15). The groups of characteristics stayed the same, only the variable personal innovativeness was removed from the learners' characteristics, and in the instructors' characteristics the instructors control was changed to practice which basically is a different labeling for the instructors ability to control the progress on the LMS. Ghazal, Al-Samarraie et al. conducted their study with 174 responding students from three universities in different regions of Yemen. All students had already used the blended-learning system. As in the results of Kamla Ali Al-Busaidi this study found in the instructor characteristics the continuous in time online support and responses as the most important criteria. Facilitator training to develop the capacities for the design, enrollment, and teaching process with support of digital systems is also seen as one of the most important implications. But also workshops to enhance students' capabilities in using digital solutions within their learning process are recommended, as there is an association between computer skills and their ability to use the system. But consistent with

previous studies there was also no significant relationship between students' experience with technology and their perceived ease of use. Ghazal, Al-Samarraie et al. argues that well-designed learning systems should not require special technology experience to be perceived as useful. Another interesting observation of this study was the positive impact of classmates' interaction and attitude on students' recognition of seeing the LMS as useful. Course designers should therefore plan the role and interactions of students and their peers wisely within the learning process as this can lead to effective interaction in the digital learning environment. Ghazal, Al-Samarraie et al. see one of the main limitations of their study in the missing evaluation of the design of the course content. And also, that the participants of their study had been part of different courses which might follow different design frameworks and offering different learning experiences. These individual experiences can lead to different perceptions based on the courses rather than the system which is evaluated. Future researchers who plan to conduct such a study should take into account this impact factor for example by focusing on consistency in the course design of courses included in the evaluation. (Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018, pp. 77188–77195)

Also in 2018, a study to identify a conceptual framework to specify critical factors for the satisfaction and acceptance of LMSs in blended learning settings was conducted by Ghazal, Aldowah et al. at a university in Yemen. Based on the D&M Model, the quality dimensions system, service and information quality are used as points of measurement. Further technology experience is included as the fourth factor. To evaluate the acceptance and satisfaction of an LMS in blended learning, the acceptance is split according to the TAM approach into perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. The other factor to assess the impact of the four variables is the student satisfaction. In contrast to the findings in the studies of Al-Busaid and Ghazal, Aldowah et al. discussed before, this research found that technology experience significantly impacted the perceived ease of use and the perceived usefulness. But there was no influence on student satisfaction found. The authors see a potential reason in the variety of technology experience. The skills that students acquired via prior experiences using the internet may not correspond to a technically-supported blended-learning environment. In line with most of the earlier publications in this field, student's system quality is a critical factor for all aspects of acceptance and satisfaction and can be particularly influenced by a user-friendly and interactive interface. The information quality in the sense of readable, accurate, up-to-date and well-formatted course materials are perceived as useful, and satisfied students. However, no real impact of the quality of information on the perception of ease of use could be identified. For service quality, only significant impact on the perceived ease of use was found. There was no significant impact on students' perceived usefulness and satisfaction, which the authors explain by the already moderate technology experience of the students participating in their evaluation. (Ghazal, Aldowah, et al., 2018, pp. 689–690, 696–697)

In 2019, authors Seman et al. investigated what students' predictors are toward using an LMS in a blended-learning system. They also investigated the relationship between the overall satisfaction and students' continuous intention to use the LMS within a blended-learning system. The target group within their investigation was a group of first year students who are new to the blended-learning system and the majority of students were below 22-years-old. They focused on this young group of students because they wanted to evaluate the research question from the perspective of millennial learners. Their research framework was mainly based on the D&M IS success model as they used the quality dimensions. They also measured the impact of individual characteristics upon students' satisfaction via the constructs computer anxiety and technology experience. Also, course quality and instructor quality are points of measurement summarized in the category of courses characteristics. Thus, the three categories individual characteristics, system characteristics and course characteristics were investigated for their impact on student satisfaction and how this in turn affects continuous intention to use the LMS in the blended-learning system. The results of the study showed that the overall satisfaction of the students has an important influence on whether the students continue to use the LMS during their learning process. The most important factors within this model were the course quality and the facilitator quality, where the authors found significant results as well as for the service quality. Interestingly and in contrast to the findings of previous studies, the information quality and system quality showed no significant impact on students' satisfaction while the service quality did. (Seman et al., 2019, p. 130,136-137)

Literature shows, as discussed in the examples above that human factors have a huge impact, especially in blended learning settings - be it different technical skills, fears, or personal attitudes of the facilitator towards the system, the social structure of the classroom, or differences in the perception of the system's benefits caused by regional or cultural factors.

The benefits of blended learning are widely known and accepted. Many institutions try to introduce an LMS in their higher education institutions to enrich their programs via blended learning courses. Although many studies have pointed to the influence of human factors especially for the successful introduction of blended-learning environments, these findings are often overlooked, according to Alomari et al. The authors found in the current research as well as in the practical introductions of LMSs, cases which still fail due to the failure to consider human factors. Based on these insights, the authors investigated a framework for the impact of human factors in their study published in 2020. Their focus is on the effectiveness of an LMS used in private and public colleges and universities in Kuwait with a sample size of 402. Alomari et al. based their framework for the impact of human factors on two previously discussed research constructs. The framework of Piccoli et al. on the effectiveness of virtual learning environments which was used as a basic concept to extract several variables as well as the hexagonal e-learning assessment model (HELAM). This model was suitable according to the researchers'

perspective as within this model in 2009 the authors Ozkan and Koseler added the additional perspectives of social issues to their research model. The aspects of learner characteristics and facilitator characteristics were taken up by Alomari et al. as well as several other impacting characteristics identified throughout a comprehensive literature review. After conducting a qualitative research, their initial estimated framework was updated by adding newly emerged factors. These factors are shown in Figure 14. The variables are grouped in three dimensions, technological factors, psychological factors, and interaction factors. For all of them a significant impact on user satisfaction was found. In this publication the user satisfaction is a dependent variable impacting the effectiveness of a blended learning LMS. (Alomari et al., 2020, pp. 23543–23554)

Figure 14: The updated model of human-related dimensions on the effectiveness of LMS at Kuwait's higher education Institutes (Alomari et al., 2020, p. 23553).

This relationship towards the effectiveness is not relevant for the aim of this research, which focuses on the key criteria of user satisfaction with blended learning systems. But the elaborated impact factors are important within this focus.

The results showed strong impact of the factors self-efficacy, usefulness, and enjoyment. The factors teaching style, promptness, feedback, learning style, availability, interaction, control, and attitude, showed variable levels of medium impact. All factors have an impact on the satisfaction, only for the factor fairness a weaker impact on satisfaction was found. For this reason, the influence on the factors mentioned should always be questioned when designing blended learning programs with the integration of an LMS. In the conclusion of this publication the authors point out the importance of strategies and tools to accommodate technological, interactional, and psychological aspects. Strengthen the self-efficacy of system users and their enjoyment will foster

their satisfaction. As already most of the other authors mentioned, proper training for facilitators as well as students is the recommended approach to decrease technology anxiety, negative attitudes towards the system and other barriers. Alomari et al. also brought aspects in their conclusions which are new to the implications discussed here before. They found significant impact for the factor brand, in the sense of users' opinions about the brand, which impacts their satisfaction. The authors conclude that institutions should preferably use widely-known LMS instead of a system which is not commonly used anywhere else. Further contributing to this aspect is the marketing of the LMS, institutions introducing an LMS should invest in the marketing of their system to increase the image of their LMS and convince the users of the benefits of the system use. (Alomari et al., 2020, pp. 23551–23554)

In 2020, another study on the factors influencing the success of blended-learning systems was conducted at a university in the United States. The researchers tried to address the lack of one research framework, bringing together a comprehensive set of variables from different perspectives in current literature. Therefore, they developed a model and validated it in an empirical study. The participants of their study were first-year students from a mandatory introduction course on IT systems, which is a blended-learning program. Hundreds of students at several colleges all over the university take part in this course which includes face-to-face sessions in class as well as online components. During the course students meet weekly with their instructor in face-to-face sessions where they conduct activities and interaction between the classmates and instructor. As well as these meetings, in the online self-study phases the online LMS including a submission system and user-interactive, multimedia, digital textbooks are used. With their study, the authors Gavin Zhang and Yan Dang aim to broaden the understanding of the success of students in such blended-learning environments. Based on earlier literature on the evaluation of blended-learning success they wanted to create a comprehensive model combining three perspectives: Self-related factors, technology and system factors, and instructional design factors. In their understanding, all measures in education should be focused on the student, so they particularly focus on factors that can impact student learning in the blended-learning environment. Therefore, their model includes the student self-related factors, where aspects of the previously discussed human factors are included. As earlier literature widely agreed on the important impact of the multiple validated success dimensions according to D&M, these are also included. Together with media richness these are the technological factors from a system success and acceptance perspective. The media richness is an important impact factor in e-learning system acceptance according to Liu et al. 2005, discussed in relation to the TAM model. The third perspective in their model are the factors of instructional design. Previous studies in this field have repeatedly highlighted the importance of instructional design. Compared to the research models discussed here, however, it is a new approach by the authors Zhang and Dang to integrate the influences of instructional design into the model as an independent third

perspective. Within the perspective of instruction design, the point of measurement is the teaching method. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 491–496)

“The teaching method is defined as the variety of specific learning activities and tasks adopted in blended learning for students to perform and complete” (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 495).

For all the factors in these three groups, the authors created hypotheses for their impact on three dependent constructs: learning climate, task-technology fit and the blended-learning flexibility. The learning climate is the atmosphere associated with all action in the learning process in class or within a digital learning environment. In the model, the learning climate further influences the satisfaction and the intention of the students to use the system. The second depended construct included in their model is the task-technology fit. As already discussed, in 2012 W.-S. Lin and Wang published their research results on the task-technology fit. They evaluated the effect of adapting the system to the task on the system success. The results of this study led Zhang and Dang to include this construct in their comprehensive blended learning success model. The third construct impacting the satisfaction and intention in this model is the blended-learning flexibility. The authors define this construct as the level of flexibility that students must complete all learning process related activities. That students have the freedom to work individually, in terms of location, pace and time. Finally, hypothesis are defined to measure the impact of these three constructs on the intention, in the sense of willingness to take further courses following this framework and the satisfaction with the blended-learning framework. According to the research findings of the authors their model is one of the first combining these three perspectives and suggesting the related factors and constructs. The empirical test with nearly 700 responses showed that students' motivation has significant impact on students' perception of the learning climate and the task-technology fit. However, blended-learning flexibility was not supported by computer self-efficacy or motivation. Also on the other two relations no significant impact was found for self-efficacy. The importance of continuous maintenance for a high quality level of IT infrastructure is essential for the success of blended learning, as on an overall level the results showed significant impact of all system factors on students perceptions of blended-learning-flexibility, task-technology fit as well as learning climate. But looking at the detailed results, information quality and media-richness do not significantly impact the learning climate. Furthermore, system quality had no significant influence on task-technology fit. Media-richness was not significant for the perception of the task-technology fit. For information quality the results of the impact on the perception of blended-learning flexibility was unexpected for the authors. Information quality seems to be statistically significant but the coefficient along this path was negative. The authors call for further validation of this partly unexpected result. The perspective of instructional design measured by the teaching method supported all hypotheses with significant results. Furthermore, all the dependent constructs showed significant support for the impact

on students' intention to use the system for further courses and their satisfaction. Future research should test the model on more than only one class, with a wider range in terms of age, educational level or by extending to other contexts where blended-learning models are applied. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 498–504)

The continuous development of digital learning environments requires an equally continuous further development of the evaluation models (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 157). Therefore, the aim of the comparative literature analysis of the state of research carried out in the previous chapters should be to find a model that is as up-to-date as possible, which fits the context of the case study and at the same time takes into account the proven findings of previous studies. Models that are no older than 2018 were understood to be as up-to-date as possible. Nevertheless, it is important to include the key findings of blended learning research from previous years and to check whether significant influencing factors have been considered in the current models. These factors are briefly summarized here.

Compared to the literature on e-learning success criteria discussed earlier, the more focused research on blended-learning success criteria pays a lot of attention to social impact factors. The HELAM model published by Ozkan and Koseler was one of the first model to bring together technological aspects and social aspects of digital learning in one research framework (Ozkan & Koseler, 2009). One year later the Blended e-Learning Success model was published. This model is even more focused on social aspects of the learning environment, as it is not at all based on one of the basic frameworks of the technological perspective. Wu et al. who published this model based it on the social cognitive theory. They showed the impact of the educational aspects in the blended learning context and in particular showed that the learning environment which includes technical aspects as well as social environmental aspects influences the learner's behavior and learning climate. (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, pp. 156–157)

To include in the evaluation process the impact of pedagogical principles in the blended-learning design, the Task-Technology Fit construct was included by Lin and Wang in their evaluation framework. The task-technology fit showed significant impact and should therefore be further considered. (W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, p. 96)

Other influencing factors that should be taken into account, according to Al Busaidi, are classmate characteristics and course flexibility as well as organizational factors. Among the influencing factors from the organizational area, the influence of intensive training for the teachers was particularly positive (Al-Busaidi, 2012). In their publication `I'm still learning` from 2018, Ghazal also underlines the significance of the influencing factors classmate interaction and facilitator training. The authors of this publication mentioned as a limitation the missing evaluation of the design and course content (Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018). This is a reason why this framework was not considered further as suitable for the evaluation of the case study within this thesis.

In another publication of S.Ghazal et al in 2018 the authors evaluated critical factors to learning management system acceptance and satisfaction in a blended-learning environment. The framework included aspects of the TAM perspective as well as the DeLone & McLearn quality dimensions. The social and human factors of influence, as well as the pedagogical aspects of the course design, emphasized by the other authors, were hardly taken into account in this evaluation model. (Ghazal, Aldowah, et al., 2018) Influencing factors that have been important in various previous studies over the years should not be ignored and therefore this model was not taken further as a candidate for this study.

In contrast, the model published by Almoari et al. in 2020 to investigate the human factors influencing the effectiveness of an LMS includes a very broad spectrum of different perspectives of influence, and in particular the focus on human factors. (Alomari et al., 2020) But as already mentioned, this research approach to the study of effectiveness does not fit to the focus of this thesis, which focuses on the success criteria of blended-learning systems. In the final selection, the model of Seman et al. and the model of Zhang and Dang were left. The research model of Seman et al. was mainly focused on the LMS in the blended-learning program (Seman et al., 2019). But as described in section 2.1.3, the LMS JWL-HeLP is very strongly interwoven with the whole blended learning concept in JWL, this limited focus on the LMS was not sufficient to reflect the complexity of the case study.

Therefore, the most appropriated up-to-date framework is the comprehensive blended learning success model published by Zhang and Dang in 2020. This model fits quite well to the case study, as the framework was also designed and tested for the evaluation of a blended-learning program which includes weekly face-to-face meetings of learner groups as well as online self-study phases with interactive, multimedia learning materials. Furthermore, all three perspectives frequently mentioned as having an impact in this comparative literature analysis process are included: Self-related factors, technology and system factors, as well as instructional design factors. Even if the model has not yet been widely tested or applied due to the recent date of publication, the new approach of including this level of the dependent variables, learning climate, task-technology fit and blended learning flexibility sounds promising, as earlier literature mentioned the importance of these factors. The model was tested with students in the USA and therefore it is quite interesting to compare the results with an evaluation in developing countries. That would help to identify even more differences. Looking closely at the findings from the comparative literature analysis, it can be seen that the facilitator characteristics factor, which has shown significant influence in many studies (for example: Cheng, 2012, p. 365; Klobas & McGill, 2010, p. 118; Seman et al., 2019, p. 137) is unfortunately not considered in the model of Zhang and Dang. Although the lack of this crucial influencing factor in the research instrument is an argument against this model, the arguments for the use of this research model outweigh it. However, since in the context of JWL, the role of facilitator is divided into onsite and online

facilitator with different tasks, this factor would have to be strongly adapted to the JWL context and thus deviate strongly from an existing research instrument. The advantage of referring to an existing instrument in order to achieve comparable results would thus hardly be possible, and therefore the argument that the facilitator characteristics in the model of Zhang and Dang are not so important with regard to the research context of this work. At the same time, this should not be taken to mean that facilitator characteristics should be neglected. Rather, they must be examined in the context of JWL by means of an individually adapted research method and therefore it is not such a decisive factor that this criterion is missing in the model of Zhang and Dang. As described in the chapter on the research method, through an analysis with a qualitative approach with a focus on facilitator characteristics, this aspect identified in the literature analysis will also be considered in the overall findings of this study.

3.5 Comprehensive Blended Learning Success Model

In order to address the goal of this thesis, the search for success criteria of blended learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions worldwide, it was a crucial sub-step to investigate which influencing factors of blended learning systems are already known from the current state of the research literature. In the process of a comparative literature analysis, the state of the research literature was examined in the previous chapters from different perspectives. This intensive investigation made it possible to identify a comprehensive picture of already established success factors of system success in general as well as from evaluations in the e-learning context. Based on these backgrounds of identified factors, specific models from the blended learning area were considered in section 3.4 and one was selected that combines as many of the identified relevant aspects as possible and should be as up-to-date as possible. Thus, the best possible compromise had to be found in this decision. The choice therefore fell on the Blended-Learning Success Model which was published by Zhang and Dang in June 2020. Even though this model does not take into account the facilitator characteristics that have been identified as crucial, it is considered to be the most up-to-date and appropriate comprehensive blended learning success model for the context of this work.

The research model chosen for the evaluation conducted in this thesis considers blended learning success factors at three levels. As shown in Figure 15, the authors of this model, Zhang and Dang have grouped the external variables on a first level. Three different perspectives - the target group-focused perspective with self-related factors, the technology and system-related factors, and the instructional design factors - are thus included in the model. At the middle level of the model, the influence of concepts measured in the e-learning context is proven and represent a complex interplay of aspects of the learning process in the blended-learning environment, including the learning climate, the task-technology fit and the blended-learning flexibility. On the

third level, the factors that influence the success of a blended-learning system in the sense of the research question can be found. The satisfaction with the system and the intention of the students to use the blended-learning system for further courses are indicators for the blended-learning system's success. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 496)

The hypotheses and path dependencies of the variables shown by the arrows in Figure 15 will not be considered further in the context of this thesis, since it is more important to find out which factors correlate with others. An analysis as it was carried out by Zhang and Dang using the structural equation modeling is beyond the scope of this work and therefore these hypotheses will not be addressed in the following sections.

Figure 15: Blended Learning Success Model (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 496)

For each group of blended-learning success drivers there is a section in which the factors are presented as they are understood in the context of this work. Within the groups of blended-learning system success factors, each factor is briefly explained in terms of its influence in other studies, how the variable is understood in Zhang and Dang's research model, and which aspects are examined. In addition, the relevance in the context of the JWL case study is briefly explained at the end alongside the results from Zhang and Dang's study.

3.5.1 Self-Related Factors

The overarching goal of all efforts to innovate in education should be to provide students with better learning experiences. Students themselves are therefore at the center of the education system. If one wants to investigate what the critical success factors of a blended learning system are from the point of view of students in marginalized regions, one wants to draw from this the starting points for measures to improve the educational offer, therefore it is crucial to also investigate student-related factors. In a technology-enhanced educational offer, such as the blended learning system, the computer self-efficacy of the students but also the motivation of the students to use the technology system for their learning can have an impact on their perception of the system. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 492)

Computer Self-Efficacy

Previous literature on the success criteria of technology-supported learning showed interesting results in evaluations of the impact of an individual's beliefs upon their own abilities to use computers. Lee and Hwang found in their study published in 2007 significant impact of students computer self-efficacy on their self-regulated learning strategy which impacted the satisfaction to use the learning system (J.-K. Lee & Hwang, 2007, pp. 74–77). Furthermore, throughout their research Wu et. al. identified significant impact of students' computer self-efficacy on their performance expectations within a blended learning environment (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 162). And also Chen identified through the research process that computer self-efficacy affects students' learning outcome expectations while using a technology-supported learning environment (Y.-C. Chen, 2014, p. 168).

But on the other hand, in his study Kamala Ali Al-Busaidi, for example, could not find any significance of the influence of computer self- efficacy on system success (Al-Busaidi, 2012, p. 27). Precisely because the critical success factors were examined in this study, this difference in influence is particularly interesting to investigate. So some authors called for further investigation on the evaluation of the impact of computer self-efficacy (Abdullah & Ward, 2016, p. 40; H.-R. Chen & Tseng, 2012, p. 404). And Zhang and Dang included the variable computer self-efficacy in their research model. Throughout their test they identified that students' computer self-efficacy doesn't play a significant role in impacting any of the three dependent variables; the learning climate, the task-technology fit and blended learning flexibility (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501).

This research aims to investigate whether computer self-efficacy is one of the critical success factors of a blended learning system for students in marginalized regions. If so, this would provide a concrete starting point for measures to improve blended learning systems. The construct self-efficacy was introduced by Bandura's social cognitive theory as one of the principal mechanisms through which behavioral modeling operates. Compeau and Higgins who applied the

social cognitive theory to training for computer skills came up with the term computer self-efficacy. Therefore computer-related self-efficacy is evaluated to examine the extent to which a person is confident in successfully performing actions independently on a computer. (Compeau & Higgins, 1995, pp. 119–122) The evaluation of computer self-efficacy through a research instrument such as the questionnaire developed by Zhang and Dang, examines different items on this variable. The evaluation of self-efficacy can address different aspects, as self-efficacy can be described in three dimensions. The magnitude of self-efficacy expresses the degree of difficulty of tasks that a person is confident of mastering. The strength expresses how firmly the person is convinced of this statement. Self-efficacy expectations with a high strength are less easy to change than those with a low strength. Generalizability indicates the extent to which self-efficacy expectations are related to specific activities or to entire area of related activities. (Bandura, 1977, p. 194; Compeau & Higgins, 1995)

Motivation

Students' motivation can be seen as the incentive that makes students work hard and actively on their tasks within the blended-learning program. Rheinberg defines motivation in 2002 as the activating orientation of the current life towards a positively evaluated target state. The strength, duration and intensity of motivation have an influence on goal-oriented action. In the context of education, this definition can be understood as follows: the degree of motivation to learn determines whether and how intensively a student learns. There are different types of motivation; in education we often refer to intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of students. The intrinsic motivation comes from the person him- or herself, for example, because an activity is seen as exciting, interesting, or challenging. In contrast, extrinsic motivation is externally controlled and reached through positive consequences, e.g. praise and recognition. (Schiefele & Streblow, 2006, pp. 232–233)

In previous literature on the success criteria of e-learning or blended-learning systems, several researchers picked up the concept of motivation and looked into the details to evaluate potential cause-effect relationships. While some studies saw motivation as an indirect phenomenon, it was particularly from the perspective of technology acceptance that motivation was increasingly taken into account as an influencing criterion with the further development of the TAM and UTAUT models.

Selim evaluated in 2007 the critical success factors for e-learning acceptance and the results of the research process showed that the two student-related variables, technical competencies and students' motivation are impacting students e-learning acceptance. (Selim, 2007, pp. 403–408)

Particularly within the research perspective of technology acceptance, several authors adapted their models to meet these needs of including the measurement of motivation into their analysis

models. In TAM 3 the authors added more points of measurement for the determinants of perceived ease of system use. One of the variables which were added therefore was computer playfulness, which could be seen as the point of measurement for the intrinsic motivation. (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008, pp. 274–278)

In addition, Chen and Tseng have also identified the influence of motivation based on the Technology Acceptance Perspective. In their study they found that perceived usefulness is the primary impact factor on the intention to use, and this factor is mainly driven by motivation. (H.-R. Chen & Tseng, 2012, p. 404)

In 2012 Venkatesh updated the UTAUT Model to the second version and included hedonic motivation. Earlier researches found motivation constructs as important impact factor. (Venkatesh et al., 2012, p. 160) While Venkatesh adapted his model so that the influence of motivation on other variables in the evaluation is directly measurable, other authors saw motivation on a different level and concluded that it has an indirect motivating effect, as the following example shows. Almaiah and Alyoussef concluded in their 2019 publication that e-learning systems reaching high levels in students' evaluations of the variables course design and instructor characteristics, motivate students to use the e-learning system (Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019, p. 171918).

Zhang and Dang concluded from the available research that intrinsic motivation in particular has a positive impact on students' performance, their intention to learn with the system and thereby also on their use of the system. Therefore, they included the variable - motivation - in their research model. The results of their study showed that student motivation has a significant impact on the perception of the learning environment. Furthermore, students' motivation also affects their perception of the fit between tasks and the supporting technology. But significant effects on blended learning flexibility could not be found. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 492, 501)

The conditions under which students participated in the blended learning program evaluated by Zhang and Dang may be very different from those of this paper's target group. Therefore, it would be particularly interesting to investigate whether the students from marginalized regions assess the influence of their self-related factors like computer self-efficacy and their motivation differently than the group of students evaluated by Zhang and Dang. It is precisely these target group-specific findings on the critical influencing factors that make it possible to find starting points in practice to further expand the blended learning systems.

3.5.2 Technology and System Factors

Urbach and Müller anticipated in their 2011 paper that usage of the D&M IS success model will remain popular in the coming ten years even if only a few studies use the entire model. In their paper they also listed an exemplary collection of IS success studies which used the D&M IS

success model as theoretical basis. In sixteen categories of IS they listed 36 publications between 2001 and 2010 which used the DeLone and McLean research model. One of these categories is learning systems. (Urbach & Müller, 2012, pp. 12–14) As identified in the research on existing literature for this thesis as discussed in the previous chapters recently published papers often still include the basic success dimensions of DeLone and McLean's model from 2003. In the publications on the success factors of a blended-learning system, these three variables were very often used to evaluate the system functionalities. In many of these studies, this construct was found to have a significant positive influence on variables such as student satisfaction with the system or the learning climate or expected learning performance (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 494).

When examining the criteria that make up a successful blended-learning system, the technical aspects naturally also include the variety and appropriate use of digital media for presenting and conveying the learning content. In order to include the influence of this diversity and the media-pedagogical use of multimedia formats in the evaluation of the learning system, the variable media richness was introduced by numerous authors (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 494). With this extension, the generally proven measurement values for the evaluation of systems are now supplemented by a consideration of media use of relevance in the educational context. Together the factors information quality, system quality, service quality and media richness are seen as technology- and system-related factors.

Information Quality

One of the three quality dimensions from the D&M IS success model is information quality. The aim of this variable is to record and investigate the impact of the quality of the information presented in the learning system from the students' point of view. The quality of the information is mainly about how relevant the learning content is, how easily understandably it is presented, how well the quality of the content is assessed or how up-to-date and accurate the information presented in the learning content is. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, Chapter Appendix Measurement Items) The D&M system quality dimensions have already proven their worth in numerous studies and have therefore been frequently applied in the evaluation of e-learning systems. Depending on the focus of the research, the influence of information quality on student satisfaction with the system, the perceived usefulness of the system or the intention to continue using the system was evaluated. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 494)

While Lee and Hwang found no significant effect of the quality of information in the learning content on students' satisfaction with the learning system as a whole, there have been many other studies that have found a significant effect (J.-K. Lee & Hwang, 2007, p. 77). One example is the evaluation by Cidral et al. who found significance for the influence of information quality in their research and concluded that the quality of information within a learning system is one of

the main drivers for students to use the system (Cidral et al., 2018, p. 283). In addition, some studies also investigated the influence of information quality on student satisfaction with the learning system. Mohammadi and Lin and Wang found significant influence (W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, p. 96; Mohammadi, 2015, pp. 369–372). Samar Ghazal et al. also investigated the influence of information quality in their study on Critical Factors for LMS Acceptance and Satisfaction in Blended Learning Systems. From the students' point of view, the quality of the information in terms of nicely prepared, correct and up-to-date learning content has a positive impact on the satisfaction and perceived usefulness of the LMS in a blended learning system. In contrast, no significant influence on the perception of ease of use was found. (Ghazal, Aldowah, et al., 2018, p. 697)

As these results from previous studies show, the quality of information can be a decisive factor for the success of a blended learning system, but they also show that the individual focus, the context of the study and the target group can lead to quite different results. Zhang and Dang also take the variable information quality within the group of system- and technology-related factors into account in their study. In the evaluation by Zhang and Dang, the influence of information quality on learning climate, task-technology fit and blended learning flexibility was investigated. It was found that the quality of the information presented in the system does not affect the learning climate, but it does have a significant impact on student perceptions of task-technology fit and blended learning flexibility. Interestingly, the coefficient associated with the path from information quality to blended learning was negative. For the authors this result was unexpected and they call for further validation and research. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501)

System Quality

The variable system quality originates from the D&M IS success Model and, like the other two quality factors from this model, has already proven to be an important success criterion in numerous general system success evaluations as well as in specific e-learning system evaluations. (Urbach & Müller, 2012, p. 12).

The system quality factor is used, for example, to examine how students assess the flexibility of the use of learning technology, how students perceive the multimedia nature of the learning content, or how reliable or useful they consider the use of the technological system for their educational purposes. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, Chapter Appendix Measurement Items) When evaluating these aspects in numerous application contexts, the researchers came to different conclusions. Seman et al. evaluated the impact of system quality within an evaluation of students' satisfaction in blended-learning environments. The results of this investigation showed an insignificant impact of the system quality upon the overall satisfaction of students. (Seman et al., 2019, p. 136) In contrast, the results of Mohammadi's 2015 research showed that system

quality, among the factors evaluated, has the greatest impact on student satisfaction. From these findings, the author concluded that a continuously developed user-friendly interface, which provides students with a good overview of their learning process, as well as easy access to the learning content, for example through a print option, are essential starting points for improving the quality of the system. (Mohammadi, 2015, p. 370). The team of authors around Samar Ghazal also agrees with these practical recommendations. In their study, they also found a significant influence of the system quality on all three dependent variables investigated: the general satisfaction of the students, the perceived usefulness as well as the perceived ease of use. (Ghazal, Aldowah, et al., 2018, p. 697)

Further in the evaluation by Zhang and Dang, the impact of system quality on learning climate, task-technology fit and blended learning flexibility was investigated. The results of the student surveys showed that of the three dependent variables for which a correlation was tested, only the influence on blended learning flexibility was significant. The system quality therefore did not have a significant effect on the task-technology fit or the learning climate in the study. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501) How this impact is evidenced from the perspective of students from marginalized regions around the world is evaluated in this thesis.

Service Quality

Service quality was only added to the system quality criteria in DeLone and McLean's updated model (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003). Since 2003, however, these three quality dimensions have proven themselves in numerous studies (Urbach & Müller, 2012, p. 12). The investigation of service quality focuses primarily on the support system for learning technology. It is investigated whether and to what extent the students perceive the support as easily accessible, fast, reliable and satisfactory. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, Chapter Appendix Measurement Items)

Especially with this factor, the results are very strongly dependent on the design of the service, but also on the definition of the service. For example, there are studies that not only understand pure support as a form of learning place in the sense of a helpdesk, but also include the interaction and support of the facilitator, such as in the study by Lee and Hwang. They recognized a significant influence of service quality on student satisfaction with the system. (J.-K. Lee & Hwang, 2007, pp. 76–77) Cidral et al. also identified service quality as one of the key drivers of e-learning system use (Cidral et al., 2018, p. 283). The authors Lin and Lwoga concluded from their findings on the significant influence of service quality that e-learning system designers need to plan service functionalities and processes well (H.-F. Lin, 2007, p. 819; Lwoga, 2014, p. 17). Mohammadi was also able to observe the significance of the influence of the factor service quality in his research study. Given the great importance of service quality, he recommends providing tutorials and instructions on the learning platform. (Mohammadi, 2015, pp. 369–372)

The findings from the study by Samar Ghazal et al. are exciting: these authors were able to determine a significant influence of service quality on the perceived ease of use but were unable to identify a significant influence of service quality on the usefulness perceived by students and their satisfaction with the system. The authors explained these results by the fact that the investigated group of students already has moderate expertise in the use of technology. (Ghazal, Aldowah, et al., 2018, p. 697)

It is these group-specific differences that need to be further explored. Zhang and Dang examined the impact of service quality within a student group in the U.S., and using the same research instrument, in this thesis the study was conducted within a group of JWL students from various marginalized regions around the world.

When examining the third of the D&M IS success dimensions, service quality, a significant influence was found on all three dependent variables examined. From the students' point of view, the service quality has an impact on the learning climate, the technology fit and the blended learning flexibility. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501)

Whether a similar result is also found in the survey of other student groups remains open and is therefore examined in the context of this work with regard to the case study with JWL.

Media Richness

Media richness theory is one of the best known theories of communication media choice. Media Richness Theory sees different levels of richness in the communication media. The richness of a communication medium indicates how much additional information a communication medium offers. This results in a classification of media into rich and less rich communication media. From a media pedagogical point of view, the choice of media should depend on the learning scenario, i.e., the task which students have to fulfill by using this communication media or the complexity of the learning content presented. A video conference, for example, has a high media richness because questions can be asked at any time, non-verbal and para-verbal communication is possible and what is discussed can be repeated and discussed by the participants in a variety of languages. This makes the rich communication medium suitable for very complex tasks, such as discussing a work assignment for a project work in the group. The presentation of learning content in the form of a PDF reading document sent by email, on the other hand, is to be classified as very low from the point of view of media richness. (Haim, 2012, pp. 8–10)

If we now examine the media richness of a blended-learning system in general, the aim is to find out whether the most diverse and appropriate media are used to convey the learning content. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 494)

Various authors have already investigated whether they can see media richness as a significant factor influencing the success of an e-learning system in their context.

Liu et al. investigated the impact of different rich media presentation formats in an e-learning offer. The research model used was designed according to flow theory and the TAM model. The results of their research showed a significant influence of media richness on students' intention to continue using the e-learning system. They also found that the presentations with the higher media richness level, in this case text, audio and video presentations, lead to an increased perceived usefulness and a higher concentration. (Liu et al., 2005, p. 180) Furthermore, Wu and Hwang identified within their research significant impact of media richness on students' perceived usability of the e-learning system for blended learning courses (W. Wu & Hwang, 2010, p. 317).

Based on these earlier findings on the influence of media richness, the authors Zhang and Dang also included this variable in their research model. As already mentioned several times, they investigated the influence of technology- and system-related variables on the learning climate, the fit between tasks and technology as well as the blended learning flexibility. In the survey of the students, a significant influence of the media richness on the learning climate and the task-technology fit was found. However, an influence on the blended learning flexibility could not be determined. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501)

In order to find out how to adapt the media for conveying the learning content and processing tasks in future blended-learning programs, one should examine how the target group rates the media richness and which formats are particularly favored and could be further developed. And therefore this factor should also be evaluated from the perspective of students in marginalized regions. This is the only way to determine whether and to what extent media richness must be taken into account as a decisive influencing factor in the expansion of higher education programs for refugees.

3.5.3 Instructional Design Factor

Technological approaches to designing a blended-learning environment should be guided by instructional design principles (Handke, 2020, p. 12). Therefore this perspective of instructional design factors should not be missing in a comprehensive blended-learning success model.

The extent to which instructional design influences the success of blended-learning systems from the students' point of view should be investigated, because if these are critical success factors, this also offers starting points for adapting blended-learning systems accordingly in practice. Different sources underline the existence of this influence, but there are different findings on the extent of this influence. Ojstersek mentioned that the learning process can be influenced indirectly through the design of the teaching method and learning environment. (Ojstersek, 2009, p. 16) The extent to which this affects student satisfaction could be further investigated. Similarly, Lin and Wang formulate that blended learning requires successfully designed learning environments and methods guided by instructional methods (W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, p. 89).

Further research into whether this is reflected in critical success factors from the students' point of view is exciting in order to find potential starting points for improving blended-learning systems.

Some authors have already taken steps in this direction and, for example, included course characteristics in their research models. For example, Seman et al. investigated the factors of course quality and instructor quality in a survey on acceptance and satisfaction with blended-learning systems. The results showed a significant influence of both factors on the students' satisfaction with the system. (Seman et al., 2019, p. 137)

Previously, Kamla Ali Al-Busaidi had also noted the lack of research investment and included course characteristics, classmates' characteristics, and organizational characteristics in the evaluation of critical success factors of an LMS in blended learning. In this study, she found significant influence upon the perceived usefulness of the LMS in the group of course characteristics for course quality and course flexibility. Classmates' characteristics, classmates' attitude and classmates' interactions showed more significant results. And in the group of organization characteristics, the training courses had a significant influence on their perceived satisfaction with the blended-learning LMS from the students' point of view. Based on these results, the author recommended to further investigate these influences and especially to evaluate them in a cross-cultural and global context. (Al-Busaidi, 2012, pp. 28–29)

This work could contribute to this, and will be based on the research model of Zhang and Dang. They also recognized in the current state of the research literature that course quality and flexibility emerged as having significant impact on students' satisfaction with e-learning systems in various studies. In addition, from a course design perspective, they also perceived the significant results on the contextual teaching methods of individual authors. Since these contextual teaching method characteristics could also have a significant influence, the authors wanted to consider all these factors from an instructional design perspective. In a variable of the teaching method, the authors brought together these context-related teaching method aspects as well as the course characteristics. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 495)

Zhang and Dang define this factor in their research model as follows:

“In this study, the teaching method is defined as the variety of specific learning activities and tasks adopted in blended learning for students to perform and complete” (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 495).

Within the research of Zhang and Dang this instructional design factor showed significant impact on all three dependent variables: learning climate, task-technology fit and blended-learning flexibility (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501). And therefore, this factor will be also included in this thesis evaluation of the JWL case study. This also contributes to Al-Busaidi's call for further investigation in cross-cultural and global context.

According to Zhang and Dang's definition, the factor teaching method is very context-dependent, and the items of the research instrument are individually adapted to each context. Therefore, it is hardly possible to validate the items in several different ways, as is the case with most other items of this research model. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 495, 498) Therefore, for the evaluation of the teaching method, the items are adapted to fit the context of the JWL case study, but the alignment of the items remains as presented in this research instrument to achieve similar results.

In addition to the aspects of the instructional design perspective summarized in the factor teaching method, the facilitator characteristics have also repeatedly been found to have a significant influence as a decisive factor from this perspective in the comparative literature analysis. (Cheng, 2012, p. 365; Klobas & McGill, 2010, p. 118; Seman et al., 2019, p. 137) The factor facilitator characteristics is not included in the model of Zhang and Dang, but since the arguments for the fit of this model outweighed this negative argument, the research model of Zhang and Dang was used as a reference for this paper. The facilitator characteristics are therefore evaluated in a separate qualitative analysis and are not included in the teaching methods influence factor within this comprehensive e-learning success model which is introduced in this section.

3.5.4 Concepts with relevance in the blended learning context

After the explanation of the external variables used by Zhang and Dang based on the results of the comparative literature analysis, the concepts with relevance in the blended learning context that the authors found to be influenced by the external variables are now presented.

However, the exact paths along which these influences act are not relevant in the context of this research and therefore the hypotheses found by the authors will not be explained further and will not be tested in the empirical part of this paper. Instead, the influencing factors identified as dependent variables in the research model will now be presented individually.

Learning Climate

Building on the preceding theoretical underpinning the authors Wu et. al. considered that the social cognitive theory is applicable to the blended-learning context. According to this theory three factors are relevant for students' learning satisfaction in blended learning environments: learners' cognitive beliefs, the technological environment, and the social environment. Within the factor social environment, students' interactions and the learning climate are identified as dimensions of students' learning satisfaction. The atmosphere in the blended-learning context is described as learning climate. (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 157)

Several researchers pointed out the importance of providing a pleasant learning climate not only in traditional learning environments, but also in technologically-supported learning settings, as

this affects students' satisfaction and is an indicator for learning effectiveness. (Y.-C. Chen, 2014, p. 161; J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 158) Wu et al. found significant impact of learning climate on students' satisfaction and concluded that therefore students and facilitators should try their best to foster and motivate a pleasant learning climate. That could also interrelate to students' performance expectations which was identified as providing the most contribution to students' satisfaction. (J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 163) Chen also found significant results when investigating the influence of the learning climate on learning gratification and proactive stickiness with web-based English learning context where this research took place (Y.-C. Chen, 2014, pp. 168–169). Based on this research, the authors Zhang and Dang included this factor influencing students' satisfaction with the blended learning system in their study. In that way, they investigated the extent to which the students perceive the learning system as helpful for their studies, how much they enjoy the blended-learning program, and how much the learning environment motivates them to learn spontaneously. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 492, Appendix Measurement Items) In their study on the success factors of a blended-learning system, Zhang and Dang investigated whether, from the students' point of view, the learning climate has an impact on their satisfaction with the system and their intention to use it for further courses. For the learning climate, the results showed significant effects on satisfaction as well as on the intention to continue studying courses within this blended-learning system. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501)

These aspects of the learning environment relate to individually designed LMSs, the concept of blended-learning programs and the resulting tasks that students complete in face-to-face interactions or online, depending on the research context. Because the learning climate, which has already been identified as a significant influencing factor across different application contexts, can be different in each context due to the different design of the blended-learning programs, it is particularly exciting to investigate whether the learning climate is also a significant influencing factor from the students' perspective at JWL.

Task- Technology fit

The concept of the task-technology fit, introduced by Goodhue & Thompson (1995), showed impact on the use of information systems and users performance within these systems. Therefore McGill and Kolbas evaluated whether this impact of the task-technology fit also affects the success and use of an LMS. Their results showed that task-technology fit plays a crucial role in the utilization and success of an LMS. (McGill & Klobas, 2009, pp. 496, 503)

In addition, the authors Lin and Wang later also found a significant influence of the task-technology fit on the utilization of an LMS in their research (W.-S. Lin & Wang, 2012, p. 96).

The authors of the Blended Learning Success Model, based on the findings from the existing literature, decided to examine the task-technology fit construct as a dependent variable in their

research as well. They would like to investigate whether the functionalities of the LMS offer exactly what students need to submit their activities and assignments. But also whether the learning content offered in the blended learning program and the tasks on the learning platform meet the students' learning goals. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 492, Appendix Measurement Items)

The results from this study showed the significant influence of the task-technology fit concept on the students' satisfaction and their willingness to take further courses in this blended-learning system (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501).

This fit of tasks, learning content and technologies used within the blended-learning environment is also very much dependent on the context of the study. It therefore remains exciting to evaluate how this influence plays out from the perspective of students in marginalized regions around the world.

Blended Learning Flexibility

Authors who deal with digital learning environments often emphasize the flexibility gained in education through digitalization. Software applications offer more flexibility, which especially for higher-education programs is an huge advantage (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020, p. 68). Thus, blended-learning programs offer more flexibility in terms of timing and location (Littlejohn & Pegler, 2007, p. 2). Because a decisive part of the learning experience for which presence is not necessarily required is outsourced to an online learning world, students gain flexibility. This makes it easier to combine study programs with students' own schedules and learning needs. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 493)

Various authors have investigated how students perceive this flexibility. For this purpose, course or learning flexibility was included in various evaluation models on success criteria of a digital learning system. In 2008, Sun et al. investigated the impact of e-learning course flexibility on student satisfaction. They found that this flexibility and the associated opportunities for self-paced learning had a significant impact on satisfaction with digital learning systems. (Sun et al., 2008, pp. 1192, 1196)

Similar results were obtained in the study by Kamala Ali-Al-Busaidi, who found a significant influence of course flexibility on blended-learning system success. In order to test how this relationship is pronounced from the perspective of other student groups, the author calls for further research in a cross-cultural and global context. (Al-Busaidi, 2012, pp. 28–29)

Based on the findings that flexibility has already proven itself as an important concept in blended-learning systems evaluations, the authors Zhang and Dang included this concept in their research model. The study of blended-learning flexibility focuses on the specific characteristics of the blended-learning program and thus asks the students to what extent this aspect contributes to more flexibility. Since instructional designers adapt blended-learning concepts individually to

the target group and the program, the design of the items differs depending on the blended-learning concept. For example, the impact of outsourcing certain learning phases to the flexible online learning environment will be investigated, or how the possibilities for learning at one's own pace or for organizing the learning effort as efficiently as possible are assessed from the students' point of view. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 493, 498, Appendix measurement items)

The results of Zhang and Dang's evaluation showed significant impact of the blended-learning flexibility on the satisfaction as well as on the intention to continue taking courses delivered through this blended-learning system (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 501).

Whether and how this influence on satisfaction and intention to continue taking courses within the system plays out in the context of the JWL Professional Certificate course is investigated in this thesis.

3.5.5 Satisfaction and Intention

In the study of system success, as was evident in the comparative literature analysis, the two major factors, **satisfaction** and **intention** have proven their significant impact in numerous research models from different perspectives and within the general system and the e-learning and blended-learning-specific context. Within two main research perspectives, the research models on technology acceptance according to Venkatesh et al (2003) and in the research models from the information system success perspective according to DeLone and McLean (2003), these variables can be found repeatedly. In the e-learning and blended-learning context, the satisfaction and intention of the students with the system were also investigated several times (e.g. Hassanzadeh et al., 2012; H.-F. Lin, 2007; Mohammadi, 2015)

Therefore, Zhang and Dang also use these two variables in their blended-learning success model. For the use in their model, however, they have specified them more precisely in a separate definition to fit into the blended-learning context. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 495)

“Specifically, satisfaction is defined as students' level of satisfaction on blended learning, and intention is defined as their willingness to take more blended classes in the future when available” (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 495).

As this thesis is based on the blended learning success model developed and validated by Zhang and Dang, this definition will also be used.

To investigate the students' satisfaction with the system, different aspects were assessed, such as how much the students enjoyed learning with this system, how pleasant the system was for them, how much it fulfilled their educational needs or whether it gave the students self-confidence to study with this learning system. According to the above definition, the intention refers to the students' willingness to take further courses in this blended-learning system. The main

question is how strong this willingness is. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 498, Appendix measurement items)

The aim of this work is to find out which factors affect the success of blended-learning higher education programs from the point of view of students in marginalized regions worldwide who study in JWL professional certificate programs. With the knowledge of which factors are relevant, one can find approaches regarding how higher education programs should be designed in order to make university education more accessible for refugees, for example. It is important to keep this big goal in mind when considering what this success of the blended-learning system looks like for which this thesis tries to find success criteria. If one then moves into the context of the case study investigated in this work, the criteria of satisfaction and willingness to take further courses in this system fit very well to determine whether the system is successful. Since these two variables, which have been identified several times in the literature as crucial measurement points, are also particularly relevant in the context of this study, they will be examined further in this paper.

It is evident that the Zhang and Dang model can be used to assess the success factors of blended-learning systems. It is pertinent to mention that Zhang and Dang's study to assess success factors was based on a group of students in a developed country, and therefore it is quite interesting to evaluate which success factors show their impact from the perspective of students in developing countries and even more precisely in marginalized regions. The major objective of this study is therefore to evaluate the success factors of blended-learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions around the globe. How this study is conducted will be explained in the following chapter.

4 Research Approach

The goal of this thesis is to identify success criteria of blended-learning systems, by capturing perspectives of marginalized students situated globally. These students are participants of higher education programs of JWL's blended learning system. To identify the success criteria of such an e-learning system, the existing literature was critically analyzed in chapter 3. Finally a model was chosen as a basis for this work, which is as up-to-date as possible and contains as many of the important influencing factors recognized from the analysis as possible. At the end of the process, the Blended Learning Success Model by Zhang and Dang, which was published in 2020, met these requirements.

The aim of this thesis is to find criteria that make blended-learning systems successful, especially from the perspective of students situated globally in marginalized areas who participate in higher education via JWL's blended-learning system. Therefore, this research will be evaluated through the method of case study and the survey conducted within the context of this case study

is the focus of the research work. Accordingly, the central research method is quantitative research using an online questionnaire.

The approach to evaluate success criteria from JWL students all around the globe required a quantitative research tool which provides the opportunity to include students within different time zones and unstable internet connectivity. At the same time the tool should have as few technical barriers as possible. An online survey allows us to conduct the study across a large geographical distribution. As the literature analysis process showed the model from Zhang and Dang as the most appropriate research framework, this model was chosen to develop an instrument for the evaluation of the presented case study. The questionnaire presented by Zhang and Dang was taken up as fundament for this. Details on how the survey was conducted will be explained in section 4.1.

4.1 Quantitative Research approach

To evaluate the blended learning success criteria within the case-study context, an instrument was needed to evaluate students' experiences all around the globe. Therefore, a standardized online questionnaire was conducted. The standardized online questionnaire is set up through Lime-Survey; this software allows automatic responsive design of the survey on multiple devices like smartphones, tablets or desktops, through the browser web-view. This feature enriches the usability and decreases the technical barriers for users, especially for users in marginalized areas, who might have limited accessibility to hardware devices. In total there were 67 questions split into 15 topics; it takes around 20-30 minutes to complete the survey. Collecting the responses to all these questions through an online survey is much more cost and time effective in a global context than any other method of data collection. That is why the quantitative method of an online survey was conducted.

A cross-sectional study approach was chosen, as a longitudinal study at several points in time would go beyond the scope of this paper. Compared to interviews conducted through online video conference software, the online survey needs lower internet bandwidth. It is especially important for a target group with unstable internet connectivity, or high costs for mobile data bundles, that the evaluation is not too heavy in data consumption, which would decrease the response numbers. The intermediate saving of questionnaires that have not been completed allows students to complete the questionnaire without having to do it all at once. The survey software does not save the IP-addresses, which gives additional data security and anonymity to students. Anonymity is highly important for students of this target group, for example the data of girls studying in Afghanistan need to be highly protected by the systems. Any references to students, especially about women who are studying, should be avoided because violent attacks on educational institutions can take place in such regions with violent regimes or high-risk

terrorist groups. The settings of the survey further allowed several students to submit feedback from the same device, as in many JWL learning centers students share devices.

At the beginning of the survey a short text explains the purpose of the evaluation, the estimated time effort, overview of data handling, data security and anonymity. The survey also encourages participation of the students. Later, information on the demographics and courses the student has taken within the JWL blended-learning program is collected. This information is measured in accordance to the Zhang and Dang instrument. Based on the literature analysis further sources were found which formulated some of these questionnaire items already in earlier publications. As in every evaluation the items have been slightly adapted according to the research context. For example, terminology and language familiar to the students was used. Items on teaching methods were given special importance and questions were formulated to ask about the characteristics of JWL's teaching methods. These items are always highly contextualized and therefore difficult to compare with other earlier evaluations in different context. Nearly all 67 questions are closed questions. Similar to Zhang and Dang's evaluation a Likert scale was used, but the authors of that model used a 7 point scale in their work (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 498), while in this paper a 5 point Likert-scale has been used. Zhang and Dang evaluated the success of a computer information system class at a public university in the United States. The experience of working with JWL students had shown that some of the students are not used to critical evaluations and providing critical feedback. This diversity in the feedback culture of a global group of students could be a reason why; it might be difficult for some students to express criticism. Based on this observation, an option to capture a 'neutral opinion' was provided. This is very important as students get an option of at least not giving praise if they do not want to criticize. The adjustment to a 5-point scale was made to avoid too complex a differentiation of the values. Since a descriptive data analysis is planned, the 5-point scale is sufficient for the scope of this work. Levels of the bipolar scale for all items is: strongly disagree, disagree, not sure, neither agree nor disagree, agree and strongly agree. Further each question has the opportunity to select **prefer not to say**, this addition helps to offer a possibility to students who prefer not to rate an item.

4.2 Questionnaire Development Process

DeLone and McLean, who with their IS success model developed the quality dimensions of system quality, service quality and information quality which are cornerstones of this research model, mentioned in the conclusion of the publication of their updated model in 2003 that they encourage researchers to test and challenge their model in several contexts but recommend where possible the application of the already validated measures instead of developing new ones (William DeLone & McLean, 2003, p. 27). Following exactly this approach the blended-

learning success model and questionnaire which was used for the evaluation of Zhang & Dang's model was used as the basis of this research. The questionnaire items were adapted according to the research context. Zhang and Dang used the term system within the items, but for this evaluation the wording was adapted to more concrete terms. This precise wording makes it easier for JWL students to really answer the questions in view of the JWL system, as the students may know different learning systems of different NGOs. As the research takes place in many centers around the world and there is therefore not always someone on site who can answer questions, this clear formulation should avoid getting answers referring to a different system. The terms learning platform was therefore used instead of system. As JWL students use computers and tablets, the items on computer self-efficacy were adapted accordingly to also include tablets and not only the use of computers. Within the items on the quality dimensions, system and information quality are kept like in Zhang & Dang's publication. For the items on the service quality, the wording which had specified system and technology support was changed to helpdesk for JWL's Learning platform. Within JWL the Helpdesk is a mail address that is easily accessible for students automatically generating tickets for the support team on all kind of student issues. Therefore, this helpdesk includes all aspects of system and technology support. As not all students contributing to the evaluation will have already contacted the helpdesk, a filter question was added before these items. Only students who have already contacted the helpdesk at least once will get access to evaluate these items. This helps to avoid incorrect answers, as students who have never used the Helpdesk are not driven to evaluate the service quality without having any experience with it. The items to evaluate the teaching method are highly contextualized within each case study. Therefore, Zhang and Dang's items were already individually developed. So the researchers weren't able to reuse existing items as they had done with the other variables. For the same reason, no previously tested items could be reused in this research, but specific items were developed to assess the different aspects of the teaching method in the JWL context. For the items of the variable task-technology fit, Zhang and Dang use validated items from previous studies, whereby it is noticeable in these that technical terminologies such as learning needs was used. JWL students participating in this evaluation are still at the beginning of their academic training and may therefore have difficulties in understanding everything correctly. In order to adapt the language to the target groups, the items were made more concrete with corresponding examples and are thus easier to understand. For the same reason the blended-learning items were adapted. The term blended learning as a term for the combined model of face-to-face learning and online learning was defined at the beginning of the questionnaire but is not a familiar term to all JWL Students. More familiar and far more widely used is the classic on-site teaching with 5 days of presence. In order to clarify the difference in the teaching concept at stake in these items, the formulation of the items was adapted to clarify the difference between JWL's blended-learning approach and traditional onsite

learning. It is important to avoid students' misunderstandings on blended-learning to obtain usable data from the evaluation of the variable blended-learning flexibility. As in the original instrument according to Zhang and Dang, between three and seven items were evaluated for each variable. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, pp. 498, 508–509 Appendix, Measurement Items) Before starting the real survey, a pre-test was conducted with two students from Afghanistan, two students from Malawi and two students from Northern Iraq. This test within different locations was helpful to see if the survey is understandable for students. Afterwards, some slight adaptations in the formulation of the items took place. Mainly some verbs were adapted to show clear differences between two items of one variable, as sometimes the verbs were too similar, especially for students who aren't native speakers and couldn't identify the slight differences. After these adaptations, during a videocall the final survey was checked with one of the students participating in the pretest.

4.3 Study Implementation

To evaluate the success criteria of blended-learning systems, from a global perspective of students in marginalized areas participating in higher education via JWL's blended-learning system, an online survey was sent out to students of JWL's professional certificate programs. These courses had been chosen as they show a consistent framework of blended learning, with online individual self-study time, two in-class meetings per week and several online learning activities and assignments. Each course has a total length of 8 weeks, and students always enroll for half a year to take three of these courses in a row. All JWL professional certificate programs are following this framework and are therefore included in the evaluation. So the survey was sent to students who participated in a minimum of one of these certificate programs: Youth Sport Facilitator, Peace Leader, Learning Facilitator, Creative Writing and Design and Community-based Ecotourism. The first intake cohort started in September 2018, the newest intake was in September 2020. All intakes had been included to reach a bigger number of students. Due to JWL's special data protection regulations it was not possible to contact each student individually. But since the Jesuits' network of local learning centers is well established all over the world and is a key element of the blended-learning approach, therefore this survey was also sent out to all center coordinators, who distributed the survey link to all students who participated in one of these courses. Further notifications were sent out within the learning platform to reach all students who were still active on the learning platform. By weekly messages within the network of onsite facilitators and coordinators, JWL's online staff was informed to encourage student participation. That contributed as one of the reasons for a higher participation rate. The questionnaire was open for participation between 04.10.2020 and 01.11.2020, during this time 81 complete answers, 72 incomplete, and one invalid questionnaire were submitted. So in total there are 80 surveys which can be used for the evaluation.

As shown in Table 2: Demographics of participants 273 students were active during October when the questionnaire was open.

Country	Active students in October 2020	Completed stu- dents in October 2020	Total active & completed JWL Professional Certifi- cate Students
Afghanistan	82	42	124
Guyana	8		8
India	25		25
Iraq	35	7	42
Kenya		61	61
Malawi	30	50	80
Myanmar	26	8	34
Philippines	10		10
Sri Lanka	36	9	45
Thailand	21		21
Total	273	177	450

Table 1: Active JWL Students in Professional Certificate Programs - Population for online survey

The survey results will be analyzed through a descriptive approach.

Details of the evaluation results can be found in Chapter 5. In Chapter 6 the research aims of finding success criteria of blended-learning systems, from a global perspective of students in marginalized areas will be discussed and summarized. Final conclusion can be found in chapter 7.

4.4 Qualitative Analysis of mentioned success criteria

This paper aims to explore the success factors of a blended learning system from the perspective of students in marginalized regions around the world. The research model selected for this purpose, as well as the majority of research models included in the literature analysis which led to this selection, were based on evaluations in developed countries. Since the research is conducted using the already existing research instrument of Zhang and Dang, it could be that factors are not considered which are crucial from the perspective of students in marginalized regions, but which are not evaluated via the instrument that was designed in developed countries. Thus, in a qualitative approach, the statements from the students to a free feedback question are examined to see which influencing factors they mention without being pushed.

But there is also a second reason why the qualitative investigation is necessary. The research model according to Zhang and Dang which was found in the process of the comparative literature analysis does not examine the influence of facilitator characteristics. However, many other authors point to the significant influence of this category on the success factors of blended learning systems in their studies. The selection of the research model, as described in section 3.4, is about finding a compromise solution that best fits the research question and the context of the study. The study of the success factors of a blended learning system from the perspective of students in marginalized regions is conducted in the context of the JWL Professional Certificate programs. As there are two categories of facilitators in these programs, an online and an onsite facilitator, the results of conventional analyses of facilitator characteristics would hardly be comparable with the results in the context of JWL anyway. Therefore, in this work, the influence of facilitator characteristics, which is perceived as significant by numerous authors (for example: Cheng, 2012, p. 365; Klobas & McGill, 2010, p. 118; Seman et al., 2019, p. 137), is examined separately. It is assumed that the facilitator characteristics because they so often showed significant influence, could also have an influence from the students' point of view. Therefore, if the students mention this category as a key factor for improvement, it can be assumed that facilitator characteristics are relevant for the success of the blended-learning system from the perspective of the target group.

For these two reasons, an open question was asked at the end of the questionnaire to find out what improvement potential the students see. The sub-question was: Do you have any further ideas how JWL Courses and Learning Platform can be improved?

As described in section 1.4 within this thesis the success of a blended-learning system is characterized by the satisfaction of the users with the system and the willingness to use the system for further courses. The question about the potential for improvement aims to find out what students would improve in order to be more satisfied and take more courses in this system. Therefore, the answers of students will be categorized according to the impact factors they have mentioned. The open question format avoids directing the students to a specific category of success factors and thus provoking certain responses. In addition to the success factor categories from the Zhang and Dang model, the factor facilitator characteristics and the frequently-mentioned impact factor of hardware and internet connection is addressed. All student statements to which this categorization refers can be found in Appendix.

All answers are examined and categorized according to the success factors that were addressed. The factors according to Zhang and Dang, which have already been validated by the research model (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020), are assumed to be crucial success factors from the perspective of students in marginalized regions if they have been raised as suggestions for improvement of the JWL blended learning system. These results can then support the results of the questionnaire evaluation.

Since the facilitator characteristics factor is to be examined more closely in the context of the case study, all statements that mention facilitator characteristics will be examined further. First, a distinction is made as to whether the statement refers to the online facilitator or the onsite facilitator. Then the aspects of the facilitator characteristics that are addressed are examined. The results are first presented, and then thematically appropriate aspects are formulated, which could then serve as items of the category facilitator characteristics in later evaluations.

5 Data analysis and results

The ultimate aim of this thesis is to find out the factors that have an impact on the success of blended-learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions worldwide. This means that it is necessary to find out what influences the satisfaction and the intention to take further courses in this system from the students' point of view. For this purpose, students who have already completed the JWL Professional Certificate programs or were currently doing so at the time of the research in October 2020 were surveyed. In total there were 450 students, but at the time of the evaluation only 273 students from the countries Afghanistan, Guyana, India, Iraq, Kenya, Malawi, Myanmar, Philippines, Sri Lanka and Thailand were active on the learning platform where the questionnaire was made available. A total of 80 students from JWL Professional Certificate programs validly completed the online questionnaire. As visualized in Table 2: Demographics of participants exactly half of the questionnaires were completed by women, so the results can be considered as gender balanced.

In addition, it can be seen from the table that half of the students surveyed are under 25 years old. JWL offers higher education programs such as the Professional Certificate Programs in marginalized regions, more specifically for communities at the margins of societies. As the table shows, almost half of the respondents are refugees. But the group of those who participate in the programs in the refugee camps from the local host communities, with 15 participants, is equally represented as those students who come from Jesuit schools or Loyola Campuses run by Jesuits or partner organizations. Almost 70% of the students who participated in the survey already knew JWL and its learning system because they had already participated in courses before.

DEMOGRAPHICS OF PARTICIPANTS		
	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	40	50,0
Female	40	50,0
Age		
18-21	16	20,0
22-24	25	31,3
25-29	19	23,8
30-34	11	13,8
35-39	7	8,8
40 and older	2	2,5
Status		
Refugee	39	48,8
Host Community	15	18,8
Student of Jesuit School / Loyola Campus	15	18,8
Other	4	5,0
Prefer not to say	7	8,8
Pre-Experience with JWL		
1st Enrollment	55	68,8
had already been enrolled	24	30,0
Other	1	1,3

Table 2: Demographics of participants

In order to better understand the structure of the group of students surveyed, it is also helpful to take a closer look at which of the professional certificate programs they have enrolled in. Figure 16 shows the questionnaire participants listed by country and program in a diagram with stacked bars. Each color in the bars represents participants from a particular Professional Certificate Program.

Figure 16: Survey Participants by program and country

Some program runs did not have any completed questionnaire from the students, therefore not all of the countries and program runs presented in section 4.3 are included in the graph.

For example, no students from the Community-based Ecotourism program, which was the first program at the Learning Center in Thailand, participated. Therefore, no results from students from Thailand are included. In addition, it can be seen that students from all four runs of the most popular program - Learning Facilitator - completed the questionnaire. These are marked in green in the diagram. From the Peace Leader program runs marked in blue, it can be seen that no students from the first and second run participated. Three students did not indicate which program they are or were enrolled in, these are marked in grey in the diagram. The height of the bars indicates how many students from a country have completely filled out the questionnaire. So it can be seen that 16 students from Afghanistan, 2 students from Guyana, 6 students from

India, 19 students from Iraq, 8 students from Kenya, 16 students from Malawi, 6 students from Myanmar and 7 students from Sri Lanka filled in the online survey for this evaluation. Furthermore, with regard to the study of a digital system, it is interesting to know how technology use is within the surveyed group. Therefore Table 3 shows the results of the various evaluated aspects of technology usage behavior.

Technology usage behaviour	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Spent time on using computers per day (TU1)</i>		
Less than one hour	5	6,3
Between 1-3 hour	30	37,5
Between 3-5 hour	19	23,8
Between 6-8 hour	14	17,5
9 hours or more	5	6,3
Other	4	5,0
Prefer not to say	3	3,8
<i>Spent time on using computers on educational purpose (per day) (TU2)</i>		
Less than one hour	6	7,5
Between 1-3 hour	28	35
Between 3-5 hour	34	42,5
Between 6-8 hour	8	10
9 hours or more	4	5
<i>Spent time on using technology for studying in offline settings per day(TU4)</i>		
Less than one hour	11	13,8
Between 1-3 hour	34	42,5
Between 3-5 hour	23	28,8
Between 6-8 hour	7	8,8
9 hours or more	2	2,5
Other	2	2,5
Prefer not to say	1	1,3
<i>Use of Learning App (TU5)</i>		
Android	30	37,5
Windows	16	20,0
both	15	18,8
doesn't use any App	19	23,8
<i>Devices used for studying (TU6)</i>		
own computer	34	42,5
computers at the learning center	5	6,3
own tablet	4	5,0
tablets at the learning center	10	12,5
own smartphone	30	37,5
device from the learning center for which it is allowed to take home	13	16,3
own device at home and JWL device at the learning center	8	10,0
<i>Access to stabile internet connectivity (TU7)</i>		
Everyday	59	73,8
Twice a week	12	15,0
Once a week	3	3,8
Other	4	5,0
Prefer not to say	2	2,5

Table 3: Technology usage behaviour within the surveyed group

The table shows that 37.5% of the surveyed students report using the computer for about 1-3 hours a day, whereas 42.5% of the students said that they use the computer for educational purposes 3-5 hours a day. This inconsistency in the students' data shown in table 2 indicates there were misunderstandings about these two questions, which is why these data should not be considered as reliable reference points. The next aspect, offline study time, could also be affected and should therefore be interpreted with caution. In offline learning settings, as shown in the table, 42.5% of participants mentioned that they engage with the learning content for 1-3 hours. Further it is shown that more than half of the students use one of the JWL learning apps, which allow offline study of the course content. The results on the devices used by the students are also interesting. As the table shows, the majority use their own devices. Since multiple answers were possible for this question, because some students use different devices, the population to which the percentages refer is also higher here. The percentage of students who report having access to an internet connection every day is 73.8% among the student group surveyed.

Since this study took place in the year 2020, which was affected by the global Corona pandemic, it was particularly interesting with regard to the face-to-face presence component of the blended-learning program to find out how the in-class meetings were conducted during this year. In 2020, 63 of the students surveyed were enrolled in ongoing programs. 30 students, or 48%, indicated that the in-class meeting was predominantly face-to-face. 46%, or 29 students, indicated that the meeting took place primarily via video conference. For 6%, i.e., 4 of the 63 students, the mode changed from presence to video conference. Comparing these results with the data of the students who participated in the programs before 2020, it can be seen that before 79% of the in-class meetings took place in presence in the learning centers and only 21% of the students participated in the exchange with their local learning group via video conference.

5.1 Results by variables

In order to investigate which factors influence the success of the blended learning-system under study, a quantitative analysis based on the research instrument of Zhang and Dang was conducted. Through an online questionnaire, students from marginalized regions were asked how much they agree with the statements on different aspects of the factors. Answers could be given via a 5-point Likert scale. The value one corresponds to **strongly disagree**, two stands for **disagree**, three for **not sure, neither agree nor disagree**, the value 4 for **agree**, the value 5 for **strongly agree**. In addition, there was the possibility to choose **Prefer not to say**, these answers are not included in the evaluation. Only in the case of the intention factor did one participant select prefer not to say for all items, which is why a population of 79 was reached for this factor. The questions on service quality were prefaced by a filter question in which students had

to answer whether they had ever used the service, in this case the helpdesk. Only those students who had used the helpdesk were asked further questions about this factor, thus resulting in a total of 18 students. Therefore the significance of these values in the service quality category is also limited due to the low population. The mean value across all factors is 4.2355. Table 4 shows the results of the descriptive statistics. From this it can be seen that the factor Intention, abbreviated as INT, achieved the highest mean value of 4.5, followed by Satisfaction (SAT) with a mean value of 4.3552. The third highest mean value was achieved by the factor Motivation (M) with 4.2979, followed by the factor Teaching Method (TM) with 4.2753. The third lowest mean value was achieved by the factor Service Quality (SVQ) with 4.1444. The second lowest value was achieved by the factor Information Quality (IQ) with 4.1027. The lowest value of all was achieved by the factor Task Technology Fit (TTF) with 4.0917. In addition to the mean values of the factors, the individual mean values of the items are also listed. The lowest mean value was achieved by the second item for the information quality factor. The students were asked to rate the extent to which they agreed with the statement: "The information provided through the Learning Platform is easy to understand. This item achieved a mean of 4.0. It is interesting when looking at the mean values of the items that the second aspect of the system quality "The technology of the Learning Platform offers multimedia (audio, video, and text) types of learning materials" with a value of 4.4375 achieved the fourth best mean value. While the fifth item of the system quality, "in general, response time of the technology of the Learning Platform is reasonable" scored the second lowest value with 4.0253.

In addition to the mean values, the minimum and maximum expression of the items is also shown in the table. In addition to these range indicators, the variance for the factors is also listed individually in the table, as well as is the variance for all items. A closer look at the variances of the factors shows that the factor Computer Self-efficacy (CSE) with 0.4832 has the largest variance, and thus spread around the mean value. The factor Service Quality (SVQ) has the second largest variance, which is again difficult to evaluate due to the small population. The variances of the factors Blended-Learning Flexibility (BLF) and Task-Technology Fit (TTF) with 0.4245 and 0.3964 are also in the area of higher variances and show that the students have given answers more widely scattered around the mean value than, for example, with the factor System Quality (SQ) which shows the smallest variance with 0.2044. In addition, the variance of the answers for the factor Media Richness (MR) was 0.2371, the second smallest. An overview of all these values is given in Table 4.

Factors	Mean	Variance	Item	Mean	Min	Max	N	Variance
CSE	4,2250	0,4832	CSE1	4,2025	1	5	80	0,7533
			CSE2	4,2625	1	5	80	0,8036
			CSE3	4,2278	2	5	80	0,5884
M	4,2979	0,3043	M1	4,3766	3	5	80	0,2905
			M2	4,2727	1	5	80	0,5431
			M3	4,2911	2	5	80	0,5167
IQ	4,1027	0,2415	IQ1	4,1923	1	5	80	0,5210
			IQ2	4,0000	2	5	80	0,5570
			IQ3	4,1899	2	5	80	0,6542
			IQ4	4,0897	1	5	80	0,5451
			IQ5	4,0395	3	5	80	0,2738
			IQ6	4,1688	3	5	80	0,6173
SQ	4,2013	0,2044	SQ1	4,1375	2	5	80	0,4998
			SQ2	4,4375	3	5	80	0,3252
			SQ3	4,1039	2	5	80	0,4891
			SQ4	4,3375	2	5	80	0,4036
			SQ5	4,0253	1	5	80	0,5378
SVQ	4,1444	0,4461	SVQ1	4,0556	2	5	18	0,7614
			SVQ2	4,1765	3	5	18	0,4044
			SVQ3	4,1667	2	5	18	0,6176
			SVQ4	4,1176	2	5	18	0,6103
			SVQ5	4,2222	3	5	18	0,4183
MR	4,2323	0,2371	MR1	4,1250	2	5	80	0,5918
			MR2	4,3125	3	5	80	0,2429
			MR3	4,2250	2	5	80	0,5310
			MR4	4,2692	3	5	80	0,3292
TM	4,2753	0,2413	TM1	4,1519	3	5	80	0,4382
			TM2	4,3038	2	5	80	0,3424
			TM3	4,2125	2	5	80	0,4226
			TM4	4,3375	2	5	80	0,5809
			TM5	4,2911	1	5	80	0,5680
			TM6	4,2625	1	5	80	0,8036
			TM7	4,3625	2	5	80	0,4112
LC	4,1813	0,2784	LC1	4,1750	2	5	80	0,3487
			LC2	4,2000	2	5	80	0,5165
			LC3	4,2375	2	5	80	0,3859
			LC4	4,1392	2	5	80	0,4034
TTF	4,0917	0,3964	TTF1	4,1625	2	5	80	0,5429
			TTF2	4,0779	2	5	80	0,6517
			TTF3	4,0641	1	5	80	0,7621
			TTF4	4,1818	3	5	80	0,3349
BLF	4,2188	0,4245	BLF1	4,2692	2	5	80	0,5370
			BLF2	4,1667	1	5	80	0,6861
			BLF3	4,2405	1	5	80	0,4927
SAT	4,3552	0,3257	SAT1	4,4500	3	5	80	0,3013
			SAT2	4,3924	2	5	80	0,3953
			SAT3	4,3846	3	5	80	0,4216
			SAT4	4,2152	1	5	80	0,7352
INT	4,5000	0,3077	INT1	4,5256	3	5	79	0,3305
			INT2	4,4684	3	5	79	0,3548

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

In the variances of the individual items, the item TM 6, "The In-Class Meetings each week are useful to help me learn the course subjects" shows the largest variance with 0.8036. The same value for the variance is achieved by the item CSE 2 "I am confident about using computers and tablets". This indicates that the spread of the answers around the mean value was particularly large for these two statements. The item MR2, "The various types of online media (including text, images, audios, animations and videos) used in the blended learning course are effective for my learning needs" showed the lowest variance with a value of 0.2429.

Overall, it can be said that a factor or item has broad support when the mean is as high as possible and the variance is as low as possible. In summary, the factors intention and satisfaction received the highest approval from the students in the survey. The factors motivation and teaching method also received above-average approval ratings. While the learning climate, service quality, information quality and task-technology fit were rated below average. The statement on the ease of understanding the information was rated worst. The system quality also scored slightly below average overall, although the students expressed the fourth strongest agreement with the sub-aspect on the availability of multimedia content through the learning system. The value of the entire category was then dragged down by the response time of the system, for example. This scored particularly poorly. In the variances, especially the media richness and the system quality showed a low spread of the answers, while the computer self-efficacy, service quality, blended-learning flexibility received very broadly spread answers from the students. The importance of in-class meetings is where student opinions diverge the most, although this item TM6 was still rated slightly above average with a mean of 4.2625. The same applies to the statement on the students' confidence in using computers and tablets.

In the next section we will explain in more detail which factors affect each other in order to draw further conclusions about the success factors of a blended-learning system from the perspective of students in marginalized regions.

5.2 Correlation of the variables

Based on the correlations, this section will now take a closer look at which factor combinations have an effect on each other. A significant correlation with other success factors can be a further indication of the relevance of a success factor from the perspective of the target group surveyed, and thus contribute to answering the research question posed at the outset.

Since none of the variables is normally distributed, the Spearman correlation coefficient was used for the data analysis. In addition, a two-sided, so-called conservative significance test was performed because there are no assumptions about direction and thus positive or negative correlation. This significance test is also referred to as a conservative significance test. The Table 5 provides an overview of the results.

		INT	SAT	BLF	TTF	LC	TM	MR	SVQ	SQ	IQ	M	CSE
INT	Spearman's Rho		0,5158	0,5385	0,3228	0,4020	0,4797	0,4310	0,3709	0,3576	0,2743	0,4112	0,1826
	Sig. (2-seitig)		0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0037**	0,0002***	0,0000***	0,0001***	0,1297	0,0012**	0,0144*	0,0002***	0,1072
	N		79	79	79	79	79	79	18	79	79	79	79
SAT	Spearman's Rho	0,5158		0,5613	0,6412	0,5684	0,6560	0,4261	0,4736	0,4356	0,4886	0,5010	0,1397
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0000***		0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0001***	0,0471*	0,0001***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,2164
	N	79		80	80	80	80	80	18	80	80	80	80
BLF	Spearman's Rho	0,5385	0,5613		0,5517	0,4931	0,6379	0,3380	0,3795	0,4749	0,3835	0,5252	0,2128
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0000***	0,0000***		0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0022**	0,1203	0,0000***	0,0004***	0,0000***	0,0581
	N	79	80		80	80	80	80	18	80	80	80	80
TTF	Spearman's Rho	0,3228	0,6412	0,5517		0,6056	0,6088	0,5244	0,7079	0,6027	0,5725	0,4274	0,2591
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0037**	0,0000***	0,0000***		0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0010***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0001***	0,0203*
	N	79	80	80		80	80	80	18	80	80	80	80
LC	Spearman's Rho	0,4020	0,5684	0,4931	0,6056		0,5871	0,4956	0,2292	0,5005	0,5488	0,3887	0,3202
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0002***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***		0,0000***	0,0000***	0,3604	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0004***	0,0038**
	N	79	80	80	80		80	80	18	80	80	80	80
TM	Spearman's Rho	0,4797	0,6560	0,6379	0,6088	0,5871		0,5661	0,4970	0,5303	0,5446	0,5594	0,1777
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***		0,0000***	0,0359*	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,1147
	N	79	80	80	80	80		80	18	80	80	80	80
MR	Spearman's Rho	0,4310	0,4261	0,3380	0,5244	0,4956	0,5661		0,9360	0,5649	0,5193	0,3910	0,2658
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0001***	0,0001***	0,0022**	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***		0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0003***	0,0172*
	N	79	80	80	80	80	80		18	80	80	80	80
SVQ	Spearman's Rho	0,3709	0,4736	0,3795	0,7079	0,2292	0,4970	0,9360		0,7344	0,5238	0,4233	0,5082
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,1297	0,0471*	0,1203	0,0010***	0,3604	0,0359*	0,0000***		0,0005***	0,0257*	0,0801	0,0313*
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18	18		18	18	18	18
SQ	Spearman's Rho	0,3576	0,4356	0,4749	0,6027	0,5005	0,5303	0,5649	0,7344		0,5994	0,3298	0,3761
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0012**	0,0001***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0005***		0,0000***	0,0028**	0,0006***
	N	79	80	80	80	80	80	80	18		80	80	80
IQ	Spearman's Rho	0,2743	0,4886	0,3835	0,5725	0,5488	0,5446	0,5193	0,5238	0,5994		0,4665	0,3326
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0144*	0,0000***	0,0004***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0257*	0,0000***		0,0000***	0,0026**
	N	79	80	80	80	80	80	80	18	80		80	80
M	Spearman's Rho	0,4112	0,5010	0,5252	0,4274	0,3887	0,5594	0,3910	0,4233	0,3298	0,4665		0,1899
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,0002***	0,0000***	0,0000***	0,0001***	0,0004***	0,0000***	0,0003***	0,0801	0,0028**	0,0000***		0,0915
	N	79	80	80	80	80	80	80	18	80	80		80
CSE	Spearman's Rho	0,1826	0,1397	0,2128	0,2591	0,3202	0,1777	0,2658	0,5082	0,3761	0,3326	0,1899	
	Sig. (2-seitig)	0,1072	0,2164	0,0581	0,0203*	0,0038**	0,1147	0,0172*	0,0313*	0,0006***	0,0026**	0,0915	
	N	79	80	80	80	80	80	80	18	80	80	80	

***: Very highly significant - The correlation is significant at the 0.001 level (two-sided).
 **: . Highly significant - The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-sided).
 *: Significant - The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-sided).

Table 5: Spearman´s Rho Correlation Coefficient

The results are summarized in section 5.2. For each of the 12 factors, the correlation with the other 11 factors is calculated according to Spearman's Rho correlation coefficient. The correlation coefficient measures the interrelation between two factors. The results are negative when the relation is negative, and positive when there is a positive relation between two factors. In the case studied here, all correlation coefficients are positive. Thus, there are no negative interrelations between two evaluated success factors. If the correlation coefficient is 0, there is no linear dependency between the variables. The closer the value is to zero, the lower the interrelation between the two blended-learning system success factors. The significance test was then used to calculate the probability value (p-value), which indicates the significance of the correlation coefficient. In the table, the significance is symbolized by the gradation of the green tones and the number of strands. As described in the legend below the table, the correlation coefficients are **very highly significant** when the p value from the significance test is less than or equal to 0.0001. **Highly significant** correlation coefficients are those with a p-value less than or equal to 0.01. Correlation coefficients with a p-value of less than or equal to 0.05 are said to be **significant** correlations. For larger values, no significant correlation can be determined.

When looking at the results, it is noticeable that the Task-Technology Fit (TTF), the Media Richness (MR), the System Quality (SQ) and the Information Quality (IQ) show a significant correlation with all other factors.

Satisfaction and Intention

Within this thesis it is assumed that the criteria satisfaction with the system and the intention in the sense of the willingness to take further courses within this blended learning system indicate the success of the system. Therefore, it is particularly interesting to consider to which factors the satisfaction and the intention correlate.

Intention has a very highly significant correlation coefficient with the factors Blended-Learning-Flexibility (BLF), Learning Climate (LC), Teaching Method (TM), Media Richness (MR), and Motivation (M). Further the factors Task-Technology-Fit (TTF) and System Quality (SQ) show highly significant correlations with the factor Intention at the 0.01 significance level. The factor Information Quality has a significant correlation with the factor Intention at the 0.05 significance level. Only the factors Service Quality and Computer Self-Efficiency show no significant correlation to the intention of the students to take further courses within the blended learning system.

Looking at the second factor which, according to the definition in this thesis, has an effect on the success of a blended-learning system, the satisfaction, it can be seen that the satisfaction correlates very highly significant to all investigated success factors except for system quality where the correlation is only significant on the 0.05 level and the factor computer self-efficacy which shows no correlation to the satisfaction.

Service quality and computer self-efficacy are the two factors that have no correlation with Intention. In the case of service quality, however, a weak correlation to student satisfaction with

the blended learning system can be seen in the data. Computer self-efficacy also shows no correlation with Satisfaction.

Service Quality (SVQ)

These results lead to a closer look at the factors Service Quality and Computer Self-Efficacy. In the case of the Service Quality factor, only the students who had already used the service in the sense of the helpdesk rated the statements. Therefore, only 18 of the 80 students evaluated these statements. This can lead to distortions in the meaningfulness of the statistical variables. The factor Service Quality shows correlations with only three other factors at the highest significance level of 0.001. This very highly significant correlation is present with the success factors Task-Technology Fit (TTF), Media Richness (MR) and System Quality (SQ). Furthermore, the service quality correlates at the lowest significance level of 0.05 with the factor Satisfaction (SAT), Teaching Method (TM), Information Quality (IQ) and Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE). No correlation could be found for the remaining four success factors.

Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE)

The factor computer self-efficacy has even less significant correlation coefficients with other factors. Only with the factor System Quality (SQ) does Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE) correlate very highly significantly. The interaction between Learning Climate (LC) and Computer Self-Efficacy is at the 0.01 significance level, the same as the correlation with Information Quality (IQ). A correlation at the lowest significance level can be found between Computer Self-Efficacy (CSE) and Service Quality (SVQ), Media Richness (MR), and Task-Technology-Fit (TTF). Computer Self-Efficacy has no significant correlation with the other five factors. Thus, this factor has fewer correlations than any other factor.

Correlations along the hypotheses formulated by Zhang and Dang

With regard to the research model of Zhang and Dang, the authors tested the dependencies and hypotheses represented by a structural equation model in their research. Going back to this model, at the first level, hypotheses were made about the influence of the external variables CSE, M, IQ, SQ, SVQ, MR, and TM on dependent variables Learning Climate (LC), Task-Technology Fit (TTF), and Blended-Learning Flexibility (BLF) (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 496). If we now examine whether there are correlations along these hypotheses in the data set collected here, we find that there is again no reciprocal relationship between CSE and BLF, SVQ and BLF, and SVQ and LC. In other words, of the hypothesized relationships of service quality, only the one with task-technology fit shows a significant correlation. The external factors motivation, information quality and system quality show highly significant correlations along all hypothesized relationships.

The second level of the model deals with the influence of the dependent variables on the factors satisfaction and interest in taking further courses in the blended learning system. As already explained, the factors Learning Climate (LC), Task-Technology Fit (TTF) and Blended-Learning

Flexibility (BLF) show a highly significant correlation with the students' satisfaction with the blended learning system. And the influence of the three dependent variables on intention is also characterized by a significant correlation between the factors. Only the factors Task-Technology Fit (TTF) and Intention (INT) do not show a perfect very highly-significant correlation like all other factor combinations.

In summary, it can be said that, with the exception of the factors computer self-efficacy and service quality, there are almost only significant correlations with other success factors. However, even with these two factors computer self-efficacy and service quality, the significant correlations always outweigh the factor combinations without correlations. Only the factors Task-Technology Fit, Information Quality and System Quality show significant correlations with both of those factors. Satisfaction and intention are defined as crucial for the success of a blended-learning system, and correlate with all the factors examined, with the exceptions mentioned for Computer Self-Efficacy and for Intention also for Service Quality. How these results correspond to those in the literature is discussed in Chapter 6. Before that, the results of the qualitative research are presented in the following section.

5.3 Evaluation of free responses

As described in section 4.4, an open question at the end of the online questionnaire asked all participants of the evaluation for further ideas on how to improve the JWL Professional Certificate programs. This was done in order to allow students to respond freely, without being pushed in one direction, which would increase their satisfaction and willingness to take further courses with the system. Since the intention and satisfaction in this study measure the success of a blended-learning system, the factors mentioned can be understood as blended-learning system success factors.

Of the 80 students who filled in the survey, 19 did not respond to this question and the remaining 61 wrote a comment in which they addressed success factors or suggested improvements to the system. Many of the comments addressed multiple aspects and are therefore included multiple times in the following lists.

Their overall satisfaction with the system was expressed by 35 participants. Their intention to take further courses in the JWL blended learning system was expressed by 29 participants. Seven students would like to take further courses in Peace and Society, six students would like to take further courses in Computer Technology, and five students would like to take programs in Entrepreneurship. Course topics Languages, Communication, Sustainable Development, Teaching, Youth Empowerment, Youth Sport, Health were each mentioned by two students as course wishes. These examples show the students' willingness to take more courses at JWL. Which in turn is seen in this thesis as an indicator of the success of the blended learning system.

When looking at the free responses and suggestions for improvement to see if success factors from Zhang and Dang's model were addressed, it was found that none of the Self-Related Factors were addressed, but all of the Technology and System Factors as well as the Instructional Design Factor, Teaching Method were addressed. Looking at this result in relation to the research model, it is noticeable that the External Influence Factors are addressed by the students, as well as the endpoints Satisfaction and Intention. However, the dependent constructs Learning climate, Task-Technology-Fit and Blended-Learning Flexibility were not addressed in the free responses.

In addition to the success factors from Zhang and Dang's model, students also addressed the facilitator characteristics which are seen by several authors as significant blended-learning system success factors. Which aspects of the facilitator characteristics are relevant for the two roles of onsite facilitator and online facilitator from the perspective of the JWL students is explained in section 5.3.2. Within this part, student statements regarding the facilitator characteristics will be thematically grouped and that leads to aspects which should be considered in further evaluation of facilitator characteristics as an impact factor on blended-learning system success from the perspective of students in marginalized regions. Furthermore, from the results of the free responses it could be recognized that from the perspective of the students in marginalized regions, the equipment with hardware and internet connectivity is also seen as a success factor of a blended-learning system. This factor was not previously considered in any of the models examined and is therefore briefly explained in section 5.3.3 based on the students' statements. The online questionnaire was carried out anonymously, so that the student statements to which this section refers can also be found in the data set, the ID from the data set was placed in brackets in front of each statement as a reference. All student statements used within this chapter can be found in their original wording in the Appendix.

Some aspects were assigned to different factors as the students' answers suggested different approaches. An example of this is the desire for improved training on how to use the platform at the very beginning. One student would like to have demo material on the platform, i.e. from a service structure aspect, so the point was assigned to the service quality factor. Another sees the onsite facilitator as having the responsibility to help, which is also intended within JWL, so the point was assigned to the Facilitator Characteristics. Another sees it as a system quality aspect that works well in general but is not easy for beginners.

5.3.1 Addressed Success Factors of Zhang and Dang's Model

From the success factors of a blended-learning system according to Zhang and Dang's model, information quality was addressed seven times, media richness six times, teaching method four times, system quality three times, and service quality once in the students' free responses.

Information Quality

The information provided within the JWL Blended-Learning System is relevant for students as statements 21, 54, 106, 141 and 153 show. Another student (35) mentions that they enjoy and think the learning materials are good. As an improvement for the quality of information, one student (57) suggests formulating the expectations for the assignments in a more understandable way.

From these statements of the students it can be seen that many of them appreciate the blended-learning system for the quality of the information. The quality of the information is frequently related to the learning content that seems to be particularly relevant to students from marginalized regions. Since so many students emphasize that they are particularly satisfied with the relevant learning content, it can be seen as an indication that the information quality, especially the relevance of the information for the learners, is an important success factor for blended-learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions.

System Quality

One student (29) probably draws a comparison between the JWL learning system and another one and remarks that the blended learning system of JWL is particularly well suited for students who live in poor surroundings. Another student (127) thinks it is crucial that a system is easy to understand and learners can easily find their way around it. Another (70) finds the system basically good, but not particularly easy to use, especially for beginners.

The JWL blended-learning system as described in section 2.1.3 is mentioned by one student as particularly suitable for the target group under investigation. Furthermore, as some students are very specific about how the system can be improved, it can be concluded from these results that the quality of the system is important to the students. It can therefore be seen as a success factor of a blended-learning system from the perspective of students in marginalized regions.

Service Quality

One student mentions (127) that she/he would be more satisfied with a system that provides help and demo material to better understand how to use the system. This could be seen as an indication that service quality in the sense of more accessible help material contributes to the success of a blended learning system.

Media Richness

In this free response, a total of 6 students mentioned the media diversity of the JWL blended-learning system. This means that about 10% of those who answered the question addressed media richness. The students (18, 52) would prefer videos instead of reading material. Students (81, 52) find monotonous text-based learning content, PDFs and reading material boring in a

blended-learning system, they wish for audio and video elements (127). Videos are more attractive to them and would help them learn (48).

Since 10% of those who made suggestions for improvement specifically mention media richness as a key factor in increasing their satisfaction, it can be concluded from these results that media richness is a blended-learning system success factor from the perspective of students in marginalized regions worldwide.

Teaching Method

Four students addressed aspects of the teaching method in their responses. One student reports that the blended learning approach is very comfortable for her/him and meets her/his learning needs (85). Others (103, 151) describe the course design approach as being particularly effective and having an impact on their actions. Another student (59) suggests an aspect of the teaching method that should be improved: the deadlines for the assignments should be dropped. Since four students refer to aspects of the teaching method in their free responses on the potential for improvement of the JWL programs, it can be concluded from these results that this factor has an influence on their satisfaction and thus the success of the system from the point of view of the student group investigated.

5.3.2 Success Factor - Facilitator Characteristics

The model by Zhang and Dang, which served as the base for this study, does not include the facilitator characteristics. The case study of JWL also has a special feature in this area, as JWL has two facilitator roles in its system. The online facilitator is usually a faculty member of the certifying institution and supervises the students on the subject matter and evaluates their work. The onsite facilitator supervises the students in the local learning groups on site and is not a subject matter expert. Rather the role of the onsite facilitator is that of a coach who guides the students in their learning process. Numerous studies on blended learning system success factors have observed a significant influence of facilitator characteristics on the success of a blended-learning system (Cheng, 2012, p. 365; McGill & Klobas, 2009, p. 118; Seman et al., 2019, p. 137). And therefore, this should also be evaluated within this thesis. In particular the results of whether the facilitator characteristics can be seen as blended-learning system success factors from the perspective of students in marginalized regions or not can contribute to answer the initial research question.

For this purpose, the students' answers to the question about what improvements they see for JWL's blended learning system were analyzed to see whether students addressed aspects related to the facilitator and if so, which aspects.

With 14 statements out of 60 responses, almost a quarter of these students addressed the Facilitator Characteristics. This result shows that a quarter of the students would like to make the

blended-learning system more successful by suggesting improvements to aspects related to the facilitators. Due to the two very different responsibilities of the facilitator roles, they are also discussed separately here.

Online Facilitator related aspects

From the students' point of view, the JWL blended-learning system could be better if the feedback process is improved (29, 73, 139) and the qualification of the online facilitator is better monitored (50). In addition, it was suggested several times (139, 51, 91) to establish a face-to-face communication via video conference or similar with the online facilitators. Some students suggested that because the feedback process is poor and they do not get feedback from the online facilitator, a face-to-face verbal communication at a scheduled time each week would improve their experience in the blended learning system.

One student (50) comments that the professional incompetence of an online facilitator reduces the quality of the course, which leads to a bad learning experience for students, who then do not want to complete courses with this blended-learning system. In contrast, however, one student (64) also reports a particularly positive experience with the blended-learning system, which she expresses in connection with her gratitude for the support provided by the online facilitator. The feedback process is rated by the students (51, 29, 73, 139) as not satisfactory because they have to wait for a long time and get their feedback much too late or because they do not get reliable assessment and feedback at all. This makes it difficult for students to understand what they did wrong and cannot understand the reasons for it. Even with open questions they do not get further if they do not get answers in time (51).

In summary, these results indicate that from the perspective of students in marginalized regions, the following aspects **online facilitator support**, **online facilitator qualification**, **online facilitator response timelines**, and **online facilitator feedback quality** impact the success of the blended-learning system.

Onsite Facilitator related Aspects

Onsite facilitator-related adjustments that could improve JWL' blended-learning system were mentioned by seven students out of 61. Therefore, based on the following results, it can be assumed that the aspects of the onsite facilitator also have an influence within the scope of the facilitator characteristics. Similar to the student statements about the improvements regarding the online facilitator, there is also one student (25) who reports that the positive experience with the onsite facilitator has contributed to their enjoyment of studying in the JWL blended-learning system. But also, in relation to the onsite facilitator, there was one student (47) who commented that the onsite facilitator's expertise was too poor and that a better prepared onsite facilitator would improve the blended learning system. Another student (72) mentioned as

a suggestion for improvement of the system that the in-class meeting was not satisfying in terms of quality and that the discussions were not in-depth enough. Many other students, who shared their suggestions for improving the blended learning system, mentioned that the onsite team was not informed enough. And in terms of JWU's organizational structure, this mainly implicates the onsite facilitator, as they are in direct contact with the students. For example, one student (107) would like to see more advertising before the start of the course in order to be better informed about the programs. Others (53, 70) refer to the fact that the blended-learning system and especially the learning platform works well if you know how everything operates, but especially at the beginning and for new students better training on the use of the system should be carried out to avoid a false impression of the system. Another student (127) connects this need for better explanations of the system even more to the onsite facilitator by directly stating that it would help to improve the blended-learning system if the onsite facilitator explains to the students how everything works.

These statements clearly show the relevance of the onsite facilitator related aspects which also have an impact on the perceived satisfaction with the system and thus on the success of the blended-learning system. The points mentioned could be grouped into the following arguments. The **onsite facilitator support** and the **qualification of the onsite facilitator** have a crucial impact, as does the **moderation of the in-class meeting** and the **helpfulness, guidance, and training to use the system**.

5.3.3 Success Factors Hardware and Internet Connectivity

This thesis deals with the question of which factors have an influence on the success of a blended-learning system from the perspective of students in marginalized regions. Based on a literature review, an existing research instrument was chosen that best examines the factors influencing current blended-learning systems. However, in order to incorporate the perspective of students in marginalized regions more strongly, their suggestions for improvement in particular were analyzed, as described in this section.

The topic of hardware and internet connectivity was mentioned six times. The chosen research model did not take this factor into account. However, because out of 61 responses, six students see the hardware equipment and internet connectivity as the key to improvement of the blended learning system, this factor should be further investigated as a blended-learning system success factor from the perspective of students in marginalized regions.

On which statements of the students this assumption is based and which aspects the students see within this influencing factor will be explained in more detail in the following section.

One student (38) noted that it is time-consuming and complicated for refugees to borrow smartphones or computers to study. It would be much easier to study with the system if tablets and laptops were provided. The same suggestion for improvement is made by student (51).

Another (71) remarks that the distribution of devices should be fair, and everyone should be treated equally. Other students address the suitability of the equipment; large laptops for the students would improve the experience with the blended learning system suggests one (37). Another (140) thinks that tablets would be good to use the offline functionality and to watch videos offline. Another student (115) mentions not the hardware but the internet connection of the learning centers as a point of improvement for JWL's blended-learning system.

These statements from the students can be summarized thematically to aspects that are relevant within the category hardware and internet connectivity from the perspective of students in marginalized regions, as they were mentioned here. Firstly, the students (38, 51, 71) addressed the accessibility and provision of hardware, from which the aspect of **accessibility of hardware for studying** can be derived. The students (37, 140) saw a possibility for improvement of the Blended-learning systems with the availability of suitable hardware. Therefore, the aspect **fit of available hardware for the requirements in the learning system** can be derived. But also, the influence of the internet connectivity, which was mentioned should not be neglected, resulting in the aspect **accessibility of internet connectivity that fulfills the requirements of studying with the blended-learning system**.

In order to better understand the starting point of hardware equipment and internet connection on which the students' suggestions for improvement were based, Figure 17 shows which devices the students who gave feedback are using. This graphic refers to the basic population of 61, i.e. only the students who also submitted suggestions for improvement. This is because 6 students from this group commented on the influencing factors in the hardware and internet connectivity category. Multiple responses were possible in the survey, as students also use different devices. So in total this graphic is based on 78 votes of 61 students. It is recognizable that the majority of the students use their own devices.

Figure 17: Devices used by the 61 students who suggested ideas for system improvements.

Regarding access to internet connectivity, 44 of the 61 students stated that they had access to internet connectivity every day. And as mentioned before, one student of this group commented that it would improve the success of the system if there was better connectivity.

The specification of these reference values for the results should help to decide in future evaluations or system implementations whether the category of hardware and internet connectivity should be taken into account as a success factor or not. The aspects mentioned are very context-related and are particularly relevant from the point of view of a target group that has a structure as described above with regard to the equipment with hardware and internet connectivity.

6 Discussion

To achieve the goal of providing more refugees and young people in marginalized regions around the world with access to higher education, an approach designed to meet the needs of the target group is necessary. Based on the latest findings, blended-learning programs are currently seen as the most promising approach. By combining self-paced, flexible online learning with planned and structured face-to-face learning phases, which can also take place across multiple locations, even at the home place, these programs meet the need of students in marginalized regions for more flexibility. More flexibility allows the integration of studies with professional activities to ensure financial and economical sustainability of students families with participation in higher education. In addition, the advantages of new technologies are used to overcome geographical distances and it is possible to enable students in remote regions to have

access to a wide range of academic programs. In addition to these advantages, blended learning, unlike other e-learning approaches, pays more attention to the elements that are crucial for a successful learning process from a pedagogical point of view. According to UNESCO, social integration during the learning process, learning in interaction with peers, and dealing with what has been learned in a local learning group in one's own living environment make a decisive contribution to the success of higher education offerings, especially for refugees and people in marginalized regions, because the students' self-confidence is strengthened and isolated learning without guidance is counteracted. (Brugha & Hollow, 2017; Gladwell et al., 2016a; UNESCO, 2018, p. 4)

Therefore, this approach, called within their strategy connected learning, is also one of the five strategies of UNHCR to achieve the goal of 15% of refugees enrolled in higher education programs by 2030. (Connected Learning in Crisis Consortium, 2020b; UNHCR, 2019)

The importance of the blended-learning approach is supported by a large body of recent literature on the success criteria of e-learning systems. Blended-learning approaches achieve significant results in terms of their impact on student satisfaction. (Alomari et al., 2020; Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020; Seman et al., 2019)

The results from this study also support this argument. Directly after the factors of general satisfaction and intention to complete further courses with the JWL blended learning system, the factors of motivation and teaching method achieved the best mean values in student survey. JWL students gave above-average positive ratings to statements related to the motivational impact of the blended-learning approach. In addition, statements related to the blended-learning approach also received above-average positive ratings. Students valued the types of tasks and forms of learning such as interaction with class members in global discussion boards and flexible offline and multimedia learning packages significantly more than many other aspects of the JWL system. This strongest endorsement of JWL's blended-learning approach from students in marginalized regions is further underscored by the highly significant correlation of motivation and teaching method with student satisfaction with the system. With regard to the students' free responses, motivation was not directly addressed by any of the students who provided a suggestion for improvement or feedback, which if not for the quantitative research findings would lead to dropping the factor as a success factor from the perspective of students in marginalized regions. The teaching method, on the other hand, was addressed several times and explicitly praised as particularly efficient or comfortable. These results clearly indicate that students in marginalized regions perceive the teaching method as crucial for the success of a learning system.

For the reasons just mentioned, the blended-learning approach is considered particularly suitable for the implementation of higher education measures for a target group of students in marginalized regions. Especially the success factors **motivation** of the blended-learning approach

and the **teaching method** are therefore crucial success factors from the point of view of the investigated target group.

For a closer look at the success factors of a blended-learning system, a comprehensive model is necessary to consider both technical and pedagogical success factors.

A blended-learning system is from a technical point of view an information system, the associated technical functionalities and their design can have a decisive impact on the success of the system, but as just described a blended-learning system is also a specific pedagogical approach, so success factors from the pedagogical perspective must also be considered. A model that combines as many of these factors as possible from different perspectives is the Blended-Learning Success Model according to Zhang and Dang, which was published in 2020. According to this model, factors which influence satisfaction with the blended-learning system and the intention to take further courses enrolled through this system were identified on two levels. The influence of these variables, satisfaction and intention on the success of an information system has been shown to be significant in numerous studies. In particular, the studies on the evaluation of information systems from the perspective of the D&M IS success Model, the Technology Acceptance, User Satisfaction and system effectiveness were incorporated. The factors satisfaction and intention have proven themselves in numerous research models as significant characteristics of system success. As the constructs originated from two very basic research perspectives the D&M IS Success Model (DeLone, William & McLean, 2003) and the TAM approach (Davis et al., 1989).

The research results collected in this thesis show that the students with a mean of 4.5 at least agree if not strongly agree to be willing to attend further courses using this system. Also the satisfaction finds broad agreement. Furthermore, the factors satisfaction and intention are particularly well suited to characterize the success of a system from the perspective of the target group, as they correlate with almost all factors. Except for service quality, which is not reliable due to an unreliable data basis and can therefore be ignored. And the factors satisfaction and intention to take further courses with the system does not correlate with the factor Computer Self-Efficacy. What the remaining results show about the factor computer self-efficacy will be explained later. In summary, based on the results of the survey and the qualitative analysis, **satisfaction** and **intention** are considered as critical success factors for blended-learning system success from the perspective of students in marginalized regions.

The factors that affect satisfaction and intention in Zhang and Dang's model emerge from numerous research perspectives and represent many of the aspects discussed in the current literature. In the following, the extent to which the results from the evaluation of these factors within a group of students in marginalized regions around the world differ from the results of other

research studies will be discussed. As described at the beginning, it is crucial to consider the different perspectives from which success factors for blended-learning systems arise. Therefore, the results of the factors from the technological perspective, then factors from the pedagogical perspective, then e-learning-specific factors and finally the facilitator-related success factors and their results will be discussed.

Technology and system-related factors

In numerous studies, the D&M IS Success Quality dimensions, Information Quality, Service Quality and System Quality have shown significant influence on the success of information systems, e-learning systems as well as in special studies on blended-learning systems. (e.g. Wu) Therefore, these three success factors have been evaluated in numerous studies. Not all of these studies found significant support for all three success factors. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 503; Mohammadi, 2015, p. 370; Seman et al., 2019, p. 136; J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 162) For example, Lee and Hwang 2007 found no significance for the influence of information quality in their study of factors influencing students satisfaction, Seman et al. found no significant influence of system quality, while Ghazal et al. found significant influence of these two quality dimensions, but not for service quality, which was significant in the studies of the other two. (Ghazal, Aldowah, et al., 2018; J.-K. Lee & Hwang, 2007; Seman et al., 2019)

While Zhang and Dang in their study could not hold the hypothesized relationships between Information Quality and Learning Climate, System Quality and Learning Climate as well as between System Quality and Task-Technology Fit, in the analysis of these success factors conducted in this paper all factor combinations with Information Quality and System Quality showed significant correlations. This means that from the perspective of students in marginalized regions, Information Quality and System Quality have a positive influence on the other factors considered, such as Learning Climate, Task-Technology Fit, Blended-Learning Flexibility, Satisfaction and Intention. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020, p. 503)

In addition, it is noticeable that the students in marginalized regions showed the lowest variance in the evaluation of the aspects of system quality and thus tended to make quite similar assessments. What was striking, however, was that within the aspects of system quality, the students rated the technology and reproduction of multimedia content as above average but rated the response time of the system below average with the second smallest mean. The multimedia technology should therefore be maintained and set a good example for other systems. The reason for the poor response time could be found in poor internet connectivity, but it is also conceivable that the students were not only referring to the technical aspects of the system, but also to the poor response time of the online tutors. This would be obvious since many students mentioned this point in their free answers, which were described in section 5.3. In order to draw reliable conclusions, the question of why students rated the system response time below

average would have to be investigated further. With regard to the quality of the system, the most important factor from the point of view of the target group was the understandable presentation of the content, for example by use of multimedia elements. In the qualitative analysis of the free responses, the students were satisfied with the quality of the information, and especially mentioned that the relevance of the learning content to their own context is crucial. The easy-to-understand wording was also mentioned in the free answers as a potential for improvement. Comprehensible and engaging learning materials and contextualized learning content should therefore be considered when designing blended learning programs for a target group in marginalized regions. This aspect of the systems quality was also specifically addressed in the free responses. The special adaptation of the JWL system to the situation of students in marginalized regions was emphasized. And as Al-Busaidi stated, the confirmation of the significance of the system and information success criteria should be seen as a call for continuous development of the system from a technical and content perspective (Al-Busaidi, 2012, pp. 28–29).

Overall, these results show that the factors of **information quality** and **system quality** are taken into account in blended-learning systems for students in marginalized regions worldwide, as they have shown significant influence on success.

The results of the third factor, service quality, which is significant from the point of view of the current literature depending on the context, are considered separately, since this was only evaluated only within a population of 18 students. Because only students who had already used the helpdesk were surveyed, the results are therefore of limited validity. However, it is clear from the demographics of the student group that a large number of students had already used the system in a previous course and therefore had already been trained and didn't needed the support. This could be another reason why the service quality factor shows particularly little correlation with other factors and, above all, does not correlate with the intention to take further courses. According to the findings of Ghazal et al. the service quality being classified as critical for success differs depending on the previous knowledge and training of the students with the system. As one student stated in his free response, and that is also described in the study by Ghazal et al 2018, tutorials or other retrievable support services are important from the students' point of view, even better is detailed training for students on how to use the system. Intensive student training would avoid frustration while using the platform and fits to the call of the JWL student for more training and help material. If this is extensively fulfilled or if the students are already familiar with the system, it is possible that the service quality in an evaluation shows hardly any significant influence, according to Ghazal et al. (2018)

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that **service quality** in the sense of support is important for the success of a blended-learning program from the perspective of students in marginalized areas. Intensive student training is therefore recommended (Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018, pp. 77188–77195). However, since most of the need for support occurs at the

very beginning of the program, and only if the students have hardly worked with the system or have little previous knowledge, it is possible that the continuous support is not perceived as critical to the success of the program because it is no longer needed.

In addition to the described quality dimensions, media richness is also included in the category of technology and system-related factors in Zhang and Dang's model as a success factor of blended-learning systems. Media richness was confirmed as a significant influencing factor in the study by Liu et al. In the study by Zhang and Dang, media richness also showed significant effects on the constructs learning climate and task-technology fit. From the perspective of students in marginalized regions around the world, the media richness correlates very strongly with the satisfaction with the blended-learning system, the willingness to take further courses using it, the blended-learning flexibility and the learning climate. For this reason alone, this factor should be considered an important success factor from the perspective of the target group. In addition, 10% of the students who gave a suggestion for improvement or free feedback also mentioned the variety of media. Videos are particularly important from the perspective of the target group, as long texts and PDFs are difficult to read and are perceived as being tiring. From the target group's point of view, media richness is to be seen as a critical success factor of a blended-learning systems.

Success factors based on a pedagogical perspective

As mentioned at the beginning, not only aspects from the technical perspective play a critical role in blended-learning systems, but also factors that result from an educational or pedagogical perspective. Two factors from this category have already been explained in the argumentation on the necessity of blended learning at the beginning of this chapter. This showed that the Motivation and Teaching Method are critical success factors from the perspective of the target group. Therefore, the teaching method and motivation will not be addressed again here.

Computer Self-Efficacy is a success factor of blended-learning systems, which is discussed very controversially in the literature. As already mentioned from the perspective of the interviewed target group, computer self-efficacy does not correlate with the satisfaction and the willingness to take further courses. Some authors have found significant influence on aspects of e-learning system success in previous evaluations (Y.-C. Chen, 2014, p. 168; J.-K. Lee & Hwang, 2007, pp. 74–77; J.-H. Wu et al., 2010, p. 162), others like Al Busaidi could not find that computer self-efficacy is a critical factor for success (Al-Busaidi, 2012, p. 27). Similarly, the authors of the Zhang and Dang research model were unable to find significance for their hypothesized effects of Computer Self-Efficacy on Blended Learning Flexibility, Learning Climate, or Task-Technology Fit in their study. In contrast, the survey conducted in this thesis using the same research instrument found a correlation with Task-Technology Fit, Media Richness, and Service Quality

that was significant at the 0.05 level. Significant correlations at the 0.01 level were found with Learning Climate and Information Quality. The correlation with system quality was highly significant. The results cannot be directly compared due to statistical values as Zhang and Dang used a structural equation model to test their hypotheses while this paper investigates whether correlations exist between factors. Nevertheless, it is striking that a total of six of the eleven examined correlations of computer self-efficacy are significant, and thus more than half of the factors have some kind of significant relationship. Crucial for the success of a blended-learning system is that any kind of connection of the evaluated factors with the factors satisfaction with the system or intention to further use the system exists. There is no correlation to either of these. A vague attempt to explain this could be the following: students in developing countries have very different levels of computer literacy (Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018, pp. 77188–77195) and therefore they might have very different levels of computer self-efficacy. This is also reflected in the fact that the computer self-efficacy factor shows the highest variance. Regardless of their computer literacy skills, the majority of students agree that they would like to take further courses. This could be due to the fact that there are not many alternative programs for the target group and also because the system is easy to use for everyone, regardless of previous knowledge and computer self-efficacy. Since the system is generally perceived as satisfactory, Ghazal Al-Samarraie et al.'s conclusion that a well-designed system does not require specific technological skills (Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018) could be seen as a reason why computer self-efficacy and intention to take further courses within this system do not correlate.

In order to make reliable statements, the issue would have to be investigated in more detail. Since the students did not mention computer self-efficacy in the free answers and suggestions for improvement and no correlations towards the two factors satisfaction and intention were found, these arguments outweigh the significant correlations found to other factors and lead to the conclusion that from the point of view of the student group surveyed, it cannot be reliably assumed that computer self-efficacy is one of the critical success factors of blended-learning systems. Based on these results, this factor is therefore dropped for the time being.

E-learning specific factors

In Zhang and Dang's model, three constructs that have been shown to be significant in the current research literature on success factors of e-learning or blended learning systems are included. These are the success factors learning climate, task-technology fit and blended-learning-flexibility. These constructs showed significant results in earlier studies, for example, the learning climate showed significant positive influence in the study by Ghazal et al (2018, pp. 77188–77195). The fit of tasks and learning technology showed significant influence on the use of the learning environment for example in the studies of Lin and Wang and McGill and Kolbas (2012, p. 96; 2009, pp. 496–503). The relevance of the factor blended-learning flexibility was

already mentioned in the beginning, students appreciate the flexibility for self-paced learning so this factor showed significant influence in the study of Al-Busaidi (2012, p. 28,29). Moreover, Zhang and Dang also found significant results for these three factors in their study. In the evaluation conducted in this paper, the correlations of blended-learning flexibility with the intention factor and the satisfaction factor were highly significant. The Learning Climate factor also correlated highly significantly with Satisfaction and Intention in the results of the survey of JWL students. The correlation of Task-Technology Fit with Intention was also highly significant. Only the correlation with Satisfaction was highly significant only at the 0.01 level. From these results it is clear that also students in marginalized regions consider these three factors as blended-learning success factors. However, since these are more complex constructs that were also considered as dependent variables by Zhang and Dang, it is not surprising that students did not directly address these factors in their feedback and suggestions for improvement. Looking at the mean values from the survey, the task-technology fit found the lowest agreement. Considering that this factor correlates strongly with other success factors of a blended-learning system, it could be concluded that further research should be done to improve the task-technology fit.

One aspect of the research question focused on which of the factors from a research model found based on current literature also show significant influence from the perspective of students in marginalized regions. The answer to this question was explained on the previous pages. The factors Satisfaction, Intention, Motivation, Information Quality, System Quality, Service Quality, Media Richness, Teaching Method, Task-Technology Fit, Blended-Learning Flexibility and Learning Climate can be seen as significant success factors for Blended-Learning System Success from the perspective of students in marginalized regions worldwide. Thus, from Zhang and Dang's model, only the Computer Self-Efficacy factor was found to be non-significant. This factor also showed no significance in the authors' study. (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)

Facilitator-related success factors

Facilitator-related aspects have a major impact on the success of a blended-learning system and should therefore also be seen as a success factor. Numerous authors have already identified significant influence of facilitator characteristics on the success of the blended-learning system in their research. (Cheng, 2012, p. 365; McGill & Klobas, 2009, p. 118; Seman et al., 2019, p. 137)

In the research model of Zhang and Dang this factor was not included and additionally the context of the case study which was examined in this work, has very specific support concept, meaning a separate qualitative analysis was necessary. The results showed that almost a quarter of the students who gave feedback and suggestions for improvement referred to the fact that the system could be improved if a facilitator-related aspect would improve. This clearly

demonstrates that from the perspective of students in marginalized regions around the world, the **facilitator characteristics** factor has an impact on the success of the blended-learning system.

The students' statements show that aspects of the **online facilitator** have both positive and negative effects on the blended-learning system from the students' perspective in marginalized regions. Facilitator Characteristics can be seen as success factors of blended-learning systems based on these results, because students report a particularly positive experience with the system due to the great support provided by their online facilitator. While others have had the exact opposite experience in the same blended-learning system but with different online facilitator. If students are no longer willing to take courses in the system due to the lack of professional qualifications of the online facilitator, this affects the success of the blended-learning system according to the definition set in this paper. Consequently, based on these results, the aspects of **online facilitator support** and the **online facilitator qualification** should be taken into account within the facilitator characteristics, as these have an influence on the success of the system. Furthermore, the results showed that the students perceived a problem with the lack of timely feedback, which they perceived as a negative aspect of the system. From their point of view this can be improved if either the blended-learning system included scheduled meetings or if the facilitators give faster and more reliable feedback. Thus, these results show that the aspect of online facilitator communication should be taken into account, as well as **online facilitator response timelines** and **online facilitator feedback quality**.

Furthermore, the results of the analysis of the free responses show that the aspects **onsite facilitator support** and **onsite facilitator qualification** should also be considered for the onsite facilitator, because the experiences of the students (25, 47) prove the impact on the perception of satisfaction with the blended-learning system. Since the onsite facilitator at JWL leads the in-class meeting twice a week and this experience can have an impact on the satisfaction with the system as student (72) mentioned, it should also be considered that the aspect **onsite facilitator moderation of In-Class meetings** within the facilitator characteristics can have an impact on the success of the blended-learning system. This factor might need to be adapted according to the context. The frequency of the described suggestions for improvement in the sense of more training by onsite facilitators on the system in order to know how everything works, particularly at the beginning of a program, showed that from the point of view of the target group, students in marginalized regions, there is an impact on the perception of the system satisfaction. The students (127, 53,70) mentioned that the JWL blended-learning system could be improved with better training and more guidance from the onsite facilitator on the use and functionalities of the system.

Therefore, the aspect of **onsite facilitators helpfulness, guidance and training to use the system** should be considered within the group facilitator characteristics. It has been shown

that students in marginalized regions have perceived an impact of this aspect on the success of the blended-learning system. The need for training for students on the structure and design, operation, and functionalities of the learning system is addressed in several studies (Alomari et al., 2020, pp. 23543–23554; Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018, pp. 77188–77195). Since it was also addressed by the students in the area of service quality, this aspect is dealt with there. Here the training refers to the fact that a facilitator should be able to explain the system to his students in the local learning group. This should be achieved through a comprehensive training of the facilitator, as also confirmed by numerous sources. Within the training, the facilitators should also be trained on the other critical aspects mentioned above.

From these results it can be seen that from the perspective of students in marginalized regions the facilitator characteristics factor is critical for the success of blended-learning systems. Since in the case study the facilitation of the students is divided into two different roles, there are also aspects of both facilitator roles that have an effect on the satisfaction with the system and thus on the success of the blended-learning system from the students' point of view. Therefore depending on the context, all aspects of support should be taken into account as far as possible. The support and qualification of both facilitator roles plays a crucial role from the perspective of the students surveyed. In the case of the online facilitators, who have the task of providing professional feedback and academic support to the students, the students see response timelines and feedback quality as critical aspects for success. The onsite facilitators take over the accompaniment of the students by supporting them in a coach-like role. The aspects of facilitation skills of the In-Class Meeting and the helpfulness, guidance and training for the use of the learning platform are therefore, from the students' point of view, crucial aspects that can have an impact on the success of the blended-learning system.

Numerous publications indicate that comprehensive facilitator training is essential to prepare facilitators to perform these critical tasks to the satisfaction of students (Alomari et al., 2020, pp. 23543–23554; Ghazal, Al-Samarraie, et al., 2018, pp. 77188–77195). Thus, a substantial facilitator training can also have an impact on the success of a blended-learning system.

Hardware and Internet Connectivity Factor

From the perspective of students in marginalized regions, the extent to which the necessary hardware and internal connections are available is also critical to the success of the blended learning system. The students' statements on this can be summarized in three aspects: **accessibility of hardware for studying, fit of available hardware for the requirements in the learning system** and **accessibility of internet connectivity that fulfills the requirements of studying with the blended-learning system**. By adapting the equipment of the learning centers to these aspects, JWL can help students to be more satisfied with the system. However,

these findings are still very vague and therefore not very reliable, as there are interesting aspects within the current data, which should be further investigated.

The results of the survey showed that the majority of students use their own devices. Why this is the case should be investigated in further evaluations, precisely because the students see it as a success factor for the system if suitable devices are provided. The same applies to the effects of internet connectivity. On the basis of the data collected, it can be stated that, from the students' point of view, it can be a critical aspect for success, even if a large proportion stated that they have access to the internet every day. In order to derive clear recommendations for action, a specific investigation of these aspects is therefore necessary.

The evaluation of the demographic data of the study conducted within this thesis as described in Chapter 5 showed that access to hardware and internet connectivity can differ widely even within the different marginalized regions of the world. It is therefore essential to consider the relevance of this aspect on a case-by-case basis.

Overall, it can be concluded from the results that the hardware equipment and internet connectivity with the aspects **accessibility of hardware for studying, fit of available hardware for the requirements in the learning system** and **accessibility of internet connectivity that fulfills the requirements of studying with the blended-learning system** from the perspective of students in marginalized regions have a decisive impact on the success of the blended-learning system. In future programs of JWL that should satisfy students in marginalized regions and lead to students wanting to take more courses in this system, these aspects should be taken into account. The success factor of hardware and internet connectivity is therefore particularly difficult to generalize for the above mentioned reasons of contextuality.

In addition to the significant factors already mentioned, the students surveyed also see the factors facilitator characteristics and hardware and internet connectivity as critical success factors for blended-learning systems. For each of these factors, various aspects were found that should be considered when enrolling further courses or planning further offerings for students in marginalized regions worldwide in order to establish a successful blended-learning system.

7 Conclusion

This thesis explored the question, of the success criteria of a blended-learning system, for students living in marginalized regions globally? The results of the study will help to facilitate access to higher education for students in marginalized regions by establishing criteria for future blended-learning system implementations that reflect the success factors from the perspective of the target group. In the widest sense, this can also contribute to UNHCR's goal of enrolling

15% of young refugees in higher education programs by 2030, as one strategy to achieve this goal is the expansion of connected learning programs. An established provider of these programs is JWL and therefore a case study was conducted at JWL to investigate what success factors should be considered in these programs. What can be achieved with successful blended-learning systems, besides contributing to the UNHCR goal, is shown by the feedback written for the JWL courses by a student in the survey of this research:

“The courses you offered gives one to know his/her identity. it led to have positive moral values in the community and outside therefore, you can be a good example for others especially youths who are addicted to drugs abuses. It help to gain knowledge and transform the society as an extra -curricular education. Help to express depression and can reaching to the solutions easily. It can be good if you offer higher education to widening the skills and become perfect intellectual so that to be easy in tackling tough conditions by helping those who are in depression.” (Survey Result, 2020)

As this quote indicates and the survey data shows, the JWL system can be seen as an example of a successful blended-learning system, as it is highly approved by students and many of them wish to take further programs of this kind. Successful blended-learning system is characterized by high student satisfaction and desire to take more courses with this system. Students of JWL in different marginalized regions around the world saw their satisfaction with the system and their intention to take further courses as being influenced by several factors. On the one hand, by the **teaching method**, which is especially adapted to the target group, and on the other hand, by the **motivation** that the offer provides through its design. Especially the context-related effective learning in the blended-learning process is perceived by the students as positive and motivating. Future programs for students in marginalized regions should therefore pay attention to a blended-learning approach to enable students to learn in a motivating and efficient way that is adapted to the context. This can be achieved, for example, by activities or project work where students implement what they have learned or can connect their learnings with their real-life experiences.

Further influence on satisfaction and the intention to take further courses with the system showed the system and technology-related factors. The **quality of the information** is one of them. From the students' point of view, this refers primarily to relevant information, context-related and easy to understand learning content. Expectations should also be clearly formulated. In addition, the **media richness**, i.e. the diversity of the media used, is critical for success. From the students' point of view, it is better to use video and audio instead of long texts. The **quality of the system** is another significant success factor from the perspective of the students that were surveyed. JWL's platform was praised for being particularly well adapted to the needs of students in marginalized regions. A platform that is as easy to use as possible is necessary for this purpose. In order to better understand how the blended-learning system is structured and

how it works, training material and explanations for students are required. Since this **quality of service** is also a significant influencing factor from the perspective of students in marginalized regions, future programs should invest in intensive system training for students. The significance of the technology and system-related factors should be understood as a call for continuous further development (Al-Busaidi, 2012, pp. 28–29). At the same time, investments in the IT system should always be monitored and based upon evaluations of the IT system success, since investing in the technology does not automatically cause success (Ojo, 2017, p. 60).

Furthermore, a good **Task-technology fit**, i.e. a good fit of the tasks and the available functionalities on the learning platform has, from the perspective of students in marginalized regions, a positive effect on the satisfaction with the blended-learning system and intention to further use it. The provider should therefore ensure that the course content and the tasks set are perfectly matched to the technological system. That means for example that the tasks can be solved well with the available technology features. From the perspective of the students surveyed, **blended-learning flexibility** is also a significant success factor. The blended-learning concept should give the students as much freedom as possible for self-paced learning, but at the same time provide sufficient structure and guidance and opportunities for interaction through face-to-face or virtual communication so that the students do not feel isolated but study together in a social environment. Social interaction is also an aspect of the learning climate. From the perspective of students in marginalized regions, the **learning climate** also influences the success of the blended-learning system. If possible, the blended-learning system should be designed in such a way that it provides a pleasant learning climate where students enjoy learning, the environment motivates them to learn, and that they enjoy the shared learning experience in global exchange with others.

In addition to these factors that emerged from Zhang and Dang's research model and were also found to be significant from the perspective of students in marginalized regions, further factors were found to be specifically relevant from the perspective of the target group surveyed. The factor Computer self-Efficacy was dropped as it didn't show enough significant results within this study.

Facilitation characteristics are critical success factors for students in marginalized regions around the world. Future programs should take into account the aspects of facilitation found in order to increase the satisfaction of students and their intention to attend further courses with the blended-learning system. From the students' point of view, the qualification, support, response timelines and feedback quality are crucial for online academic support. In addition, the following aspects should be examined as regards the face-to-face facilitator: Support, qualification, facilitation of in-class meetings, helpfulness, guidance and training on system usage. The aspects are listed separately, as in the context studied these responsibilities are divided between two facilitator roles. The best possible fulfillment of the mentioned aspects can be

achieved through intensive and holistic training of the facilitators. Since the tasks and thus the aspects that have an impact on the success of the system in the context of JWL differ greatly according to the facilitator role, it is recommended for JWL to provide facilitator training depending on the role. In addition, the investigated context showed that from the students' perspective, the **equipment with suitable hardware and sufficient internet connectivity** is critical for the success of the blended learning offer. The aspects accessibility of hardware for studying, fit of available hardware for the requirements in the learning system and accessibility of internet connectivity that fulfills the requirements of studying with the blended-learning system are important from students' perspective. Since this aspect is strongly context-related and not enough data has been collected on the circumstances behind it, it is not possible to make a general statement on this success factor. However, JWL should take note of this significant aspect from the perspective of their students and undertake further investigations to equip their students accordingly in order to ensure the satisfaction of the students and their intention to take further courses. Which would enrich even more the success for their blended-learning system.

In conclusion, then, and thus answering the research question, the following factors influence the success of blended-learning systems from the perspective of students in marginalized regions worldwide:

Intention, Satisfaction, Motivation, Teaching Method, Information Quality, System Quality, Service Quality, Media Richness, Task-Technology Fit, Blended-Learning-Flexibility, Learning Climate, Facilitator Characteristics and within JWL's context the hardware and internet connectivity.

A further exciting aspect that emerged in the research, and is highlighted here because it has rarely been considered within JWL's system planning processes, is the significant influence of marketing and the appearance of the learning system as a particular brand on the success of the learning system (Alomari et al., 2020, pp. 23551–23554). Although this factor has not been studied much, it would be exciting to further explore how marketing initiatives would impact system success, especially from the perspective of JWL students.

This work also has some limitations that need to be considered when interpreting the results. This research work took a highly specialized blended-learning program which is adapted to the challenges of students in marginalized areas where the organization JWL has been working for many years and has already gathered experience. That might have affected the generalization of the results to a wider group of students in marginalized areas. Furthermore the impact of other factors caused by the environment or JWL as organization were been taken into account, but might have impacted the results. Particularly because the programs examined also included pilot runs, i.e., first implementations of new programs, as well as second, third, or fourth

enrollments in which, for example, the onsite and online supervisors in some cases already had significantly more experience with the program, there may have been inconsistencies in the data. Organizational processes onsite and at JWL improved with time and experience, but the fact that the results for individual programs did not show significant deviations from each other because the populations were too small cannot eliminate the influence of such inconsistencies. Another limitation of the analysis is that, due to the time constraints of this master's thesis, the statistical method used in Zhang and Dang's research instrument could not be applied to the data analysis, so that no direct comparison can be drawn between the target group studied by the authors in the USA and the students in marginalized regions surveyed here. In addition, it should be noted that the students, as indicated by the demographic survey, mostly came from countries in which people often refrain from openly criticizing issues for cultural reasons. For example in several countries critical thinking is not deeply rooted in their cultures and government school systems. In the evaluation on a Likert scale of 1-5, it is therefore possible that students are reluctant to express criticism and that in some cases a **neither agree nor disagree** meant a negative evaluation that was not so openly marked for reasons of politeness or culture. This in turn could have led to incorrect data.

In order to improve the validity of the data, the service quality in particular should be re-evaluated in further research steps, as the small sample is not a reliable basis for the data. The same applies to the facilitator characteristics, as these were researched in a qualitative free study. It would be better in a future study to include the facilitator characteristics with all the aspects mentioned in the research model. In a further study, the hardware and internet connectivity aspects could also be included in the questionnaire and measured with specific items in order to find out more precisely how many students regard this aspect as critical to success. In addition, the study should also be conducted in other contexts from the perspective of students in marginalized regions in order to exclude possible effects of the organization JWL and to thus obtain more generalizable data. If these studies were conducted within a larger population, it might be possible to draw regional or cultural conclusions. Based on the data within this research these are not meaningful because the sample is too small. With these findings, future blended-learning systems could be better adapted to the target groups. With more and more adapted programs, satisfaction and intention to take courses would rise and more equality in higher education can be created in the global context. In the widest sense, this can then also contribute to UNHCR's goal of enrollment of 15% of refugee youth in higher education programs by 2030.

8 Glossary

BL	Blended Learning
BLF	Blended-Learning-Flexibility, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
CSE	Computer Self-Efficacy, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
D&M	DeLone and McLean the authors of a widely-known and frequently cited system success model.
FC	Facilitator Characteristics
INT	Intention, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
IQ	Information Quality, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
IS Success	Information System Success
JWL	Jesuit Worldwide Learning
LC	Learning Climate, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
M	Motivation, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
MR	Media Richness, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
SAT	Satisfaction, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
SQ	System Quality, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
SVQ	Service Quality, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model according to (Davis et al., 1989b)
TM	Teaching Method, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
TTF	Task-Technology Fit, Blended-Learning Success Factor according to (Gavin Zhang & Yan Dang, 2020)
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, United Nations Organization for the Promotion of Education, Science and Culture, and Communication and Information.
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, United Nations refugee agency
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology according to (Venkatesh et al., 2003)

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11 Appendix

11.1 Questionnaire according to Zhang and Dang, 2020

Items	Code+ AA1:D 63
Computer Self-Efficacy	
I enjoy using computers and tablets.	CSE1
I am confident about using computers and tablets	CSE2
In general, I am comfortable with using computers, tablets and software applications.	CSE3
Motivation	
The blended learning environment motivates me to learn the course content.	M1
I feel my motivation to learn the course content increases because it's offered as a blended-learning program. (Compared to a course in complete online self-directed learning or complete In-Class mode)	M1
The In-Class Meetings enhance my motivation in studying this course.	M3
Information Quality	
The information provided through the Learning Platform is relevant for my learning. (Help: I can see that the learning materials are relevant to reach the learning objectives of this course. The information on the platform is relevant to do the learning activities and assignments successfully.)	IQ1
The information provided through the Learning Platform is easy to understand. (Help: The language used is easy to understand. The learning materials are presented in a way that I can easily understand the information)	IQ2
The information provided through the Learning Platform is overall very good.	IQ3
The information provided through the Learning Platform is up to date. (Help: The examples, case studies and materials seem to be up to date (Not outdated and old))	IQ4
The information provided through the Learning Platform is complete.(Help: There are now open questions, after studying one unit I know how to do the activities and assignment.)	IQ5
The information provided through the Learning Platform is accurate. (Help: The information is correct in all details)	IQ6
System Quality	
The technology of the Learning Platform offers flexibility in learning as to time and place.	SQ1
The technology of the Learning Platform offers multimedia (audio, video, and text) types of learning materials.	SQ2

The technology of the Learning Platform offers sufficient functions for my learning.	SQ3
In general, the technology of JWL's Learning Platform is reliable.	SQ4
In general, response time of the technology of the Learning Platform is reasonable.	SQ5
Service Quality	
Have you ever contacted the JWL-Helpdesk (Mail address: jwl-helpdesk@seitwerk.de) ?	SVQ0
The Helpdesk for JWL's Learning Platform answers promptly. (Help: Answers within 72 hours)	SVQ1
The Helpdesk for JWL's Learning Platform is reliable.	SVQ2
The Helpdesk for JWL's Learning Platform is accessible. (Help: is accessible (= can be contacted easily))	SVQ3
Using the Helpdesk to get support is convenient.	SVQ4
Overall my impression of contacting the Helpdesk for JWL's Learning Platform is satisfactory.	SVQ5
Media Richness	
In addition to the In-Class Meetings (via Zoom or Onsite) , the blended learning course also uses a wide range of online media to support my learning, including text, images, audio, animations and videos	MR1
The various types of online media (including text, images, audios, animations and videos) used in the blended learning course are effective for my learning needs.	MR2
The various types of online media (including text, images, audio, animations and videos) used in the blended learning course are helpful for me to complete the assignments and learning activities.	MR3
Overall, the blended learning course provides a wide range of media that are supportive for my learning.	MR4
Teaching Method	
I have a positive feeling toward using the digital learning materials during the In-Class Meetings.	TM1
The interactive self study materials are helpful for me to learn the content input of each unit.	TM2
Having several small learning activities is helpful for me to learn the concepts covered in the unit.	TM3
Assignments and Project work are helpful to find out if I'm able to transfer what I have learned to real tasks.	TM4
The exchange with my classmates in the global class discussions is helpful to deepen my understanding of the unit's learning content.	TM5
The In-Class Meetings each week are useful to help me learn the course subjects.	TM6
Having practical relevant assignments and activities where I bring in the experiences of my community keeps me motivated to keep studying this course.	TM7
Learning Climate	
The process of using the JWL Learning Platform to assist my learning is pleasant.	LC1

I have fun with the blended learning program.	LC2
I find the blended learning program to be enjoyable.	LC3
The learning climate provided by the blended learning program could motivate my spontaneous learning	LC4
Task-Technology-Fit	
The various functionalities used on the Learning Platform for submitting the activities and assignments match my learning needs.	TTF1
The technology of the Learning Platform suits for all tasks I have to submit while studying this course.	TTF2
This course provides me with all the information and material I need to reach my learning goals.	TTF3
I feel that my learning goals and needs are met by utilizing JWLs Learning Platform for blended learning programs	TTF4
Blended- Learning Flexibility	
Meeting my onsite facilitator only twice a week in the classroom and working on the activities and assignments at my own place of choice (either in the learning center or at home) gives me more flexibility to study this course.	BLF1
Meeting my onsite facilitator only twice a week in the classroom and working on the activities and assignments at my own place of choice (either in the learning center or at home) allows me to learn and complete the assignments at my own pace.	BLF2
Meeting my onsite facilitator only twice a week in the classroom and working on the activities and assignments at my own place of choice (either in the learning center or at home) allows me to arrange my study time for the course more effectively.	BLF3
Satisfaction	
Overall, the blended learning course is enjoyable.	SAT1
Overall, the blended learning program is pleasant to me.	SAT2
This blended learning course gives me self confidence.	SAT3
Overall, the blended learning environment satisfies my educational needs.	SAT4
Intention	
If available, I intend to take more blended learning courses in the future.	INT1
I'm likely to attend another blended-learning course in the near future.	INT2
Do you have any further ideas how JWL Courses and Learning Platform can be improved? What kind of courses would you like to be offered to satisfy your learning needs? What needs to be improved on the learning platform? Your ideas and comments are highly appreciated.	INT3

11.2 Results of free responses

The numbers in brackets refer to the ID of survey participants. For every attempt to complete the survey a running number was assigned, which is the ID. Thus, the highest ID was 157, which anonymously characterizes the exact survey participant. This ID was used both here and in the text in brackets as a reference to indicate exactly where in the dataset the statement can be found. Of the 80 students who filled in the survey, 19 did not respond to this question and the remaining 61 wrote a comment in which they addressed success factors or suggested improvements to the system. The addressed aspects were then categorized. Since many statements also contain several aspects, they are also assigned to several categories. The ID in the brackets is therefore the unique way to identify the statement in the database.

Addressed Success Factors:	
IQ: (7x)	<p>(21) Programm is relevant for my learning</p> <p>(35) Ami kindly appreciate the important of JWL to engage us in skills and experience my opinion so since well and enjoying alat</p> <p>(54) It helps me a lot to improve my self-confidence.</p> <p>(57) if we know about the facilitators expectation only we can give our correct answer so if you include it will be good we have enough materials to do our assignments easily</p> <p>(106) The courses you offered gives one to know his/her identity. it led to have positive moral values in the community and outside therefore, you can be a good example for others especially youths who are addicted to drugs abuses. It help to gain knowledge and transform the society as an extra -curricular education . Help to express depression and can reaching to the solutions easily. It can be good if you offer higher education to widening the skills and become perfect intellectual so that to be easy in tackling tough conditions by helping those who are in depression.</p> <p>(141) First of all, I want to thank the JWL committee for providing us with such useful courses that help us to improve and expand our knowledge and understanding. All the courses are useful and needed for us to learn them.</p> <p>(153) By attending JWL Course and Learning Platform is very benefit , very helpful and improving by discovering about myself.</p>
MR: (6x)	<p>(18) Videos are more fun and understandable</p> <p>(28) Fully satisfied with my learning needs, sometimes reading is difficult</p> <p>(48) More videos would be great for my understanding</p> <p>(52) the books and Pdf its such old and boring style, (the videos of) Dr barbara make me get the idea in a few minutes that what attracts us more</p> <p>(81) Use more videos than PDFs, Reading cases is boring</p> <p>(127) Since its blending learning, there should be some more video and audio part in the portal ,it would be better and more helpful.</p>

SQ: (3x)	<p>(29) JWL learning platform is more useful for the students, who are living in the poor</p> <p>(127) The portal should be easy to understand, the learner could find every unit and detail easily.</p> <p>(70) The course and the platform is well designed only to say that it becomes hard when new students are starting the course because it the thing which we were not familiar with but as we keep on studying we get used and all goes smoothly.</p>
SVQ: (1x)	<p>(127) This learning program should have a guide or a demo how to use the material and portal.</p>
TM: (4x)	<p>(59) No time limit for Assignments to submit</p> <p>(85) Blended-learning approach makes me feel comfortable, confident and meets my learning needs</p> <p>(103) the program has a lot of impact on me. Its very effective and useful. I learned and also improved the way of teaching.</p> <p>(151) I like JWL courses and learning Porcess that is very effective and helps me to improve</p>
H: (6x)	<p>(37) You may gave us big lap top which are new.</p> <p>(38) Firstly, in order to improve JWL's learning platform we need to be given tablets or computers so that for is refugees it should be easier because we spend much time while trying to borrow smart phones or computers to use, so if we are provided with laptops or tables it can make our work easier.</p> <p>(51) There should be laptops or tablets available for these blended learning programs.</p> <p>(71) Treat everyone as equal. I mean when it comes to devices(computer, tablet and so on)</p> <p>(115) I think it would be better if your center provide a better internet connection.</p> <p>(140) If we could have the har of the reading or any tablet to watch the videos offline it will be great.</p>
FC- general (2x)	<p>(51) There should be active communication between Students and online facilitators because once we get stuck or have questions, we write questions to the online facilitators but no replies. It could be good to have feedback on each work submitted within a unit or week. Yet, weekly works which are to be marked by the online facilitators are delaying with marking them. We only get feedback from works which are under responsibility of the Onsite facilitator.</p>

	<p>(91) I can see my facilitator and classmates but one thing I would like to suggest that it would be better if we could have discussion face to face in the platforms with the specific time and schedule. Right now, we can communicate only by using text to reply and comment. We don't have the chance to see face to face and having verbal communication.</p>
FC- On-site (7x)	<p>(25) I am very happy to participate in this course. specially I am thankful from Ms. Shallyn. She is a very kind and understandable girl.</p> <p>(47) there is a suggestion that our onsite facilitator is very weak and doesn't have enough knowledge about the subject.</p> <p>(53) overall the course contents are good but the course facilitator didn't guide properly and for the first two weeks we were not aware of how to access the course contents therefore it created confusion and it caused the delay in submission of assignment and project work.</p> <p>(70) The course and the platform is well designed only to say that it becomes hard when new students are starting the course because it the thing which we were not familiar with but as we keep on studying we get used and all goes smoothly.</p> <p>(72) Moreover, the InClass meetings don't fulfil my learning expectations because everything discussed are quite basic in nature and nothing new is learned so far.</p> <p>(107) Advertisement is the best thinks for improve our course because here nobody not much know about this course</p> <p>(127) The facilitator should at least give a brief detail about how to use the material and portal. The facilitator should be helpful toward learners.</p>

FC- Online (5x)	<p>(29) what needs to be improved is the way of scoring the discussions and the feedback from the facilitator for each one</p> <p>(50) I would strongly suggest that there should be a team to check the knowledge of all the online facilitators before giving them a class to handle, as choosing weak online facilitator from the in charge centers can bring the quality of the lessons very low, and giving students bad learning experiences which will end up in not participating in the future learning courses.</p> <p>(64) I am really, grateful for this wonderful, and unforgettable casualty. My online facilitator Ms Tsoi should be appreciated and regarded, for the support she rendered.</p> <p>(73) what I wanted to ask if possible when marking our works if a person fails he or she needs your comment so that he may know what was the casuse of the failure.</p> <p>(139) There should be an active collaboration between students and online facilitators because they don't give feedback on weekly submitted works. students cannot be able to know if they are doing the works correctly.</p>
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